

Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 2935–3068

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Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Technical Report 0028

Cover photo

MAHLI view of a rock target named Achnasheen. Located on the lower north slope of Aeolis Mons, east of the south end of the Greenheugh pediment, this image was acquired on Sol 2965. Windblown sand fills fractures and lows on the rock surface. Illuminated by sunlight from the upper left, this is MAHLI image 2965MH0007060011004415C00.

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Acknowledgements

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Note that pages are not numbered in this document because all of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, and *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* were inserted separately after creation using a word processing tool that differs from the one used for the text.

Abstract

Covering the time between Curiosity’s 2935th and 3068th Martian days (sols) of operations in northern Gale crater, Mars, this document is a compilation of the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Principal Investigator’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities conducted during that period. The report includes brief sol-by-sol notes—written as the mission unfolded—regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used and significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation. The document, further, contains information regarding range and scale (camera working distance and scale of in-focus elements of an image); the parent images, range, and scale information associated with each MAHLI focus merge product created onboard the instrument; and a description of the purpose and intent behind acquisition of each MAHLI image and creation of each onboard focus merge product. The MSL science team and rover engineers routinely used the information contained in this report during the course of the mission for tactical planning, strategic planning, and scientific analysis.

DOI’s for MAHLI data archived with the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS)

MAHLI data product type	DOI	URL for DOI
EDR images	10.17189/1520187	https://doi.org/10.17189/1520187
EDR videos	10.17189/1520232	https://doi.org/10.17189/1520232
EDR focus merge products	10.17189/1520396	https://doi.org/10.17189/1520396
RDR images	10.17189/1520292	https://doi.org/10.17189/1520292
RDR videos	10.17189/1520222	https://doi.org/10.17189/1520222
RDR focus merge products	10.17189/1520169	https://doi.org/10.17189/1520169

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction and purpose

This document is a compilation of the Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Principal Investigator's notes and information about MAHLI images and activities that occurred during the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) mission between Sols 2935 and 3068.

MAHLI is a 2-megapixel color camera with a focusable macro lens mounted on the turret at the end of a robotic arm aboard NASA's MSL rover, Curiosity (Edgett *et al.* 2012). The rover landed and began operation in northern Gale crater, Mars, on 6 August 2012 (Vasavada *et al.* 2014).

Each *Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook* covers a specific period corresponding to a release of MAHLI data to the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) Imaging Node (see Table on previous page). As some MAHLI data can arrive from Mars months or years after a given release period, the publication of these reports typically lags behind the PDS release schedule by a period that varies from one occasion to the next, depending largely on when data acquired during that period arrive on Earth and when we have time to complete the *Principal Investigator's Notebook* report.

This report, *Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 2935–3068*, corresponds to MAHLI data Release 27 in the NASA PDS archives. These are data acquired 07 November 2020 through 24 March 2021.

1.2 Versions and change log

The enclosed materials were compiled as the MSL mission unfolded. That being the case, we might sometimes have made errors. The reader should be aware that this report might be corrected via release of a new version in the future.

A new version would also be created if new data from this report's period (Martian sols) are received from the instrument after an earlier version has been made available. This can occur because MAHLI can store data onboard the instrument for weeks, months, and even years after acquisition. As a result, images are archived with the NASA PDS on the basis of when they are received on Earth, not when they are acquired on Mars.

Covering the Sol 2935 through 3068 period, this document is Version 1.

If this were a later version, this section would document the changes made relative to the previous.

1.3 Changes beginning Sols 2959–2967 and 2989

This 28th MAHLI Technical Report features some changes relative to previous reports. These changes were implemented as we approached our 3000th sol as part of a larger effort to reduce labor cost. Labor cost includes the time and effort required to check for and correct errors. The changes implemented include using lowercase letters/words to describe each MAHLI item the Range and Scale information sheets, Focus Merge information sheets, and in the PDS comment (RATIONALE_DESC). The RATIONALE_DESC was further changed to shorten them and the practice of stating which APXS and ChemCam targets were included in a given MAHLI image was, unfortunately, abandoned. While we realize this latter practice reduces information content within the RATIONALE_DESC, this results in a useful labor cost savings. Labor costs become a premium as missions such as MSL are extended years beyond their original primary mission, and budgets to operate the instruments and spacecraft are reduced. Beginning at Sol 2989, we also changed the format of the Range and Scale information sheets, Focus Merge information sheets, and RATIONALE_DESC Comment sheets as part of our effort to reduce labor cost through simplification.

2 Instrument activities for this period

This section captures day-by-day or sol-by-sol notes written by the MAHLI PI and PI's assistants, as the mission unfolded, regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used or significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 2935 – 3068						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Drive through "The Benches"	08 Nov 20	2935	8	63	5	The REMS UV sensor was imaged to inspect dust accumulation. Then, MAHLI imaged the APXS targets Hunt_Hill and Muckle_Minn after Hunt_Hill was brushed by the DRT. Later, the focus stack images were merged.
	10–11 Nov 20	2938	3	23	2	MAHLI imaged the APXS target Hart_Fell after APXS acquired observations of and retracted from the target. Later, the focus stack images were merged.
	12–13 Nov 20	2940	3	23	2	MAHLI imaged the APXS target West_Loch after APXS acquired observations of and retracted from the target. Later, the focus stack images were merged.
	15 Nov 20	2942	8	72	0	MAHLI imaged the APXS targets St_Ninian and Geesa_Water.
	16 Nov 20	2943	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 2942 were merged.
	18 Nov 20	2945	10	72	6	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed APXS and ChemCam target Lasswade and the APXS and ChemCam target Ingliston. Later, the focus stack images were merged.
	22 Nov 20	2949	7	51	4	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed APXS and ChemCam target Giova which APXS investigated via a 2-spot raster. Later, the focus stack images were merged.
	24 Nov 20	2951	4	33	3	MAHLI imaged the target Saughieside_Hill after APXS acquired observations of and retracted from the target. Later, the focus stack images were merged.
Drive toward the Sands of Forvie	28 Nov 20	2955	12	57	4	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Rest_and_Be_Thankful which APXS investigated via a 2-spot raster. Next, wheel inspection images were obtained with the rover parked at one position. Later, the focus stack images were merged.
Drive toward the Sands of Forvie	02 Dec 20	2959	3	25	2	MAHLI imaged the APXS target Edinburrie after APXS acquired observations of and retracted from the target. Later, the focus stack images were merged.
	08 Dec 20	2965	3	23	2	MAHLI imaged the target Achnasheen and the focus stack images were merged.
	10 Dec 20	2967	3	25	2	MAHLI imaged the target Dun_Eideann and the focus stack images were merged.
	12 Dec 20	2969	7	61	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Coupar_Angus and Auchnafree_Hill.
	14 Dec 20	2970	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 2969 were merged.
	15 Dec 20	2972	3	23	2	MAHLI imaged the target Torness and the focus stack images were merged.
	18 Dec 20	2974	13	95	8	MAHLI imaged the targets An_Dun_Cod_Baa (before and after DRT), and Carn_Mor; later, the focus stack images were merged.
	20 Dec 20	2977	3	6	0	MAHLI imaged the target An_Dun with the dust cover closed due to restrictions on cover actuation for the December holiday stand-down period.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 2935 – 3068						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
At the Sands of Forvie eolian sand deposit	02 Jan 21	2989	6	48	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Ronas Hill and Braewick Beach at the Sands of Forvie.
	03 Jan 21	2990	5	11	0	The target Braewick Beach and the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets were imaged at the Sands of Forvie.
	04 Jan 21	2991	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 2989 were merged.
	05 Jan 21	2992	10	66	4	MAHLI imaged the targets Airor and Ratharsair at the Sands of Forvie campaign site and the focus stack images were merged.
	06 Jan 21	2993	4	26	2	MAHLI imaged the targets Ratharsair and Airor as well as the REMS UV sensor at the Sands of Forvie campaign site and the focus stack images were merged. MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 1 through 3926 (data from Sols 2592–2933) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA.
	07 Jan 21	2994	4	27	2	MAHLI imaged the targets Airor and Traquair at the Sands of Forvie campaign site and the focus stack images were merged.
	08 Jan 21	2995	1	2	0	MAHLI imaged the target Traquair at the Sands of Forvie campaign site.
Drive toward Mont Mercou	11 Jan 21	2998	0	0	6	The focus stack images from Sols 2992, 2993 and 2994 were merged again due to an arm fault on Sol 2996 which prevented acquisition of new MAHLI data.
	12 Jan 21	2999	4	8	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Kleber and Nugarth. MAHLI also imaged the wheel-surface interfaces of the two rover front wheels.
	17 Jan 21	3004	4	36	0	MAHLI imaged the target Tomb_of_the_Eagles.
	18 Jan 21	3005	20	20	3	MAHLI imaged $\geq 360^\circ$ of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel. The focus stack images from Sol 3004 were merged.
	20 Jan 21	3007	4	32	0	MAHLI imaged the target Easthouses.
	21 Jan 21	3008	0	0	3	Focus stack images from Sol 3007 were merged.
	24 Jan 21	3010	7	61	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT target La_Roque_Gageac and the target Gageac_et_Rouillac.
		3011	1	1	5	MAHLI imaged the left middle wheel and the focus stack images from Sol 3010 were merged.
	26–27 Jan 21	3013	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Champagnac and the focus stack images were merged.
	28–29 Jan 21	3015	4	36	3	MAHLI imaged the target Beaupouyet and the focus stack images were merged.
31 Jan 21	3017	5	54	0	MAHLI imaged a target named Neuvic after it was brushed by the DRT. After that, the robotic arm was positioned high above the rover and pointed southwestward, toward the Sands of Forvie sand sheet. There, it acquired a daylight context image of the scene, followed by 17 images (1 test set-up and 16 images commanded as video), at night, in an experiment to help constrain the upper threshold on whether saltating sands on Mars spark a visible triboelectric discharge (triboluminescence). The camera position for this was described by Edgett et al. (2012, https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-012-9910-4) as “periscope and giraffe’s eye view” – this is the first time it has been used since landing.	
Drive toward Mont Mercou	01 Feb 21	3018	0	0	3	The focus stack images from Sol 3017 were merged.
	03 Feb 21	3020	3	23	2	MAHLI imaged the target Lunas and the focus stack images were merged.
	05 Feb 21	3022	4	33	3	MAHLI imaged the target Tammies and the focus stack images were merged.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 2935 – 3068						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Drive toward Mont Mercou	07 Feb 21	3024	8	72	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT target Coutures and the target Biron.
	08 Feb 21	3025	0	0	6	The focus stack images from Sol 3024 were merged.
	09 Feb 21	3026	3	23	2	MAHLI imaged the target Labouquerie and the focus stack images were merged.
	10 Feb 21	3027	4	36	3	MAHLI imaged the target Brantome and the focus stack images were merged.
	11 Feb 21	3028	3	23	2	MAHLI imaged the target Firbeix and the focus stack images were merged.
	14 Feb 21	3031	5	47	4	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Dordogne and the focus stack images were merged.
	17 Feb 21	3034	8	53	4	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Limeyrat and the focus stack images were merged.
	18 Feb 21	3035	4	36	0	MAHLI imaged the target Fleurac.
	19 Feb 21	3036	3	15	4	MAHLI imaged the target Fleurac and the focus stack images from Sol 3035 and 3036 were merged.
	20 Feb 21	3037	5	47	4	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Chalus and the focus stack images were merged.
	23 Feb 21	3040	3	25	2	MAHLI imaged the target Plazac and the focus stack images were merged.
	25 Feb 21	3042	3	25	2	MAHLI imaged the target Manzac and the focus stack images were merged.
	27–28 Feb 21	3044	8	72	6	MAHLI imaged the targets Pazayac and Sadillac and the focus stack images were merged.
Drive toward Mont Mercou and Nontron drill site	02–03 Mar 21	3047	3	25	2	MAHLI imaged the target Daglan and the focus stack images were merged.
	04 Mar 21	3049	2	6	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Marval and Valojoux.
	07 Mar 21	3051	7	61	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT target Montrem and the target Peyrat.
	08 Mar 21	3052	0	0	5	The focus stack images from Sol 3051 were merged.
Nontron drill site	10 Mar 21	3054	8	53	4	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Nontron before and after DRT and a drill bit preload test; then the focus stack images were merged.
	12 Mar 21	3056	3	6	0	Drill preparation activities at the planned Nontron sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Nontron sample discard pile and the alternate and intended "Portion Characterization" sites.
	The Nontron sample was extracted using Curiosity's drill on Sol 3056 . The MAHLI was not operated during the period that the drill bit assembly held the sample until sample analyses were complete. The sample held by the drill bit assembly was discarded on Sol 3068 .					
	24 Mar 21	3068	6	13	0	MAHLI imaged the Nontron sample discard pile, the Nontron drill hole and the surfaces surrounding SAM inlet #1, with the inlet cover open, a follow-up to Nontron sample drop-offs.

3 Helpful tips

3.1 MAHLI instrument and investigation

Please refer to Edgett *et al.* (2012) for a description of the MAHLI instrument and investigation, Edgett *et al.* (2015) for information about the characterization and calibration of the instrument, and Yingst *et al.* (2016) for some of the lessons learned after ~1.5 Mars years of surface operations. Additional information on how the instrument and data have been used is in the paper by Minitti *et al.* (2013) and the extended abstract by Garvin *et al.* (2017).

3.2 MAHLI image IDs

MAHLI images and onboard focus merge products are identified by their image IDs. The following figure describes the information content of these IDs.

Note that raw images released within minutes of receipt on Earth to the public via the JPL-Caltech web site (<http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/>) do not necessarily have the correct, final, archival image IDs.

MAHLI Image IDs

The diagram illustrates the structure of a MAHLI Image ID: **0132MH0001580010101221C00**. Each digit is underlined, and arrows point from descriptive labels to the corresponding digits. The labels are: 'sol' (0), 'camera MH = MAHLI' (132), 'sequence ID' (000), 'order in sequence' (1), 'CDPID counter' (58001), 'CDPID a.k.a. MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID' (10101), 'GOP counter' (221), 'product type as received from Mars' (C), and 'version' (00). A note explains that for onboard focus merge products, the sol is the sol of the merge, not necessarily the parent images. Another note states that the MAHLI team prioritizes yellow items in a focus stack, acquired in order of increasing CDPID. A final note explains that the product type indicates the image as received from Mars, not necessarily the image being viewed, which may be further processed.

- This is the only official, correct, archival image ID scheme.
- Raw Images released rapidly at <http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/> do not always give you the correct, archival image ID.

Note that, for onboard focus merge products, the sol is the sol that the merge took place. This is **not** always on the same sol that the parent images were acquired.

The MAHLI team pays most attention to the items in yellow. In a focus stack, the images are acquired in order of increasing CDPID.

Product type tells you about the image as received from Mars; not necessarily the image you are looking at, if it has been further processed, uncompressed, or recompressed on Earth.

sol → 0

camera MH = MAHLI → 132

sequence ID → 000

order in sequence usually, first = 0, second = 1, etc. → 1

CDPID counter How many times the following CDPID has been used since landing → 58001

CDPID a.k.a. MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID → 10101

GOP counter for video Group of Pictures (JPEG video frames) → 221

product type as received from Mars → C

version version received on Earth 0 = parent image on Mars → 00

The NASA PDS archives include documentation that describes the MAHLI image ID and file naming scheme and the nature of the archived Experiment Data Record (EDR) and Reduced Data Record (RDR) products (Malin *et al.*, 2013).

The EDR products, the raw data product, have the following file name scheme:

- 1 **[Image ID]_XXXX** – these are always 8-bit images except for the 16-bit products (type A) returned from MAHLI for calibration purposes.

The RDR products are of the following nature:

- 2 **[Image ID]_DRXX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated color images,
- 3 **[Image ID]_DRLX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated and geometric calibrated color images,
- 4 **[Image ID]_DRCX** – 8-bit relative radiometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied, and
- 5 **[Image ID]_DRCL** – 8-bit relative radiometric and geometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied.

The following table describes the variety of image types (raw, lossless, JPEG, focus merge, thumbnail, *etc.*). Malin *et al.* (2013) described these in greater detail.

product type	product format
A	raster 16-bit image
B	raster 8-bit image
C	lossless compressed image
D	JPEG grayscale image
E	JPEG 4:2:2 color image
F	JPEG 4:4:4 color image
G	raster thumbnail of parent image
H	JPEG gray thumbnail of parent image
I	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of parent image
J	raster 8-bit video frame
K	lossless compressed video frame
L	JPEG grayscale video frame
M	JPEG 4:2:2 color video frame
N	JPEG 4:4:4 color video frame
O	raster 8-bit thumbnail of video frame
P	JPEG gray thumbnail of video frame
Q	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of video frame
R	focus merge best focus image product
S	focus merge range map product
T	focus merge best focus thumbnail
U	focus merge range map thumbnail

Types R and T are JPEG 4:4:4; S and U are JPEG grayscale products.

3.3 MAHLI LED positions

The MAHLI camera head has two groups of two white light LEDs (Edgett *et al.* 2012), called Group 1 and Group 2. For reference, the figure below shows their location on the camera head and how these locations translate to positions relative to pixel 0,0 (column 0, row 0) on the MAHLI CCD. In addition, MAHLI has two 365 nm ultraviolet (UV) LEDs, also shown in the figure. Each group of two LEDs (Group 1, Group 2, and UV) can be operated together or independently with each of the other two groups. When the LEDs are used, which group was operated is reported in the RATIONALE_DESC description of the image intent and purpose (**Section 6**).

MAHLI image TVC_MH0809080020000032B00, left, shows the violet and white reflections of the UV and Group 1 and Group 2 white light LEDs, indicating their location in relation to the CCD's pixel at column 0, row 0. The photograph on the right shows the camera head with its dust cover open and LEDs labeled.

4 Camera range and scale information

4.1 Purpose and description

MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* (or “Distance and Scale Information Sheets”) describe **(a)** the distance between the MAHLI camera and an imaged target, and **(b)** the scale of in-focus features in the image, based on knowledge of that distance. Usually, these are determined using the camera’s stepper motor count focus position (Edgett *et al.* 2015).

These information sheets were created only for cases in which there was a need. Cases for which they are not usually created include those when the only MAHLI image(s) acquired on a given sol are **(a)** views of the landscape, focused at infinity; **(b)** intended to make a rover self-portrait mosaic; **(c)** sky flat field calibration data; or **(d)** routinely-acquired images of the rover wheels for inspection purposes.

For the Sol 2935–3068 period, *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were created for the following **Sols: 2935, 2938, 2940, 2942, 2945, 2949, 2951, 2955, 2959, 2965, 2967, 2969, 2972, 2974, 2977, 2989, 2990, 2992, 2993, 2994, 2995, 2999, 3004, 3005, 3007, 3010, 3011, 3013, 3015, 3017, 3020, 3022, 3024, 3026, 3027, 3028, 3031, 3034, 3035, 3036, 3037, 3040, 3042, 3044, 3047, 3049, 3051, 3054, 3056, 3068.**

The origin of the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was in the need for a rapid, tactical response from the MAHLI team to the Curiosity Rover Planners—the engineers tasked with operating the rover’s mobility and robotic arm systems—for range-finding and image scale information derived from MAHLI’s autofocus and focus merge capabilities. As described by Minitti *et al.* (2013), during the rover’s first sample extraction campaign, conducted at the Rocknest eolian sand deposit in October–November 2012, the engineers elected to use MAHLI autofocus sub-frames to confirm their estimates of the range to the sand surface for subsequent scoop placement (Anderson *et al.* 2015). These *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were borne of that effort to provide the information almost as soon as the data arrived on Earth.

Presented in this section are the latest versions of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, for the above stated sols, as of the date of this *MAHLI Technical Report* publication. Most of these sheets were actively used during the MSL mission for tactical and strategic planning, as well as for the scientific analyses. Note that some of the sheets exhibit slightly different formatting from each other, as the formatting and content evolved over time.

The image IDs presented in these Information Sheets are the identifiers of the best, least-compressed version of the image received from Mars for a given camera position for the stated purpose (autofocus, imaging, range-finding, etc.). In cases for which only a thumbnail version of the image was received, the image ID is colored orange.

4.2 Formulae

4.2.1 Working distance

The working distance (d_w , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was computed from the empirical relationship between working distance and motor count for the flight unit MAHLI when the dust cover is open (m_{open}) described by Edgett *et al.* (2015):

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For the dust cover closed case (m_{closed}), Edgett *et al.* (2015) found that m_{closed} is related to m_{open} as follows:

$$m_{closed} = 17075 - m_{open}. \quad (2)$$

4.2.2 Standoff distance (RP distance; MAHLI toolframe +X distance)

The standoff distance (d_s , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* is 1.9 cm less than the MAHLI working distance (Edgett *et al.* 2015). Note that “standoff distance” is equivalent to “RP distance” and “MAHLI toolframe +X distance”; see **Section 7.1**). It is determined by subtracting 1.9 cm from the working distance (d_w) computed from motor count:

$$d_s = d_w - 1.9 \text{ cm} \quad (3)$$

4.2.3 Distance or range uncertainty estimate

Estimation approach applied to the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

For the Sol 0–945 period (except Sol 687), the uncertainty in distance (whether expressed as d_w or d_s) was estimated using an early version of our team’s understanding (Edgett *et al.* 2013) of the flight unit MAHLI depth of field (DOF; d_{old_DOF} , in centimeters) as a function of working distance (d_w).

The method for estimating the far range of the DOF, d_{old_far} , was:

$$d_{old_far} = ad_w^5 - bd_w^4 + cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 + ed_w - f \quad (4)$$

in which $a = 2.067963396 \times 10^{-10}$, $b = 5.81503025785 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 1.55563715379086 \times 10^{-5}$, $d = 1.78558768966003 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 7.87243271888297 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 3.57047935299353 \times 10^{-2}$.

The method for estimating the near range of the DOF, d_{old_near} , was:

$$d_{old_near} = -(ad_w^5 + bd_w^4 - cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 - ed_w + f) \quad (5)$$

in which $a = -9.6497783 \times 10^{-12}$, $b = 1.06050131902 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 5.8615047292452 \times 10^{-6}$, $d = 2.42284468424977 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 4.28714139095939 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 7.534391000189 \times 10^{-4}$.

The MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* added the absolute values of the near and far DOF, then divided by two, to provide an overall uncertainty, $\pm d_{old_DOF}$, in centimeters:

$$\pm d_{old_DOF} = ((-d_{old_near}) + d_{old_far})/2 \quad (6)$$

The $\pm d_{old_DOF}$ estimate was sufficient for using MAHLI as a range finder for subsequent scoop placement during the Rocknest sample extraction campaign (Minitti *et al.* 2013; Anderson *et al.* 2015).

Improved estimation method, used for Sol 687 and after Sol 945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

Later analysis refined our DOF estimate (Edgett *et al.* 2015), but these results arrived too late to be incorporated into most of the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*. That said, for small working distances (e.g., < 20 cm), the results are about the same. As a function of dust cover open focus motor count (m_{open}), the near (d_{near}) and far (d_{far}) depth of field can be expressed, in centimeters, as:

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

in which, for d_{near} , $a = 1.03565$, $b = -11.9083$, $c = 2.82403 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.29003 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.34332 \times 10^{-12}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 1.03438$, $b = -11.4118$, $c = 2.69297 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.17752 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.02494 \times 10^{-12}$.

4.2.4 Pixel scale

The estimated pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel) is based on working distance (d_w) and applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. We estimate the scale from the working distance (d_w) as described by Edgett *et al.* (2012):

$$p = 6.9001 + 3.5201d_w. \quad (8)$$

4.2.5 Pixel scale uncertainty estimate

No estimation applied to the Sol 0–998 range and scale information sheets

No estimate of pixel scale uncertainty was applied to the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* until Sol 999.

Estimation approach

Pixel scale uncertainty (p_{far} , p_{near} , $\pm p_{uncertainty}$, in μm per pixel) can be estimated based on the depth of field (d_{far} , d_{near} , in centimeters; **Equation 7**) and pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel, **Equation 8**) as determined from working distance (d_w , in centimeters; **Equation 1**). The uncertainty applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. The uncertainty can be estimated as follows (please round $\pm p_{uncertainty}$ to the nearest 0.1 μm per pixel):

$$p_{far} = (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{far})) - p, \quad (9)$$

$$p_{near} = p - (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{near})), \text{ and} \quad (10)$$

$$\pm p_{uncertainty} = (p_{far} + p_{near})/2. \quad (11)$$

4.2.6 Image dimensions estimate

The image dimension estimates described in the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* are computed by multiplying the estimated pixel scale (p) by the number of horizontal (columns) and vertical (rows) covered by the image. This simplistic approach, of course, assumes that the target is a plane parallel to the CCD.

updated: 10_November_2020

Sol 2935 - MAHLI Image Range and Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not list and describe all images, it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working Distance is a photography term; it is the distance from front of front lens element (the sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff (RP Distance) = MAHLI Tool Frame + X distance; measured from plane defined by tips of MAHLI Contact Sensor Probes to target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations in Edgett et al. (2015; doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447)

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance (cm) from Motor Count	Standoff (cm) (RP Distance) (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count	Depth of Field (range uncertainty estimate) based on working distance		Pixel Scale from Working Distance (µm/pixel) based on working distance	Pixel Scale Uncertainty ± estimate based on Depth of Field estimate (µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate) based on pixel scale	
						DOF near (cm)	DOF far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

REMS UV Sensor - dust accumulation monitoring

mhli00095	Standard viewing position	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~15 cm		2 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2935MH0000950011003928C00	3928	13260	16.7	14.8	-0.7	0.8	65.7	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9

Target named Hunt_Hill (a.k.a. Hunt_Hill_RP) - After DRT - APXS target

mhli00706	Context view	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~25 cm		3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2935MH0007060011003930C00	3930	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00763	Medium Resolution Stereo-1	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2935MH0007630011003933C00	3933	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2935MH0002270001003998R00		<i>range map product:</i> 2935MH0002270001003999S00							
mhli00763	Medium Resolution Stereo-2	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2935MH0007630011003944C00	3944	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2935MH0002270001003996R00		<i>range map product:</i> 2935MH0002270001003997S00							
mhli00732	High Resolution view	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~2 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2935MH0007320011003955C00	3955	14689	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2935MH0002270001003994R00		<i>range map product:</i> 2935MH0002270001003995S00							

Target named Muckle_Minn (a.k.a. Muckle_Minn_RP) - APXS target

mhli00706	Context view	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~25 cm		3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2935MH0007060011003966C00	3966	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
mhli00721	Medium Resolution Stereo-1	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2935MH0007210011003969C00	3969	13979	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2935MH0002270001003992R00		<i>range map product:</i> 2935MH0002270001003993S00							
mhli00721	Medium Resolution Stereo-2	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2935MH0007210011003980C00	3980	13974	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2935MH0002270001003990R00		<i>range map product:</i> 2935MH0002270001003991S00							

updated: 11_November_2020

Sol 2938 - MAHLI Image Range and Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not list and describe all images, it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working Distance is a photography term; it is the distance from front of front lens element (the sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff (RP Distance) = MAHLI Tool Frame +X distance; measured from plane defined by tips of MAHLI Contact Sensor Probes to target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations in Edgett *et al.* (2015; doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447)

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance (cm) from Motor Count	Standoff (cm) (RP Distance) (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count	Depth of Field (range uncertainty estimate) based on working distance		Pixel Scale from Working Distance (µm/pixel) based on working distance	Pixel Scale Uncertainty ± estimate based on Depth of Field estimate (µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate) based on pixel scale	
						DOF near (cm)	DOF far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Target named **Hart_Fell** (a.k.a. **Hart_Fell_rp**) - after APXS retraction

mhli00706	Context view	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~25 cm		3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2938MH0007060011004001C00	4001	13010	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2
mhli00173	Medium Resolution Stereo-1	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		10 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2938MH0001730011004004C00	4004	13929	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>		2938MH0002650001004025R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2938MH0002650001004026S00					
mhli00173	Medium Resolution Stereo-2	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		10 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2938MH0001730011004014C00	4014	13936	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>		2938MH0002650001004023R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2938MH0002650001004024S00					

updated: 13_November_2020

Sol 2940 - MAHLI Image Range and Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not list and describe all images, it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working Distance is a photography term; it is the distance from front of front lens element (the sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff (RP Distance) = MAHLI Tool Frame +X distance; measured from plane defined by tips of MAHLI Contact Sensor Probes to target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations in Edgett *et al.* (2015; doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447)

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance (cm) from Motor Count	Standoff (cm) (RP Distance) (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count	Depth of Field (range uncertainty estimate) based on working distance		Pixel Scale from Working Distance (µm/pixel) based on working distance	Pixel Scale Uncertainty ± estimate based on Depth of Field estimate (µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate) based on pixel scale	
						DOF near (cm)	DOF far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Target named **West_Loch** (a.k.a. **West_Loch_rp**) - after APXS retraction

mhli00706	Context view	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~25 cm		3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2940MH0007060011004028C00	4028	13012	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.1	101.3	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1
mhli00299	Medium Resolution Stereo-1	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		10 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2940MH0002990011004031C00	4031	14026	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>		2940MH0002650001004052R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2940MH0002650001004053S00					
mhli00299	Medium Resolution Stereo-2	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		10 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2940MH0002990011004041C00	4041	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>		2940MH0002650001004050R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2940MH0002650001004051S00					

updated: 16_November_2020

Sol 2942 - MAHLI Image Range and Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not list and describe all images, it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working Distance is a photography term; it is the distance from front of front lens element (the sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff (RP Distance) = MAHLI Tool Frame +X distance; measured from plane defined by tips of MAHLI Contact Sensor Probes to target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations in Edgett *et al.* (2015; doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447)

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance (cm) from Motor Count	Standoff (cm) (RP Distance) (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count	Depth of Field (range uncertainty estimate) based on working distance		Pixel Scale from Working Distance (µm/pixel) based on working distance	Pixel Scale Uncertainty ± estimate based on Depth of Field estimate (µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate) based on pixel scale	
						DOF near (cm)	DOF far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Target named **St_Ninian** (a.k.a. **St_Ninian_rp**) - APXS target

mhl00706	Context view	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~25 cm		3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2942MH0007060011004055C00	4055	13009	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2
mhl00709	Medium Resolution Stereo-1	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2942MH0007090011004058C00	4058	13950	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2943MH0001630001004136R00				<i>range map product:</i>		2943MH0001630001004137S00			
mhl00709	Medium Resolution Stereo-2	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2942MH0007090011004069C00	4069	13949	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2943MH0001630001004134R00				<i>range map product:</i>		2943MH0001630001004135S00			
mhl00795	High Resolution view	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~2 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2942MH0007950011004080C00	4080	14602	4.1	2.2	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2943MH0001630001004132R00				<i>range map product:</i>		2943MH0001630001004133S00			

Target named **Geesa_Water** (a.k.a. **Geesa_Water_rp**) - APXS target

mhl00706	Context view	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~25 cm		3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2942MH0007060011004091C00	4091	13010	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2
mhl00803	Medium Resolution Stereo-1	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2942MH0008030011004094C00	4094	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2943MH0001630001004130R00				<i>range map product:</i>		2943MH0001630001004131S00			
mhl00803	Medium Resolution Stereo-2	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2942MH0008030011004105C00	4105	13983	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2943MH0001630001004128R00				<i>range map product:</i>		2943MH0001630001004129S00			
mhl00795	High Resolution view	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~2 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2942MH0007950011004116C00	4116	14730	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2943MH0001630001004126R00				<i>range map product:</i>		2943MH0001630001004127S00			

updated: 30_November_2020

Sol 2955 - MAHLI Image Range and Scale Information*

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not list and describe all images, it describes each camera positioning.
Working Distance is a photography term; it is the distance from front of front lens element (the sapphire window) to the target.
Standoff (RP Distance) = MAHLI Tool Frame + X distance; measured from plane defined by tips of MAHLI Contact Sensor Probes to target.
Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations in Edgett et al. (2015; doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447)

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance (cm) from Motor Count	Standoff (cm) (RP Distance) (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count	Depth of Field (range uncertainty estimate) based on working distance		Pixel Scale from Working Distance (µm/pixel) based on working distance	Pixel Scale Uncertainty ± estimate based on Depth of Field estimate (µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate) based on pixel scale	
						DOF near (cm)	DOF far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Target named Rest and Be Thankful (a.k.a. Rest and Be Thankful_rp) - After DRT - APXS Spot 2 - QRM

mhl00706	Context view	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~25 cm		3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2955MH0007060011004321C00	4321	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00699	Med. Res. Stereo-1 Relief Model Position 1	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2955MH0006990011004324C00	4324	14005	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		2955MH0001530001004383R00		range map product: 2955MH0001530001004384S00							
mhl00699	Med. Res. Stereo-2 Relief Model Position 2	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2955MH0006990011004335C00	4335	14012	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		2955MH0001530001004381R00		range map product: 2955MH0001530001004382S00							
mhl00705	Med. Res. Relief Model Position 3	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		2 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2955MH0007050011004346C00	4346	14005	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl00705	Med. Res. Relief Model Position 4	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		2 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2955MH0007050011004348C00	4348	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl00705	Med. Res. Relief Model Position 5	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		2 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2955MH0007050011004350C00	4350	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl00744	High Resolution view	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~2 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2955MH0007440011004352C00	4352	15124	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		2955MH0001530001004379R00		range map product: 2955MH0001530001004380S00							

Target named Rest and Be Thankful (a.k.a. Rest and Be Thankful_rp) - After DRT - APXS Spot 1

mhl00699	Medium Resolution view	intended Standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2955MH0006990011004363C00	4363	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		2955MH0001530001004377R00		range map product: 2955MH0001530001004378S00							

Rover Wheel Inspection - Top view, looking down on wheels

mhl00769	Left (Port) Rear Wheel	intended dist. to top of wheel: ~170 cm		1 images: 0 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2955MH0007690011004373E01	4373	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	Left (Port) Middle Wheel	intended dist. to top of wheel: ~112 cm		1 images: 0 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2955MH0007700011004374E01	4374	12660	~114	~112	~28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	Left (Port) Front Wheel	intended dist. to top of wheel: ~135 cm		1 images: 0 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2955MH0007710011004375E01	4375	12642	~137	~135	~38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	Right (Starboard) Front Wheel	intended dist. to top of wheel: ~124 cm		1 images: 0 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2955MH0007720011004376E01	4376	12648	~126	~124	~32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

updated: 02_December_2020

Sol 2959 - MAHLI Image Range and Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not list and describe all images, it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working Distance is a photography term; it is the distance from front of front lens element (the sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff (RP Distance) = MAHLI Tool Frame +X distance; measured from plane defined by tips of MAHLI Contact Sensor Probes to target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations in Edgett *et al.* (2015; doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447)

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance (cm) from Motor Count	Standoff (cm) (RP Distance) (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count	Depth of Field (range uncertainty estimate) based on working distance		Pixel Scale from Working Distance (µm/pixel) based on working distance	Pixel Scale Uncertainty ± estimate based on Depth of Field estimate (µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate) based on pixel scale	
						DOF near (cm)	DOF far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Edinburrie** (a.k.a. **Edinburrie_rp**) - after APXS retraction

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff (RP distance) ~25 cm		3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2959MH0007060011004386C00	4386	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
mhli00763	medium resolution stereo-1	intended standoff (RP distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2959MH0007630011004389C00	4389	14022	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>		2959MH0002650001004412R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2959MH0002650001004413S00					
mhli00763	medium resolution stereo-2	intended standoff (RP distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2959MH0007630011004400C00	4400	14024	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>		2959MH0002650001004410R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2959MH0002650001004411S00					

updated: 08_December_2020

Sol 2965 - MAHLI Image Range and Scale Information*

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not list and describe all images, it describes each camera positioning.
 Working Distance is a photography term; it is the distance from front of front lens element (the sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff (RP Distance) = MAHLI Tool Frame +X distance; measured from plane defined by tips of MAHLI Contact Sensor Probes to target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations in Edgett *et al.* (2015; doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447)

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance (cm) from Motor Count	Standoff (cm) (RP Distance) (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count	Depth of Field (range uncertainty estimate) based on working distance		Pixel Scale from Working Distance (µm/pixel) based on working distance	Pixel Scale Uncertainty ± estimate based on Depth of Field estimate (µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate) based on pixel scale	
						DOF near (cm)	DOF far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Achnasheen**

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff (RP distance) ~25 cm		3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2965MH0007060011004415C00	4415	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00182	medium resolution stereo-1	intended standoff (RP distance) ~5 cm		10 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2965MH0001820011004418C00	4418	14037	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>		2965MH0002650001004439R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2965MH0002650001004440S00					
mhli00182	medium resolution stereo-2	intended standoff (RP distance) ~5 cm		10 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2965MH0001820011004428C00	4428	14043	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>		2965MH0002650001004437R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2965MH0002650001004438S00					

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2967 - MAHLI Image Range and Scale Information*

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not list and describe all images, it describes each camera positioning.
 Working Distance is a photography term; it is the distance from front of front lens element (the sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff (RP Distance) = MAHLI Tool Frame +X distance; measured from plane defined by tips of MAHLI Contact Sensor Probes to target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations in Edgett *et al.* (2015; doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447)

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance (cm) from Motor Count	Standoff (cm) (RP Distance) (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count	Depth of Field (range uncertainty estimate) based on working distance		Pixel Scale from Working Distance (µm/pixel) based on working distance	Pixel Scale Uncertainty ± estimate based on Depth of Field estimate (µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate) based on pixel scale	
						DOF near (cm)	DOF far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Dun_Eideann**

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff (RP distance) ~25 cm		3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2967MH0007060011004442C00	4442	13011	26.9	25.0	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.2
mhli00723	medium resolution stereo-1	intended standoff (RP distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2967MH0007230011004445C00	4445	13986	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>		2967MH0002650001004468R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2967MH0002650001004469S00					
mhli00723	medium resolution stereo-2	intended standoff (RP distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2967MH0007230011004456C00	4456	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>		2967MH0002650001004466R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2967MH0002650001004467S00					

updated: 14_December_2020

Sol 2969 - MAHLI Image Range and Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not list and describe all images, it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working Distance is a photography term; it is the distance from front of front lens element (the sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff (RP Distance) = MAHLI Tool Frame +X distance; measured from plane defined by tips of MAHLI Contact Sensor Probes to target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations in Edgett et al. (2015; doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447)

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance (cm) from Motor Count	Standoff (cm) (RP Distance) (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count	Depth of Field (range uncertainty estimate) based on working distance		Pixel Scale from Working Distance (µm/pixel) based on working distance	Pixel Scale Uncertainty ± estimate based on Depth of Field estimate (µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate) based on pixel scale	
						DOF near (cm)	DOF far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Coupar_Angus**

mhli00706	context view			intended standoff (RP Distance) ~25 cm	3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images								
	2969MH0007060011004471C00	4471	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00699	medium resolution stereo-1			intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm	11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images								
	2969MH0006990011004474C00	4474	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 2970MH0002270001004539R00				<i>range map product:</i> 2970MH0002270001004540S00					
mhli00699	medium resolution stereo-2			intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm	11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images								
	2969MH0006990011004485C00	4485	14011	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
		<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 2970MH0002270001004537R00				<i>range map product:</i> 2970MH0002270001004538S00					
mhli00813	high resolution view			intended standoff (RP Distance) ~2 cm	11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images								
	2969MH0008130011004496C00	4496	14706	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
		<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 2970MH0002270001004535R00				<i>range map product:</i> 2970MH0002270001004536S00					

target named **Auchnafree_Hill**

mhli00706	context view			intended standoff (RP Distance) ~25 cm	3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images								
	2969MH0007060011004507C00	4507	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00699	medium resolution stereo-1			intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm	11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images								
	2969MH0006990011004510C00	4510	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 2970MH0002270001004533R00				<i>range map product:</i> 2970MH0002270001004534S00					
mhli00699	medium resolution stereo-2			intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm	11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images								
	2969MH0006990011004521C00	4521	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 2970MH0002270001004531R00				<i>range map product:</i> 2970MH0002270001004532S00					

updated: 18_December_2020

Sol 2974 - MAHLI Image Range and Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not list and describe all images, it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working Distance is a photography term; it is the distance from front of front lens element (the sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff (RP Distance) = MAHLI Tool Frame +X distance; measured from plane defined by tips of MAHLI Contact Sensor Probes to target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations in Edgett et al. (2015; doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447)

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance (cm) from Motor Count	Standoff (cm) (RP Distance) (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count	Depth of Field (range uncertainty estimate) based on working distance		Pixel Scale from Working Distance (µm/pixel) based on working distance	Pixel Scale Uncertainty ± estimate based on Depth of Field estimate (µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate) based on pixel scale	
						DOF near (cm)	DOF far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named An_Dun

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff (RP Distance) ~25 cm		2 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2974MH0001900011004569C00	4569	13030	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
mhli00224	medium resolution stereo-1	intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		10 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2974MH0002240011004571C00	4571	14157	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.5	3.3
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 2974MH0001700000904677R00		range map product: 2974MH0001700000904678S00							
mhli00244	medium resolution stereo-2	intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		10 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2974MH0002240011004581C00	4581	14143	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 2974MH0001700000904675R00		range map product: 2974MH0001700000904676S00							

target named Cod_Baa - before DRT

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff (RP Distance) ~25 cm		2 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2974MH0001900011004591C00	4591	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.8	2.0	99.6	6.6	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00122	medium resolution view	intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		2 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2974MH0001220011004593C00	4593	14037	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6

target named Cod_Baa - after DRT

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff (RP Distance) ~25 cm		3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2974MH0007060011004595C00	4595	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00699	medium resolution stereo-1	intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2974MH0006990011004598C00	4598	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 2974MH0001700000904673R00		range map product: 2974MH0001700000904674S00							
mhli00699	medium resolution stereo-2	intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2974MH0006990011004609C00	4609	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 2974MH0001700000904671R00		range map product: 2974MH0001700000904672S00							
mhli00744	high resolution view	intended standoff (RP Distance) ~1 cm		11 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2974MH0007440011004620C00	4620	15117	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 2974MH0001700000904669R00		range map product: 2974MH0001700000904670S00							

target named Carn_Mor

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff (RP Distance) ~25 cm		3 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 2 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images									
	2974MH0007060011004631C00	4631	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.8	2.0	99.6	6.6	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00182	medium resolution stereo-1	intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		10 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2974MH0001820011004634C00	4634	14035	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 2974MH0001700000904667R00		range map product: 2974MH0001700000904668S00							
mhli00182	medium resolution stereo-2	intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm		10 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2974MH0001820011004644C00	4644	14041	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 2974MH0001700001004665R00		range map product: 2974MH0001700000904666S00							
mhli00184	high resolution view	intended standoff (RP Distance) ~2 cm		10 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 8 relative focus stack images									
	2974MH0001840011004654C00	4654	14754	3.6	1.7	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 2974MH0001700001004663R00		range map product: 2974MH0001700001004664S00							

updated: 22_December_2020

Sol 2977 - MAHLI Image Range and Scale Information*

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not list and describe all images, it describes each camera positioning.
 Working Distance is a photography term; it is the distance from front of front lens element (the sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff (RP Distance) = MAHLI Tool Frame +X distance; measured from plane defined by tips of MAHLI Contact Sensor Probes to target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations in Edgett *et al.* (2015; doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447)

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance (cm) from Motor Count	Standoff (cm) (RP Distance) (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count	Depth of Field (range uncertainty estimate) based on working distance		Pixel Scale from Working Distance (µm/pixel) based on working distance	Pixel Scale Uncertainty ± estimate based on Depth of Field estimate (µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate) based on pixel scale	
						DOF near (cm)	DOF far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **An_Dun** - dust cover closed

Note: Where the Motor Count is given in blue font, that means the dust cover was closed; please use caution in interpreting the range and scale information, as the results are less certain.

mhli00553	medium resolution APXS spot 1	<i>intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm</i>	2 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images										
	2977MH0005530010904680C00	4680	3284	8.4	6.5	-0.2	0.2	36.6	0.8	1608	1198	5.9	4.4
mhli00553	medium resolution APXS spot 2	<i>intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm</i>	2 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images										
	2977MH0005530010904682C00	4682	3272	8.3	6.4	-0.2	0.2	36.3	0.8	1608	1198	5.8	4.3
mhli00553	medium resolution APXS spot 3	<i>intended standoff (RP Distance) ~5 cm</i>	2 images: 1 a.f. sub-frame(s), 1 full-frame(s), 0 focus stack images										
	2977MH0005530010904684C00	4684	3297	8.6	6.7	-0.2	0.2	37.1	0.8	1608	1198	6.0	4.4

Sol 2989 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information*

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (μm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± μm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Ronas_Hill

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	2989MH0007060010904686C00	4686	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	2989MH0001730010904689C00	4689	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	2991MH0008170000704750R00					range map product:							2991MH0008170000704751S00
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	2989MH0001730010904699C00	4699	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	2991MH0008170000704748R00					range map product:							2991MH0008170000704749S00

target named Braewick_Beach

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	2989MH0007060010904709C00	4709	13007	27.1	25.2	-1.9	2.1	102.4	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3		
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	2989MH0007630010904712C00	4712	13905	7.5	5.6	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.4	4.0		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	2991MH0008170000704746R00					range map product:							2991MH0008170000704747S00
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	2989MH0007630010904723C00	4723	13922	7.4	5.5	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	2991MH0008170000704744R00					range map product:							2991MH0008170000704745S00

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 2990 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information*

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHU front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHU contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (μm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± μm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Braewick_Beach

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (μm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± μm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhl00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	2990MH0001220010904734C00	4734	13913	7.5	5.6	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	4.0

MAHLI calibration target

Note: one can also use features in these images to determine scale; the scale information presented here is based on motor count, not analysis of the images.

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (μm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± μm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhl00371	bar target - 5 cm working distance												
	2990MH0003710010804736C00	4736	14367	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl00372	cent target - 5 cm working distance												
	2990MH0003720010704738C00	4738	14360	5.0	3.1	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl00374	calibration target + front left wheel + surface - 30 cm working distance												
	autofocus on calibration target												
	2990MH0003740010704740C00	4740	12961	30.4	28.5	-2.3	2.7	113.8	8.7	1608	1198	18.3	13.6
	manual infinity focus												
	2990MH0003740020704741C00	4741	12552	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	1608	1198	(infinity)	(infinity)

APXS calibration target

Note: one can also use features in the image(s) to determine scale; the scale information presented here is based on motor count, not analysis of the image(s).

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (μm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± μm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhl00373	6.9 cm working distance												
	2990MH0003730010704743C00	4743	13942	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

Sol 2992 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Airor - bedform crest**

mhl00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	2992MH0001970010704753C00	4753	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl00676	medium resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	first range-finding sub-frame (centered; starting pixel 752, 544)												
	2992MH000676000704754C00	4754	14129	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	128	128	0.4	0.4
	full frame, focus based on first range-finding subframe												
	2992MH0006760010704755C00	4755	14129	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4
	second range-finding sub-frame (starting pixel 576, 544)												
	2992MH0006760020704756C00	4756	14104	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	128	128	0.4	0.4
	third range-finding sub-frame (starting pixel 928, 544)												
	2992MH0006760030704757C00	4757	14153	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	128	128	0.4	0.4
	fourth range-finding sub-frame (starting pixel 752, 368)												
2992MH0006760040704758C00	4758	14146	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	128	128	0.4	0.4	
fifth range-finding sub-frame (starting pixel 752, 720)													
2992MH0006760050704759C00	4759	14117	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	128	128	0.4	0.4	

target named **Ratharsair - bedform trough**

mhl00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	2992MH0001970010704761C00	4761	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl00676	medium resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	first range-finding sub-frame (centered; starting pixel 752, 544)												
	2992MH000676000704762C00	4762	14089	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	128	128	0.4	0.4
	full frame, focus based on first range-finding subframe												
	2992MH0006760010604763C00	4763	14089	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5
	second range-finding sub-frame (starting pixel 576, 544)												
	2992MH0006760020604764C00	4764	14103	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	128	128	0.4	0.4
	third range-finding sub-frame (starting pixel 928, 544)												
	2992MH0006760030604765C00	4765	14073	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.4	0.5	128	128	0.4	0.4
	fourth range-finding sub-frame (starting pixel 752, 368)												
2992MH0006760040604766C00	4766	14088	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	128	128	0.4	0.4	
fifth range-finding sub-frame (starting pixel 752, 720)													
2992MH0006760050604767C00	4767	14096	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	128	128	0.4	0.4	

target named **Airor - bedform crest**

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	2992MH0007060010604769C00	4769	13027	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.8		
mhl00721	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	2992MH0007210010604772C00	4772	14184	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		2992MH0007070000604824R00				range map product:						2992MH0007070000604825S00	
mhl00721	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	2992MH0007210010604783C00	4783	14181	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		2992MH0007070000604822R00				range map product:						2992MH0007070000604823S00	

target named **Ratharsair - bedform trough**

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	2992MH0007060010604794C00	4794	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7		
mhl00723	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	2992MH0007230010604797C00	4797	14126	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		2992MH0007070000604820R00				range map product:						2992MH0007070000604821S00	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		2998MH0001630001100050R00				range map product:						2998MH0001630001100051S00	
mhl00723	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	2992MH0007230010604808C00	4808	14121	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		2992MH0007070000604818R00				range map product:						2992MH0007070000604819S00	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		2998MH0001630001100048R00				range map product:						2998MH0001630001100049S00	

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 2993 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)		

target named Ratharsair - bedform trough

target named Ratharsair - bedform trough													
mhli00122	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	2993MH0001220010604827C00	4827	14038	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
mhli00746	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	2993MH0007460010604829C00	4829	14760	3.6	1.7	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2993MH0007030001100005R00				<i>range map product:</i>		2993MH0007030001100006S00		
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2998MH0001630001100046R00				<i>range map product:</i>		2998MH0001630001100047S00			

target named Airor - bedform crest

target named Airor - bedform crest													
mhli00794	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	2993MH0007940010504840C00	4840	15206	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2993MH0007030001100003R00				<i>range map product:</i>		2993MH0007030001100004S00			
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2998MH0001630001100044R00				<i>range map product:</i>		2998MH0001630001100045S00			

REMS UV sensor

REMS UV sensor													
mhli00095	standard viewing position		intended standoff: ~15 cm										
	2993MH0000950011100002C00	2	13260	16.7	14.8	-0.7	0.8	65.7	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 2994 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named *Airor* - bedform crest

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00122	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	2994MH0001220011100008C00	8	14036	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6

target named *Traquair* - small bedform crest

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	2994MH0007060011100010C00	10	13023	26.2	24.3	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	1608	1198	15.9	11.9
mhli00740	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	2994MH0007400011100013C00	13	14091	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2994MH0007030001100036R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2994MH0007030001100037S00				
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2998MH0001630001100042R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2998MH0001630001100043S00				
mhli00740	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	2994MH0007400011100024C00	24	14103	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2994MH0007030001100034R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2994MH0007030001100035S00				
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		2998MH0001630001100040R00		<i>range map product:</i>		2998MH0001630001100041S00				

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 2995 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Traquair - small bedform crest

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhl00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	2995MH0001220011100039C00	39	13944	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

last update: 30_June_2021

Sol 2999 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Kleber

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	2999MH0007060011100053C00	53	13001	27.5	25.6	-1.9	2.2	103.8	7.2	1608	1198	16.7	12.4

target named Nugarth

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	2999MH0007060011100056C00	56	13006	27.2	25.3	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3

inspect front rover wheel/surface interfaces

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhl00259	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to wheel-surface interface: ~140 cm											
	2999MH0002590001100058C00	58	12660	~113	~111	~-27	~50	~400	~135	1608	1198	~64	~48
mhl00262	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to wheel-surface interface: ~112 cm											
	2999MH0002620001100059C00	59	12660	~113	~111	~-27	~50	~400	~135	1608	1198	~64	~48

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3004 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Tomb_of_the_Eagles**

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3004MH0007060011100061C00	61	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3004MH0007630011100064C00	64	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3005MH0001930001100120R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3005MH0001930001100121S00						
mhl00763	medium-r resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3004MH0007630011100075C00	75	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3005MH0001930001100118R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3005MH0001930001100119S00						
mhl00801	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm											
	3004MH0008010011100086C00	86	15117	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3005MH0001930001100116R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3005MH0001930001100117S00						

Sol 3005 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 1 of 5 (performed on sol 3005)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	3005MH0007690011100096E01	96	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	3005MH0007700011100097E01	97	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	3005MH0007710011100098E01	98	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	3005MH0007720011100099E01	99	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 2 of 5 (performed on sol 3005)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	3005MH0007690011100100E01	100	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	3005MH0007700011100101E01	101	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	3005MH0007710011100102E01	102	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	3005MH0007720011100103E01	103	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 3 of 5 (performed on sol 3005)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	3005MH0007690011100104E01	104	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	3005MH0007700011100105E01	105	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	3005MH0007710011100106E01	106	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	3005MH0007720011100107E01	107	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 4 of 5 (performed on sol 3005)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	3005MH0007690011100108E01	108	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	3005MH0007700011100109E01	109	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	3005MH0007710011100110E01	110	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	3005MH0007720011100111E01	111	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

Continued on Next Page...

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 5 of 5 (performed on sol 3005)													
mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	3005MH0007690011100112E01	112	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	3005MH0007700011100113E01	113	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	3005MH0007710011100114E01	114	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	3005MH0007720011100115E01	115	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3007 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Easthouses															
mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3007MH0001900011100123C00	123	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhli00297	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3007MH0002970011100125C00	125	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3008MH0001930001100158R00				range map product:						3008MH0001930001100159S00	
mhli00297	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3007MH0002970011100135C00	135	14005	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3008MH0001930001100156R00				range map product:						3008MH0001930001100157S00	
mhli00297	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3007MH0002970011100145C00	145	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3008MH0001930001100154R00				range map product:						3008MH0001930001100155S00	

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3010 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **La_Roque_Gageac - after DRT**

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3010MH0007060011100161C00	161	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3010MH0006990011100164C00	164	14012	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3011MH0002270001100230R00				range map product:					3011MH0002270001100231S00
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3010MH0006990011100175C00	175	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3011MH0002270001100228R00				range map product:					3011MH0002270001100229S00
mhli00785	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm												
	3010MH0007850011100186C00	186	15148	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3011MH0002270001100226R00				range map product:					3011MH0002270001100227S00

target named **Gageac_et_Rouillac**

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3010MH0007060011100197C00	197	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhli00721	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3010MH0007210011100200C00	200	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3011MH0002270001100224R00				range map product:					3011MH0002270001100225S00
mhli00721	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3010MH0007210011100211C00	211	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3011MH0002270001100222R00				range map product:					3011MH0002270001100223S00

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3011 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

rover wheel inspection - view below rover undercarriage

mhl00818	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to wheel hub: ~187 cm										
	3011MH0008180011100221E01	221	12612	~191	~189	~65	~218	~679	~499	1608	1198	~109	~84

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3013 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Champagnac													
mhli00586	context view		intended standoff - 15 cm										
	3013MH0005860011100233C00	233	13258	16.8	14.9	-0.7	0.8	65.9	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3013MH0001820011100235C00	235	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3013MH0001930001100268R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3013MH0001930001100269S00							
mhli00182	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3013MH0001820011100245C00	245	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3013MH0001930001100266R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3013MH0001930001100267S00							
mhli00184	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3013MH0001840011100255C00	255	14715	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3013MH0001930001100264R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3013MH0001930001100265S00							

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3015 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Beaupouyet**

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3015MH0007060011100271C00	271	13013	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3015MH0007630011100274C00	274	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3015MH0001930001100310R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3015MH0001930001100311S00						
mhl00763	medium-r resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3015MH0007630011100285C00	285	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3015MH0001930001100308R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3015MH0001930001100309S00						
mhl00794	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm											
	3015MH0007940011100296C00	296	15084	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3015MH0001930001100306R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3015MH0001930001100307S00						

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3017 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Neuvic - after DRT

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3017MH0007060011100313C00	313	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00763	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3017MH0007630011100316C00	316	14038	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product: 3018MH0001930001100370R00				range map product: 3018MH0001930001100371S00							
mhli00763	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3017MH0007630011100327C00	327	14040	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product: 3018MH0001930001100368R00				range map product: 3018MH0001930001100369S00							
mhli00822	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm											
	3017MH0008220011100338C00	338	15217	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product: 3018MH0001930001100366R00				range map product: 3018MH0001930001100367S00							

Sands of Forvie sand sheet - eolian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - daylight context image and night-time imaging with no LED or Phobos illumination

mhli00819	daylight context image												
	3017MH0008190011100348C00	348	12552	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	1600	1198	(infinity)	(infinity)
mhli00820	night image - test set-up												
	3017MH0008200011100349C00	349	12552	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	1600	1198	(infinity)	(infinity)
mhli00821	night - first frame of 16-image video												
	3017MH0008210001100350K00	350	12552	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	1600	1198	(infinity)	(infinity)

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Sol 3020 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Lunas													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3020MH0007060011100373C00	373	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3020MH0001820011100376C00	376	14022	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3020MH0002650001100397R00			range map product:			3020MH0002650001100398S00	
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3020MH0001820011100386C00	386	14019	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3020MH0002650001100395R00			range map product:			3020MH0002650001100396S00	

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3022 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Tamnies**

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3022MH0007060011100400C00	400	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1	
mhli00173	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3022MH0001730011100403C00	403	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3022MH0001930001100436R00				<i>range map product:</i>							3022MH0001930001100437S00
mhli00173	medium-r resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3022MH0001730011100413C00	413	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3022MH0001930001100434R00				<i>range map product:</i>							3022MH0001930001100435S00
mhli00796	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm												
	3022MH0007960011100423C00	423	15142	2.8	0.9	0.0	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0	
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3022MH0001930001100432R00				<i>range map product:</i>							3022MH0001930001100433S00

Sol 3024 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Coutures - after DRT

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3024MH0007060011100439C00	439	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhli00709	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3024MH0007090011100442C00	442	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3025MH0001630001100520R00				range map product:					3025MH0001630001100521S00
mhli00709	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3024MH0007090011100453C00	453	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3025MH0001630001100518R00				range map product:					3025MH0001630001100519S00
mhli00823	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm												
	3024MH0008230011100464C00	464	15117	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3025MH0001630001100516R00				range map product:					3025MH0001630001100517S00

target named Biron

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3024MH0007060011100475C00	475	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1	
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3024MH0006990011100478C00	478	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3025MH0001630001100514R00				range map product:					3025MH0001630001100515S00
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3024MH0006990011100489C00	489	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3025MH0001630001100512R00				range map product:					3025MH0001630001100513S00
mhli00732	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3024MH0007320011100500C00	500	14641	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3025MH0001630001100510R00				range map product:					3025MH0001630001100511S00

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3026 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Labouquerie													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3026MH0007060011100523C00	523	13071	23.6	21.7	-1.4	1.6	89.9	5.2	1608	1198	14.5	10.8
mhl00306	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3026MH0003060011100526C00	526	14077	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3026MH0002650001100547R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3026MH0002650001100548S00							
mhl00306	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3026MH0003060011100536C00	536	14089	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3026MH0002650001100545R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3026MH0002650001100546S00							

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3027 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Brantome													
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3027MH0007060011100550C00	550	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3027MH0006990011100553C00	553	14011	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3027MH0001930001100589R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3027MH0001930001100590S00				
mhli00699	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3027MH0006990011100564C00	564	14021	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3027MH0001930001100587R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3027MH0001930001100588S00				
mhli00824	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3027MH0008240011100575C00	575	14708	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3027MH0001930001100585R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3027MH0001930001100586S00				

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3028 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Firbeix													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3028MH0007060011100592C00	592	13008	27.1	25.2	-1.8	2.1	102.2	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2
mhl00306	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3028MH0003060011100595C00	595	14025	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3028MH0002650001100616R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3028MH0002650001100617S00				
mhl00306	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3028MH0003060011100605C00	605	14020	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3028MH0002650001100614R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3028MH0002650001100615S00				

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3031 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)			
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)		
target named Dordogne - after DRT															
mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3031MH0007060011100619C00	619	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl00723	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3031MH0007230011100622C00	622	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3031MH0001530001100671R00				range map product:						3031MH0001530001100672S00	
mhl00723	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3031MH0007230011100633C00	633	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3031MH0001530001100669R00				range map product:						3031MH0001530001100670S00	
mhl00823	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3031MH0008230011100644C00	644	15048	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3031MH0001530001100667R00				range map product:						3031MH0001530001100668S00	
mhl00723	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3031MH0007230011100655C00	655	13974	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3031MH0001530001100665R00				range map product:						3031MH0001530001100666S00	

Sol 3034 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)			
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)		
target named Limeyrat - after DRT - quantitative relief model (QRM) data															
mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3034MH0007060011100674C00	674	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhli00699	med res - stereo-1 & relief model position 1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3034MH0006990011100677C00	677	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3034MH0001530001100732R00				range map product:						3034MH0001530001100733S00	
mhli00699	med res - stereo-2 & relief model position 2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3034MH0006990011100688C00	688	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3034MH0001530001100730R00				range map product:						3034MH0001530001100731S00	
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 3	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
3034MH0007050011100699C00	699	14005	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7			
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 4	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
3034MH0007050011100701C00	701	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7			
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 5	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
3034MH0007050011100703C00	703	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7			
mhli00785	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3034MH0007850011100705C00	705	15085	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3034MH0001530001100728R00				range map product:						3034MH0001530001100729S00	
mhli00699	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3034MH0006990011100716C00	716	13979	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3034MH0001530001100726R00				range map product:						3034MH0001530001100727S00	

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3035 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Fleurac**

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3035MH0007060011100735C00	735	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3035MH0006990011100738C00	738	14045	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3036MH0001530001100791R00				range map product:						3036MH0001530001100792S00	
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3035MH0006990011100749C00	749	14045	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3036MH0001530001100789R00				range map product:						3036MH0001530001100790S00	
mhli00699	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3035MH0006990011100760C00	760	14048	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3036MH0001530001100787R00				range map product:						3036MH0001530001100788S00	

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3036 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Fleurac														
mhl00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	APXS raster spot 1													
	3036MH0001220011100771C00	771	13964	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
mhl00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	APXS raster spot 2													
	3036MH0001220011100773C00	773	13974	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
mhl00825	high resolution view	intended standoff - 3 cm												
	APXS raster spot 2													
	3036MH0008250011100775C00	775	14359	5.0	3.1	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3036MH0001530001100785R00	range map product:					3036MH0001530001100786S00					

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3037 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)			
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)		
target named Chalus - after DRT															
mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3037MH0007060011100794C00	794	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3037MH0007630011100797C00	797	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3037MH0001530001100846R00				range map product:						3037MH0001530001100847S00	
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3037MH0007630011100808C00	808	14026	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3037MH0001530001100844R00				range map product:						3037MH0001530001100845S00	
mhl00813	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3037MH0008130011100819C00	819	14720	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3037MH0001530001100842R00				range map product:						3037MH0001530001100843S00	
mhl00763	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3037MH0007630011100830C00	830	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3037MH0001530001100840R00				range map product:						3037MH0001530001100841S00	

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3040 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Plazac													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3040MH0007060011100849C00	849	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3040MH0007630011100852C00	852	14033	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3040MH0002650001100875R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3040MH0002650001100876S00							
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3040MH0007630011100863C00	863	14042	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3040MH0002650001100873R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3040MH0002650001100874S00							

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3042 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Manzac													
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3042MH0007060011100878C00	878	13027	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.8
mhli00723	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3042MH0007230011100881C00	881	14031	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3042MH0002650001100904R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3042MH0002650001100905S00						
mhli00723	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3042MH0007230011100892C00	892	14039	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3042MH0002650001100902R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3042MH0002650001100903S00						

Sol 3044 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Pazayac

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3044MH0007060011100907C00	907	13011	26.9	25.0	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.2	
mhli00709	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3044MH0007090011100910C00	910	13943	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3044MH0001630001100988R00				range map product:					3044MH0001630001100989S00
mhli00709	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3044MH0007090011100921C00	921	13966	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3044MH0001630001100986R00				range map product:					3044MH0001630001100987S00
mhli00794	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm												
	3044MH0007940011100932C00	932	14958	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.1	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3044MH0001630001100984R00				range map product:					3044MH0001630001100985S00

target named Sadillac

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3044MH0007060011100943C00	943	13005	27.3	25.4	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3	
mhli00709	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3044MH0007090011100946C00	946	13936	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3044MH0001630001100982R00				range map product:					3044MH0001630001100983S00
mhli00709	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3044MH0007090011100957C00	957	13942	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3044MH0001630001100980R00				range map product:					3044MH0001630001100981S00
mhli00658	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm												
	3044MH0006580011100968C00	968	14910	3.2	1.3	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.2	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3044MH0001630001100978R00				range map product:					3044MH0001630001100979S00

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3047 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Daglan													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3047MH0007060011100991C00	991	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00699	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3047MH0006990011100994C00	994	14035	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
		corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product: 3047MH0002650001101017R00				range map product: 3047MH0002650001101018S00						
mhl00699	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3047MH0006990011101005C00	1005	14036	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
		corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product: 3047MH0002650001101015R00				range map product: 3047MH0002650001101016S00						

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3049 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Marval

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3049MH0007060011101020C00	1020	13001	27.5	25.6	-1.9	2.2	103.8	7.2	1608	1198	16.7	12.4

target named Valojoux

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3049MH0007060011101023C00	1023	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7

Sol 3051 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Montrem** - after DRT

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3051MH0007060011101026C00	1026	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhli00723	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3051MH0007230011101029C00	1029	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3052MH0002270001101094R00				range map product:					3052MH0002270001101095S00
mhli00723	medium-r resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3051MH0007230011101040C00	1040	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3052MH0002270001101092R00				range map product:					3052MH0002270001101093S00
mhli00785	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm												
	3051MH0007850011101051C00	1051	15111	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3052MH0002270001101090R00				range map product:					3052MH0002270001101091S00

target named **Peyrat**

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3051MH0007060011101062C00	1062	13023	26.2	24.3	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	1608	1198	15.9	11.9	
mhli00723	medium-r resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3051MH0007230011101065C00	1065	14144	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3052MH0002270001101088R00				range map product:					3052MH0002270001101089S00
mhli00723	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3051MH0007230011101076C00	1076	14132	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3052MH0002270001101086R00				range map product:					3052MH0002270001101087S00

Sol 3054 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

intended drill target named Nontron - before DRT													
mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3054MH0001900011101097C00	1097	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 1												
	3054MH0001220011101099C00	1099	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

intended drill target named Nontron - after DRT													
mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3054MH0007060011101101C00	1101	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 1												
	3054MH0007630011101104C00	1104	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3054MH0001530001101155R00		range map product:		3054MH0001530001101156S00			
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 1												
	3054MH0007630011101115C00	1115	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3054MH0001530001101153R00		range map product:		3054MH0001530001101154S00			
mhl00785	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm											
	APXS raster spot 1												
	3054MH0007850011101126C00	1126	15102	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3054MH0001530001101151R00		range map product:		3054MH0001530001101152S00			
mhl00763	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3054MH0007630011101137C00	1137	13991	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3054MH0001530001101149R00		range map product:		3054MH0001530001101150S00			

intended drill target named Nontron - after drill bit pre-load test													
mhl00465	context view	intended standoff - 35 cm											
	3054MH0004650011101148C00	1148	12895	36.5	34.6	-3.3	3.9	135.3	12.7	1608	1198	21.8	16.2

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3056 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

intended sample discard site for planned Nontron drill sample

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3056MH0001900011101158C00	1158	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0

alternate portion characterization site for planned Nontron drill sample

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3056MH0001970011101160C00	1160	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9

intended portion characterization site for planned Nontron drill sample

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3056MH0001970011101162C00	1162	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0

Sol 3068 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Nontron sample discard pile

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00619	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3068MH0006190011101164C00	1164	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1

Nontron drill hole

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00619	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3068MH0006190011101166C00	1166	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00774	intermediate-resolution view	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3068MH0007740011101168C00	1168	13523	11.5	9.6	-0.4	0.4	47.4	1.3	1608	1198	7.6	5.7

SAM sample inlet 1 - cover open - after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00779	full-frame using manual focus	intended standoff - 20 cm											
	3068MH0007790011101169C00	1169	13080	23.1	21.2	-1.4	1.5	88.3	5.0	1608	1198	14.2	10.6
	full-frame based on 128 x 128 autofocus sub-frame (starting pixel 1008, 768)												
	3068MH0007790031101171C00	1171	13094	22.5	20.6	-1.3	1.4	86.1	4.8	1608	1198	13.8	10.3

Nontron sample discard pile

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00122	medium-resolution	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 1	3068MH0001220011101173C00	1173	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0
mhli00122	medium-resolution	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2	3068MH0001220011101175C00	1175	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0

5 Focus merge product information

5.1 Purpose and description

The MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* provide information about the best focus and range map products created by focus merges performed onboard the MAHLI instrument.

The information includes:

1. thumbnail images representing the appearance of each best focus and range map product;
2. a brief title or description of the image target and purpose;
3. the Sol and date (UTC) that the merged parent images were acquired;
4. the Sol on which the focus merge took place,
5. image IDs for the focus merge products and a corresponding full-frame image;
6. the MAHLI command sequence that acquired the parent images and the command sequence that created the focus merge products;
7. the commanded stack depth; that is, the number of parent images acquired in a given focus stack;
8. the type of focus stack (relative or absolute; see definitions in **Section 7**);
9. a list of the thumbnail image IDs for the parent images acquired in the focus stack (because, in some cases, these are the only versions of the focus stack images that are received on Earth);
10. the focus position (stepper motor count) for each parent image in the focus stack;
11. the range and range uncertainty determined from the focus position (motor count) of each parent image; and
12. the grayscale DN value corresponding to each parent image motor count and range in the focus merge range map product.

Further, for each parent image, the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* state whether any of the full-size images (Individual Focus Stack Images) were received on Earth, listing:

13. the image ID of the full-size parent or child image, if received on Earth;
14. the date on which the full-size image was received (applicable only to *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* for the period between Sol 0 and 946 after that, with the exception of Sol 930, this practice was abandoned as unnecessary);
15. the compression quality of the best version of the image, if received on Earth (this practice was later abandoned as unnecessary); and

16. a statement regarding the fate of parent images not received on Earth; that is, the Sol on which the parent was deleted from the data storage inside the instrument’s digital electronics assembly (DEA).

Each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is identified by the Sol on which the parent images were acquired. The onboard merge, in some cases, might have been performed on a later sol.

The parent images identified in rows that are colored orange, if they have a corresponding DN value in a yellow colored column, are those that participated in the creation of the focus merge product. In other words, those that are in white rows (for which there is a corresponding DN in the yellow column) had no in-focus elements and thus were not incorporated into the merged product, even if they had been commanded to be merged. Which images were commanded to be merged can be determined by the yellow-colored column that indicates the corresponding DN values in the range map image product; for cases in which the commanded focus stack depth is > 8 , the corresponding DN values (yellow colored column) will indicate the 8 commanded to be merged (the instrument cannot merge > 8 but it can acquire > 8 images in a focus stack).

In cases in which the focus stack parent images were returned to Earth, the data user has the option to perform a new focus merge using software approaches available on Earth, now or in the future, which might outperform the MAHLI onboard algorithm. The user also has the opportunity, in these cases, to improve each parent image before performing the merge (e.g., remove blemishes, perform flat field correction, etc.).

When a > 8 image focus stack has been acquired, the orange colored rows can *also* indicate recommendations for images that would contain in-focus elements and could be added to a future focus merge product, whether performed onboard MAHLI on Earth after receipt of the full-size images. Those images that are recommended, but were not merged onboard, have no “Corresponding DN in Range Map” in the yellow, rightmost columns of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*.

For the Sol 2935–3068 period, focus stacks that were merged onboard the instrument were acquired on **Sols 2935, 2938, 2940, 2942, 2945, 2949, 2951, 2955, 2959, 2965, 2967, 2969, 2972, 2974, 2989, 2992, 2993, 2994, 3004, 3007, 3010, 3013, 3015, 3017, 3020, 3022, 3024, 3026, 3027, 3028, 3031, 3034, 3035, 3036, 3037, 3040, 3042, 3044, 3047, 3051, 3054**. Unless otherwise stated, the onboard focus merges performed during this period were all of the “basic” type (see Edgett *et al.* 2012; Edgett *et al.* 2015).

5.2 Formulae

5.2.1 Range

When acquiring a focus stack, the MAHLI camera head is held in a fixed position. This means that the working distance (d_w) — and corresponding standoff distance (d_s) — is constant (see **Section 5.2.5**). However, each image acquired in a focus stack is done so at a different focus position; that is, a different stepper motor count position (m_{open} or m_{closed} ; usually m_{open}). That motor count is related to the range (r_{fm}) between the front lens element of the camera and the in-focus elements of the image by the same empirical formula (**Equation 1**) as applied to determine working distance from motor count. In centimeters,

$$r_{fm} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (12)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For each parent image in a given focus stack, this range is given in the green colored column on the right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

5.2.2 Range uncertainty estimate

The uncertainty ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) in the computed range (r_{fm}) is estimated using depth of field as related to the corresponding range (via motor count; **Equation 12**) for each merged parent image. The range uncertainty estimate is noted in the light green column on the lower right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Estimated Range Uncertainty”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created before Sol 942, our estimate of range uncertainty was based on the older (Edgett *et al.* 2013) depth of field equations described in **Section 4.2.3**, **Equations 4, 5, and 6**, in which we substituted r_{fm} for d_w .

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Depth of Field”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created starting with Sol 942, we used the refined knowledge of MAHLI depth of field, described by Edgett *et al.* (2015) and in **Equation 7** of **Section 4.2.3** to determine d_{far} and d_{near} for each focus stack parent image motor count. The resulting range uncertainty estimate ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) reported in the light green column on the lower right side of the corresponding *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is estimated by the average of the absolute values of d_{far} and d_{near} :

$$\pm r_{uncertainty} = ((-d_{near}) + d_{far})/2. \quad (13)$$

Alternatively, particularly after Sol 1000, the depth of field is reported in the form of both the near and far (d_{far} and d_{near}) depths of field, per **Equation 7**.

5.2.3 Corresponding DN in range map product

Focus merge range map products created onboard MAHLI are returned as grayscale JPEG compressed images. The pixel values (DN) range from 0 to 255. These are assigned by the onboard software on the basis of commanded focus stack depth. The table below, from Edgett *et al.* (2015), shows the relationship between each image commanded to be focus merged and its corresponding grayscale DN value in a MAHLI range map product. In other words, if the instrument is commanded to merge eight images, DN values are assigned according to the second column in the table; if commanded to merge only four images, the corresponding DN values are those in the sixth column. Thus, each DN in a range map product can be related to a motor count position and a corresponding range via linear interpolation between these values.

Relation between commanded image participant in an onboard MAHLI focus merge and range map grayscale data value (DN)							
image commanded to be merged	DN for 8-image merge	DN for 7-image merge	DN for 6-image merge	DN for 5-image merge	DN for 4-image merge	DN for 3-image merge	DN for 2-image merge
1st	255	255	255	255	255	255	255
2nd	223	218	212	204	191	170	127
3rd	191	182	170	153	127	84	—
4th	159	145	127	102	63	—	—
5th	127	109	84	51	—	—	—
6th	95	72	42	—	—	—	—
7th	63	36	—	—	—	—	—
8th	31	—	—	—	—	—	—

5.2.4 Determination of which parent images participated in a given focus merge product (orange rows)

Focus merge parent images in the orange colored rows on each of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* are an indicator of the images that were actually merged. A merge of up to 8 images might be commanded, but perhaps only 3, 4, or 5 of them actually exhibit in-focus elements the get incorporated into the best focus image product.

As discussed by Edgett *et al.* (2015), the parent images that were actually merged, relative to the number commanded to be merged (indicated by the number of yellow-colored rows regarding the corresponding DN in the range map products on the right side of each *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*), are determined by the range of grayscale DN, between 0 and 255, in the focus merge range map product. For example, if the DN range of this product is 91 to 138, then only three of 8 images commanded to be merged participated in that merge, per the DN values corresponding to an 8-image focus merge, per the table above.

5.2.5 Camera working distance and standoff distance

For a given focus stack, the distance between the MAHLI camera head and an imaged target can be determined from a corresponding image acquired via autofocus (assuming the autofocus effort found focus). In other words, while the range between the camera and the in-focus elements of a parent image are captured by the individual parent images in the focus stack (**Section 5.2.1**), the camera acquired the stack from a fixed working distance. On the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the corresponding autofocused image, and its stepper motor count focus position, are stated on the left side of the sheet, beneath the thumbnail images, in rows and columns colored light blue.

For some *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the working distance (d_w) and standoff distance (d_s) are provided in these blue rows and columns. These were computed from the motor count position using the same formulae for d_w and d_s described in **Section 4.2 (Equations 1 and 3, respectively)**. Where these values are not given, the data user can apply **Equations 1 and 3** to the motor count, or use the corresponding full-frame image ID to identify the working distance and standoff distance using the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* for that Sol. We began to regularly provide a result for d_w and d_s starting with Sol 694; before that, the cases in which these

values are not given are a reflection of the evolution of the production and content of the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* over time.

updated: 16_November_2020

Sol 2935 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Hunt_Hill** - Stereo-1 - After DRT - APXS target - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2935		Acquired on Date:		8-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2935		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00227		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00763		
2935MH0007630011003933C00		14000				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2935MH0002270001003998R00		3998		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2935MH0002270001003999S00		3999		Motor Count Interval:		24		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2935MH0007630031003935I01		3935	—	2935MH0007630031003935C00	13904	7.5	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
2935MH0007630031003936I01		3936	—	2935MH0007630031003936C00	13928	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
2935MH0007630031003937I01		3937	x	2935MH0007630031003937C00	13952	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
2935MH0007630031003938I01		3938	x	2935MH0007630031003938C00	13976	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
2935MH0007630031003939I01		3939	x	2935MH0007630031003939C00	14000	6.8	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
2935MH0007630031003940I01		3940	x	2935MH0007630031003940C00	14024	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
2935MH0007630031003941I01		3941	x	2935MH0007630031003941C00	14048	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
2935MH0007630031003942I01		3942	—	2935MH0007630031003942C00	14072	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 2935 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Hunt_Hill** - Stereo-2 - After DRT - APXS target - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2935		Acquired on Date:		8-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2935		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00227		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00763				
2935MH0007630011003944C00		14002				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2935MH0002270001003996R00		3996		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2935MH0002270001003997S00		3997		Motor Count Interval: 24				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2935MH0007630031003946I01		3946	—	2935MH0007630031003946C00	13906	7.5	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
2935MH0007630031003947I01		3947	—	2935MH0007630031003947C00	13930	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
2935MH0007630031003948I01		3948	x	2935MH0007630031003948C00	13954	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
2935MH0007630031003949I01		3949	x	2935MH0007630031003949C00	13978	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
2935MH0007630031003950I01		3950	x	2935MH0007630031003950C00	14002	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
2935MH0007630031003951I01		3951	x	2935MH0007630031003951C00	14026	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
2935MH0007630031003952I01		3952	x	2935MH0007630031003952C00	14050	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
2935MH0007630031003953I01		3953	—	2935MH0007630031003953C00	14074	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 2935 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Hunt_Hill** - After DRT - APXS target - ~2 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2935		Acquired on Date:		8-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2935		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00227		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00732		
2935MH0007320011003955C00		14689				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	3.8	Best Focus Image:		2935MH0002270001003994R00		3994		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	1.9	Range Map Product:		2935MH0002270001003995S00		3995		Motor Count Interval:		36		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2935MH0007320031003957I01		3957	—	2935MH0007320031003957C00	14545	4.27	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	255	1
2935MH0007320031003958I01		3958	x	2935MH0007320031003958C00	14581	4.15	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	223	2
2935MH0007320031003959I01		3959	x	2935MH0007320031003959C00	14617	4.03	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	191	3
2935MH0007320031003960I01		3960	x	2935MH0007320031003960C00	14653	3.92	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	159	4
2935MH0007320031003961I01		3961	x	2935MH0007320031003961C00	14689	3.82	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5
2935MH0007320031003962I01		3962	x	2935MH0007320031003962C00	14725	3.71	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	85	6
2935MH0007320031003963I01		3963	x	2935MH0007320031003963C00	14761	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	63	7
2935MH0007320031003964I01		3964	x	2935MH0007320031003964C00	14797	3.52	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	31	8

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Sol 2935 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target Muckle_Minn - Stereo-1 - APXS target - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2935		Acquired on Date:		8-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2935		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00227		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00721				
2935MH0007210011003969C00		13979				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	7.0	Best Focus Image:		2935MH0002270001003992R00		3992		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	5.1	Range Map Product:		2935MH0002270001003993S00		3993		Motor Count Interval: 42				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2935MH0007210031003971I01		3971	—	2935MH0007210031003971C00	13811	8.3	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.8	255	1
2935MH0007210031003972I01		3972	x	2935MH0007210031003972C00	13853	7.9	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	223	2
2935MH0007210031003973I01		3973	x	2935MH0007210031003973C00	13895	7.6	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	191	3
2935MH0007210031003974I01		3974	x	2935MH0007210031003974C00	13937	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
2935MH0007210031003975I01		3975	x	2935MH0007210031003975C00	13979	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
2935MH0007210031003976I01		3976	x	2935MH0007210031003976C00	14021	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
2935MH0007210031003977I01		3977	x	2935MH0007210031003977C00	14063	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
2935MH0007210031003978I01		3978	—	2935MH0007210031003978C00	14105	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

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Sol 2935 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target Muckle_Minn - Stereo-2 - APXS target - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2935		Acquired on Date:		8-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2935		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00227		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00721				
2935MH0007210011003980C00		13974				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	7.0	Best Focus Image:		2935MH0002270001003990R00		3990		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	5.1	Range Map Product:		2935MH0002270001003991S00		3991		Motor Count Interval: 42				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2935MH0007210031003982I01		3982	—	2935MH0007210031003982C00	13806	8.3	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	255	1
2935MH0007210031003983I01		3983	x	2935MH0007210031003983C00	13848	8.0	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	223	2
2935MH0007210031003984I01		3984	x	2935MH0007210031003984C00	13890	7.6	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	191	3
2935MH0007210031003985I01		3985	x	2935MH0007210031003985C00	13932	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	159	4
2935MH0007210031003986I01		3986	x	2935MH0007210031003986C00	13974	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	127	5
2935MH0007210031003987I01		3987	x	2935MH0007210031003987C00	14016	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6
2935MH0007210031003988I01		3988	—	2935MH0007210031003988C00	14058	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
2935MH0007210031003989I01		3989	—	2935MH0007210031003989C00	14100	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 2938 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Hart_Fell** - Stereo-1 - after APXS retraction - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2938		Acquired on Date:		10-Nov-2020							
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2938		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00265		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00173					
2938MH0001730011004004C00		13929				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic					
computed working distance (cm):	7.3	Best Focus Image:		2938MH0002650001004025R00		4025		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack					
computed standoff distance (cm):	5.4	Range Map Product:		2938MH0002650001004026S00		4026		Motor Count Interval:		30			
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>		Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	Pixel Scale uncertainty ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
						near	far	near	far				
2938MH0001730021004005I01		4005	—	2938MH0001730021004005C00	13809	8.3	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	255	1	
2938MH0001730021004006I01		4006	—	2938MH0001730021004006C00	13839	8.0	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	223	2	
2938MH0001730021004007I01		4007	—	2938MH0001730021004007C00	13869	7.8	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	191	3	
2938MH0001730021004008I01		4008	x	2938MH0001730021004008C00	13899	7.6	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	159	4	
2938MH0001730021004009I01		4009	x	2938MH0001730021004009C00	13929	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	127	5	
2938MH0001730021004010I01		4010	x	2938MH0001730021004010C00	13959	7.1	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	85	6	
2938MH0001730021004011I01		4011	x	2938MH0001730021004011C00	13989	6.9	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	63	7	
2938MH0001730021004012I01		4012	x	2938MH0001730021004012C00	14019	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8	

updated: 16_November_2020

Sol 2938 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Hart_Fell** - Stereo-2 - after APXS retraction - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2938		Acquired on Date:		10-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2938		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00265		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00173		
2938MH0001730011004014C00		13936				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	7.3	Best Focus Image:		2938MH0002650001004023R00		4023		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	5.4	Range Map Product:		2938MH0002650001004024S00		4024		Motor Count Interval:		30		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2938MH0001730021004015I01		4015	—	2938MH0001730021004015C00	13816	8.2	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	255	1
2938MH0001730021004016I01		4016	—	2938MH0001730021004016C00	13846	8.0	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	223	2
2938MH0001730021004017I01		4017	x	2938MH0001730021004017C00	13876	7.7	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	191	3
2938MH0001730021004018I01		4018	x	2938MH0001730021004018C00	13906	7.5	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	159	4
2938MH0001730021004019I01		4019	x	2938MH0001730021004019C00	13936	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	127	5
2938MH0001730021004020I01		4020	x	2938MH0001730021004020C00	13966	7.1	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	85	6
2938MH0001730021004021I01		4021	x	2938MH0001730021004021C00	13996	6.9	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	63	7
2938MH0001730021004022I01		4022	x	2938MH0001730021004022C00	14026	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

updated: 16_November_2020

Sol 2940 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target West_Loch - Stereo-1 - after APXS retraction - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2940		Acquired on Date:		12-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2940		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00265		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00299				
2940MH0002990011004031C00		14026				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.7	Best Focus Image:		2940MH0002650001004052R00		4052		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.8	Range Map Product:		2940MH0002650001004053S00		4053		Motor Count Interval:		36		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2940MH0002990021004032I01		4032	x	2940MH0002990021004032C00	13882	7.7	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
2940MH0002990021004033I01		4033	x	2940MH0002990021004033C00	13918	7.4	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
2940MH0002990021004034I01		4034	x	2940MH0002990021004034C00	13954	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
2940MH0002990021004035I01		4035	x	2940MH0002990021004035C00	13990	6.9	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
2940MH0002990021004036I01		4036	x	2940MH0002990021004036C00	14026	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
2940MH0002990021004037I01		4037	x	2940MH0002990021004037C00	14062	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
2940MH0002990021004038I01		4038	—	2940MH0002990021004038C00	14098	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	63	7
2940MH0002990021004039I01		4039	—	2940MH0002990021004039C00	14134	6.0	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	31	8

updated: 16_November_2020

Sol 2940 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **West_Loch** - Stereo-2 - after APXS retraction - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2940		Acquired on Date:		12-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2940		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00265		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00299		
2940MH0002990011004041C00		14029				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	6.7	Best Focus Image:		2940MH0002650001004050R00		4050		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.8	Range Map Product:		2940MH0002650001004051S00		4051		Motor Count Interval:		36		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2940MH0002990021004042I01		4042	x	2940MH0002990021004042C00	13885	7.7	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
2940MH0002990021004043I01		4043	x	2940MH0002990021004043C00	13921	7.4	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
2940MH0002990021004044I01		4044	x	2940MH0002990021004044C00	13957	7.1	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
2940MH0002990021004045I01		4045	x	2940MH0002990021004045C00	13993	6.9	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
2940MH0002990021004046I01		4046	x	2940MH0002990021004046C00	14029	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
2940MH0002990021004047I01		4047	x	2940MH0002990021004047C00	14065	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
2940MH0002990021004048I01		4048	—	2940MH0002990021004048C00	14101	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
2940MH0002990021004049I01		4049	—	2940MH0002990021004049C00	14137	6.0	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 16_November_2020

Sol 2942 – MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2942		Acquired on Date:		15-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2943		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00163		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00709		
2942MH0007090011004058C00		13950				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):		7.2		Best Focus Image:		2943MH0001630001004136R00		4136		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack		
computed standoff distance (cm):		5.3		Range Map Product:		2943MH0001630001004137S00		4137		Motor Count Interval: 48		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	Pixel Scale uncertainty ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
						near	far					
2942MH0007090031004060I01		4060	—	2942MH0007090031004060C00	13758	8.8	-0.2	0.2	37.7	0.8	255	1
2942MH0007090031004061I01		4061	x	2942MH0007090031004061C00	13806	8.3	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	223	2
2942MH0007090031004062I01		4062	x	2942MH0007090031004062C00	13854	7.9	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	191	3
2942MH0007090031004063I01		4063	x	2942MH0007090031004063C00	13902	7.5	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	159	4
2942MH0007090031004064I01		4064	x	2942MH0007090031004064C00	13950	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	127	5
2942MH0007090031004065I01		4065	x	2942MH0007090031004065C00	13998	6.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	85	6
2942MH0007090031004066I01		4066	x	2942MH0007090031004066C00	14046	6.6	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
2942MH0007090031004067I01		4067	—	2942MH0007090031004067C00	14094	6.3	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 16_November_2020

Sol 2942 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2942	Acquired on Date:		15-Nov-2020								
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2943	Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8	Relative							
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00163		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00709			
2942MH0007090011004069C00		13949				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic			
computed working distance (cm):	7.2	Best Focus Image:		2943MH0001630001004134R00	4134	This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack							
computed standoff distance (cm):	5.3	Range Map Product:		2943MH0001630001004135S00	4135	Motor Count Interval:		48					
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	Pixel Scale uncertainty ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8	
						near	far						
2942MH0007090031004071I01		4071	—	2942MH0007090031004071C00	13757	8.8	-0.2	0.2	37.7	0.8	255	1	
2942MH0007090031004072I01		4072	x	2942MH0007090031004072C00	13805	8.3	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	223	2	
2942MH0007090031004073I01		4073	x	2942MH0007090031004073C00	13853	7.9	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	191	3	
2942MH0007090031004074I01		4074	x	2942MH0007090031004074C00	13901	7.5	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	159	4	
2942MH0007090031004075I01		4075	x	2942MH0007090031004075C00	13949	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	127	5	
2942MH0007090031004076I01		4076	x	2942MH0007090031004076C00	13997	6.9	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	85	6	
2942MH0007090031004077I01		4077	x	2942MH0007090031004077C00	14045	6.6	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7	
2942MH0007090031004078I01		4078	—	2942MH0007090031004078C00	14093	6.3	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8	

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Sol 2942 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2942		Acquired on Date:		15-Nov-2020							
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2943		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00163		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00795			
2942MH0007950011004080C00		14602				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic			
computed working distance (cm):		4.1		Best Focus Image:		2943MH0001630001004132R00		4132		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack			
computed standoff distance (cm):		2.2		Range Map Product:		2943MH0001630001004133S00		4133		Motor Count Interval: 84			
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	Pixel Scale uncertainty ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8	
						near		far					
2942MH0007950031004082I01		4082	—	2942MH0007950031004082C00	14266	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	255	1	
2942MH0007950031004083I01		4083	x	2942MH0007950031004083C00	14350	5.00	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	223	2	
2942MH0007950031004084I01		4084	x	2942MH0007950031004084C00	14434	4.67	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	191	3	
2942MH0007950031004085I01		4085	x	2942MH0007950031004085C00	14518	4.36	-0.1	0.1	22.2	0.3	159	4	
2942MH0007950031004086I01		4086	x	2942MH0007950031004086C00	14602	4.08	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	127	5	
2942MH0007950031004087I01		4087	x	2942MH0007950031004087C00	14686	3.82	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	85	6	
2942MH0007950031004088I01		4088	x	2942MH0007950031004088C00	14770	3.59	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	63	7	
2942MH0007950031004089I01		4089	—	2942MH0007950031004089C00	14854	3.37	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	31	8	

Target **St_Ninian** - APXS target - ~2 cm standoff

updated: 16_November_2020

Sol 2942 – MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target Geesa_Water - Stereo-1 - APXS target - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2942		Acquired on Date:		15-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2943		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00163		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00803				
2942MH0008030011004094C00		14006				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2943MH0001630001004130R00		4130		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2943MH0001630001004131S00		4131		Motor Count Interval: 84				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2942MH0008030031004096I01		4096	—	2942MH0008030031004096C00	13670	9.7	-0.3	0.3	40.9	1.0	255	1
2942MH0008030031004097I01		4097	x	2942MH0008030031004097C00	13754	8.8	-0.2	0.2	37.8	0.8	223	2
2942MH0008030031004098I01		4098	x	2942MH0008030031004098C00	13838	8.0	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	191	3
2942MH0008030031004099I01		4099	x	2942MH0008030031004099C00	13922	7.4	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	159	4
2942MH0008030031004100I01		4100	x	2942MH0008030031004100C00	14006	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
2942MH0008030031004101I01		4101	x	2942MH0008030031004101C00	14090	6.3	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	85	6
2942MH0008030031004102I01		4102	—	2942MH0008030031004102C00	14174	5.8	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	63	7
2942MH0008030031004103I01		4103	—	2942MH0008030031004103C00	14258	5.4	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	31	8

updated: 16_November_2020

Sol 2942 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target Geesa_Water - Stereo-2 - APXS target - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2942		Acquired on Date:		15-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2943		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00163		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00803				
2942MH0008030011004105C00		13983				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	7.0	Best Focus Image:		2943MH0001630001004128R00		4128		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	5.1	Range Map Product:		2943MH0001630001004129S00		4129		Motor Count Interval:		84		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty <small>near far</small>		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
2942MH0008030031004107I01		4107	—	2942MH0008030031004107C00	13647	9.9	-0.3	0.3	41.8	1.0	255	1
2942MH0008030031004108I01		4108	x	2942MH0008030031004108C00	13731	9.0	-0.3	0.2	38.6	0.9	223	2
2942MH0008030031004109I01		4109	x	2942MH0008030031004109C00	13815	8.2	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	191	3
2942MH0008030031004110I01		4110	x	2942MH0008030031004110C00	13899	7.6	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	159	4
2942MH0008030031004111I01		4111	x	2942MH0008030031004111C00	13983	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
2942MH0008030031004112I01		4112	x	2942MH0008030031004112C00	14067	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	85	6
2942MH0008030031004113I01		4113	—	2942MH0008030031004113C00	14151	5.9	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	63	7
2942MH0008030031004114I01		4114	—	2942MH0008030031004114C00	14235	5.5	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	31	8

updated: 16_November_2020

Sol 2942 – MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target Geesa_Water - APXS target - ~2 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2942		Acquired on Date:		15-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2943		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00163		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00795				
2942MH0007950011004116C00		14730				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	3.7	Best Focus Image:		2943MH0001630001004126R00		4126		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	1.8	Range Map Product:		2943MH0001630001004127S00		4127		Motor Count Interval:		84		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2942MH0007950031004118I01		4118	x	2942MH0007950031004118C00	14394	4.82	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	255	1
2942MH0007950031004119I01		4119	x	2942MH0007950031004119C00	14478	4.50	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	223	2
2942MH0007950031004120I01		4120	x	2942MH0007950031004120C00	14562	4.21	-0.1	0.1	21.7	0.3	191	3
2942MH0007950031004121I01		4121	x	2942MH0007950031004121C00	14646	3.94	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	159	4
2942MH0007950031004122I01		4122	x	2942MH0007950031004122C00	14730	3.70	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	127	5
2942MH0007950031004123I01		4123	x	2942MH0007950031004123C00	14814	3.47	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	85	6
2942MH0007950031004124I01		4124	—	2942MH0007950031004124C00	14898	3.27	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	63	7
2942MH0007950031004125I01		4125	—	2942MH0007950031004125C00	14982	3.08	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	31	8

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2945 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Lasswade** - Stereo-1 - After DRT - APXS and ChemCam target - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2945		Acquired on Date:		18-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2945		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00163		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00699		
2945MH0006990011004146C00		14006				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2945MH0001630001004220R00		4220		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2945MH0001630001004221S00		4221		Motor Count Interval:		30		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2945MH0006990031004148I01		4148	—	2945MH0006990031004148C00	13886	7.7	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
2945MH0006990031004149I01		4149	—	2945MH0006990031004149C00	13916	7.4	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
2945MH0006990031004150I01		4150	x	2945MH0006990031004150C00	13946	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
2945MH0006990031004151I01		4151	x	2945MH0006990031004151C00	13976	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
2945MH0006990031004152I01		4152	x	2945MH0006990031004152C00	14006	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
2945MH0006990031004153I01		4153	x	2945MH0006990031004153C00	14036	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	85	6
2945MH0006990031004154I01		4154	—	2945MH0006990031004154C00	14066	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
2945MH0006990031004155I01		4155	—	2945MH0006990031004155C00	14096	6.3	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2945 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Lasswade** - Stereo-2 - After DRT - APXS and ChemCam target - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2945		Acquired on Date:		18-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2945		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00163		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00699		
2945MH0006990011004157C00		14006				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2945MH0001630001004218R00		4218		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2945MH0001630001004219S00		4219		Motor Count Interval:		30		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2945MH0006990031004159I01		4159	—	2945MH0006990031004159C00	13886	7.7	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
2945MH0006990031004160I01		4160	—	2945MH0006990031004160C00	13916	7.4	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
2945MH0006990031004161I01		4161	x	2945MH0006990031004161C00	13946	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
2945MH0006990031004162I01		4162	x	2945MH0006990031004162C00	13976	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
2945MH0006990031004163I01		4163	x	2945MH0006990031004163C00	14006	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
2945MH0006990031004164I01		4164	x	2945MH0006990031004164C00	14036	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	85	6
2945MH0006990031004165I01		4165	—	2945MH0006990031004165C00	14066	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
2945MH0006990031004166I01		4166	—	2945MH0006990031004166C00	14096	6.3	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2945 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target Lasswade - After DRT - APXS and ChemCam target - ~2 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2945		Acquired on Date:		18-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2945		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00163		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00813				
2945MH0008130011004168C00		14702				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	3.8	Best Focus Image:		2945MH0001630001004216R00		4216		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	1.9	Range Map Product:		2945MH0001630001004217S00		4217		Motor Count Interval: 30				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2945MH0008130031004170I01	4170	—	2945MH0008130031004170C00	14582	4.14	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	255	1	
2945MH0008130031004171I01	4171	—	2945MH0008130031004171C00	14612	4.05	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	223	2	
2945MH0008130031004172I01	4172	x	2945MH0008130031004172C00	14642	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	191	3	
2945MH0008130031004173I01	4173	x	2945MH0008130031004173C00	14672	3.87	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	159	4	
2945MH0008130031004174I01	4174	x	2945MH0008130031004174C00	14702	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	127	5	
2945MH0008130031004175I01	4175	x	2945MH0008130031004175C00	14732	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	85	6	
2945MH0008130031004176I01	4176	x	2945MH0008130031004176C00	14762	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	63	7	
2945MH0008130031004177I01	4177	—	2945MH0008130031004177C00	14792	3.53	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	31	8	

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2945 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Ingliston** - Stereo-1 - APXS and ChemCam target - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2945		Acquired on Date:		18-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2945		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00163		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00168				
2945MH0001680011004181C00		14001				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2945MH0001630001004214R00		4214		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2945MH0001630001004215S00		4215		Motor Count Interval:		18		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2945MH0001680021004182I01	4182	—	2945MH0001680021004182C00	13929	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1	
2945MH0001680021004183I01	4183	—	2945MH0001680021004183C00	13947	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2	
2945MH0001680021004184I01	4184	x	2945MH0001680021004184C00	13965	7.1	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3	
2945MH0001680021004185I01	4185	x	2945MH0001680021004185C00	13983	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4	
2945MH0001680021004186I01	4186	x	2945MH0001680021004186C00	14001	6.8	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5	
2945MH0001680021004187I01	4187	x	2945MH0001680021004187C00	14019	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6	
2945MH0001680021004188I01	4188	x	2945MH0001680021004188C00	14037	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7	
2945MH0001680021004189I01	4189	—	2945MH0001680021004189C00	14055	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8	

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2945 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Ingliston** - Stereo-2 - APXS and ChemCam target - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2945		Acquired on Date:		18-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2945		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00163		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00168				
2945MH0001680011004191C00		14000				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2945MH0001630001004212R00		4212		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2945MH0001630001004213S00		4213		Motor Count Interval: 18				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2945MH0001680021004192I01		4192	—	2945MH0001680021004192C00	13928	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
2945MH0001680021004193I01		4193	—	2945MH0001680021004193C00	13946	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
2945MH0001680021004194I01		4194	x	2945MH0001680021004194C00	13964	7.1	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
2945MH0001680021004195I01		4195	x	2945MH0001680021004195C00	13982	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
2945MH0001680021004196I01		4196	x	2945MH0001680021004196C00	14000	6.8	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
2945MH0001680021004197I01		4197	x	2945MH0001680021004197C00	14018	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6
2945MH0001680021004198I01		4198	x	2945MH0001680021004198C00	14036	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
2945MH0001680021004199I01		4199	x	2945MH0001680021004199C00	14054	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2945 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Ingliston** - APXS and ChemCam target - ~1 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2945		Acquired on Date:		18-Nov-2020							
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2945		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00163		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00426					
2945MH0004260011004201C00		15112				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic					
computed working distance (cm):	2.8	Best Focus Image:		2945MH0001630001004210R00		4210		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack					
computed standoff distance (cm):	0.9	Range Map Product:		2945MH0001630001004211S00		4211		Motor Count Interval:		48			
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images		Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far					
2945MH0004260021004202I01		4202	—	2945MH0004260021004202C00		14920	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	255	1
2945MH0004260021004203I01		4203	x	2945MH0004260021004203C00		14968	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	223	2
2945MH0004260021004204I01		4204	x	2945MH0004260021004204C00		15016	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	191	3
2945MH0004260021004205I01		4205	x	2945MH0004260021004205C00		15064	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	159	4
2945MH0004260021004206I01		4206	x	2945MH0004260021004206C00		15112	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
2945MH0004260021004207I01		4207	x	2945MH0004260021004207C00		15160	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	85	6
2945MH0004260021004208I01		4208	x	2945MH0004260021004208C00		15208	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	63	7
2945MH0004260021004209I01		4209	—	2945MH0004260021004209C00		15256	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2949 – MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Giova** - Stereo-1 - After DRT - APXS spot 2 - ChemCam target - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2949		Acquired on Date:		22-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2949		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00153		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00709		
2949MH0007090011004230C00		14007				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2949MH0001530001004279R00		4279		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2949MH0001530001004280S00		4280		Motor Count Interval:		48		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2949MH0007090031004232I01		4232	—	2949MH0007090031004232C00	13815	8.2	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	255	1
2949MH0007090031004233I01		4233	—	2949MH0007090031004233C00	13863	7.8	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	223	2
2949MH0007090031004234I01		4234	—	2949MH0007090031004234C00	13911	7.5	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
2949MH0007090031004235I01		4235	x	2949MH0007090031004235C00	13959	7.1	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
2949MH0007090031004236I01		4236	x	2949MH0007090031004236C00	14007	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
2949MH0007090031004237I01		4237	x	2949MH0007090031004237C00	14055	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	85	6
2949MH0007090031004238I01		4238	—	2949MH0007090031004238C00	14103	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
2949MH0007090031004239I01		4239	—	2949MH0007090031004239C00	14151	5.9	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	31	8

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2949 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Giova** - Stereo-2 - After DRT - APXS spot 2 - ChemCam target - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2949		Acquired on Date:		22-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2949		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00153		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00709		
2949MH0007090011004241C00		14009				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2949MH0001530001004277R00		4277		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2949MH0001530001004278S00		4278		Motor Count Interval:		48		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2949MH0007090031004243I01		4243	—	2949MH0007090031004243C00	13817	8.2	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.8	255	1
2949MH0007090031004244I01		4244	—	2949MH0007090031004244C00	13865	7.8	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	223	2
2949MH0007090031004245I01		4245	—	2949MH0007090031004245C00	13913	7.5	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	191	3
2949MH0007090031004246I01		4246	x	2949MH0007090031004246C00	13961	7.1	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
2949MH0007090031004247I01		4247	x	2949MH0007090031004247C00	14009	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
2949MH0007090031004248I01		4248	x	2949MH0007090031004248C00	14057	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	85	6
2949MH0007090031004249I01		4249	—	2949MH0007090031004249C00	14105	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
2949MH0007090031004250I01		4250	—	2949MH0007090031004250C00	14153	5.9	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	31	8

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2949 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Giova** - After DRT - APXS spot 1 - ChemCam target - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2949		Acquired on Date:		22-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2949		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00153		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00709				
2949MH0007090011004252C00		14030				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.7	Best Focus Image:		2949MH0001530001004275R00		4275		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.8	Range Map Product:		2949MH0001530001004276S00		4276		Motor Count Interval: 48				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2949MH0007090031004254I01		4254	—	2949MH0007090031004254C00	13838	8.0	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	255	1
2949MH0007090031004255I01		4255	—	2949MH0007090031004255C00	13886	7.7	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
2949MH0007090031004256I01		4256	—	2949MH0007090031004256C00	13934	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
2949MH0007090031004257I01		4257	x	2949MH0007090031004257C00	13982	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
2949MH0007090031004258I01		4258	x	2949MH0007090031004258C00	14030	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
2949MH0007090031004259I01		4259	x	2949MH0007090031004259C00	14078	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	85	6
2949MH0007090031004260I01		4260	—	2949MH0007090031004260C00	14126	6.1	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	63	7
2949MH0007090031004261I01		4261	—	2949MH0007090031004261C00	14174	5.8	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	31	8

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2949 – MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Giova** - After DRT - APXS spot 2 - ChemCam target - ~2 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2949		Acquired on Date:		22-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2949		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00153		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00713				
2949MH0007130011004263C00		14724				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	3.7	Best Focus Image:		2949MH0001530001004273R00		4273		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	1.8	Range Map Product:		2949MH0001530001004274S00		4274		Motor Count Interval:		78		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2949MH0007130031004265I01		4265	—	2949MH0007130031004265C00	14412	4.75	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	255	1
2949MH0007130031004266I01		4266	—	2949MH0007130031004266C00	14490	4.46	-0.1	0.1	22.6	0.3	223	2
2949MH0007130031004267I01		4267	—	2949MH0007130031004267C00	14568	4.19	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	191	3
2949MH0007130031004268I01		4268	x	2949MH0007130031004268C00	14646	3.94	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	159	4
2949MH0007130031004269I01		4269	x	2949MH0007130031004269C00	14724	3.72	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	127	5
2949MH0007130031004270I01		4270	x	2949MH0007130031004270C00	14802	3.51	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	85	6
2949MH0007130031004271I01		4271	—	2949MH0007130031004271C00	14880	3.31	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	63	7
2949MH0007130031004272I01		4272	—	2949MH0007130031004272C00	14958	3.13	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	31	8

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2951 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target Saughieside_Hill - Stereo-1 - after APXS retraction - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2951		Acquired on Date:		24-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2951		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00193		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00182				
2951MH0001820011004285C00		14007				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2951MH0001930001004318R00		4318		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2951MH0001930001004319S00		4319		Motor Count Interval: 24				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2951MH0001820021004286I01		4286	x	2951MH0001820021004286C00	13911	7.5	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
2951MH0001820021004287I01		4287	x	2951MH0001820021004287C00	13935	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
2951MH0001820021004288I01		4288	x	2951MH0001820021004288C00	13959	7.1	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
2951MH0001820021004289I01		4289	x	2951MH0001820021004289C00	13983	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
2951MH0001820021004290I01		4290	x	2951MH0001820021004290C00	14007	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
2951MH0001820021004291I01		4291	x	2951MH0001820021004291C00	14031	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	85	6
2951MH0001820021004292I01		4292	x	2951MH0001820021004292C00	14055	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
2951MH0001820021004293I01		4293	—	2951MH0001820021004293C00	14079	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2951 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target Saughieside_Hill - Stereo-2 - after APXS retraction - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2951		Acquired on Date:		24-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2951		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00193		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00182				
2951MH0001820011004295C00		14003				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2951MH0001930001004316R00		4316		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2951MH0001930001004317S00		4317		Motor Count Interval: 24				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
						near	far					
2951MH0001820021004296I01		4296	—	2951MH0001820021004296C00	13907	7.5	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
2951MH0001820021004297I01		4297	x	2951MH0001820021004297C00	13931	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
2951MH0001820021004298I01		4298	x	2951MH0001820021004298C00	13955	7.1	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
2951MH0001820021004299I01		4299	x	2951MH0001820021004299C00	13979	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
2951MH0001820021004300I01		4300	x	2951MH0001820021004300C00	14003	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
2951MH0001820021004301I01		4301	x	2951MH0001820021004301C00	14027	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
2951MH0001820021004302I01		4302	x	2951MH0001820021004302C00	14051	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
2951MH0001820021004303I01		4303	—	2951MH0001820021004303C00	14075	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 15_December_2020

Sol 2951 – MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target Saughieside_Hill - after APXS retraction - ~2 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2951		Acquired on Date:		24-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2951		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00193		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00302				
2951MH0003020011004305C00		14713		CDPID				Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	3.7	Best Focus Image:		2951MH0001930001004314R00		4314		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	1.8	Range Map Product:		2951MH0001930001004315S00		4315		Motor Count Interval:		30		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2951MH0003020021004306I01		4306	x	2951MH0003020021004306C00	14593	4.11	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	255	1
2951MH0003020021004307I01		4307	x	2951MH0003020021004307C00	14623	4.01	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	223	2
2951MH0003020021004308I01		4308	x	2951MH0003020021004308C00	14653	3.92	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	191	3
2951MH0003020021004309I01		4309	x	2951MH0003020021004309C00	14683	3.83	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	159	4
2951MH0003020021004310I01		4310	x	2951MH0003020021004310C00	14713	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	127	5
2951MH0003020021004311I01		4311	x	2951MH0003020021004311C00	14743	3.66	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	85	6
2951MH0003020021004312I01		4312	x	2951MH0003020021004312C00	14773	3.58	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	63	7
2951MH0003020021004313I01		4313	x	2951MH0003020021004313C00	14803	3.50	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	31	8

updated: 07_January_2021

Sol 2955 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		Target Rest_and_Be_Thankful - Stereo-1 - After DRT - APXS Spot 2 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff												
Sol Data Were Acquired:			2955			Acquired on Date:			28-Nov-2020					
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:			2955			Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8	Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:			mhli00153		Image Acquisition Sequence:			mhli00699		
2955MH0006990011004324C00		14005					CDPID			Focus Merge Type:			Basic	
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2955MH0001530001004383R00			4383	This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack						
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2955MH0001530001004384S00			4384	Motor Count Interval:		30				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images			Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
2955MH0006990031004326I01		4326	—	2955MH0006990031004326C00			13885	7.7	-0.2 0.2		33.9	0.7	255	1
2955MH0006990031004327I01		4327	x	2955MH0006990031004327C00			13915	7.4	-0.2 0.2		33.1	0.6	223	2
2955MH0006990031004328I01		4328	x	2955MH0006990031004328C00			13945	7.2	-0.2 0.2		32.3	0.6	191	3
2955MH0006990031004329I01		4329	x	2955MH0006990031004329C00			13975	7.0	-0.2 0.2		31.6	0.6	159	4
2955MH0006990031004330I01		4330	x	2955MH0006990031004330C00			14005	6.8	-0.2 0.2		30.9	0.6	127	5
2955MH0006990031004331I01		4331	x	2955MH0006990031004331C00			14035	6.6	-0.2 0.2		30.2	0.6	85	6
2955MH0006990031004332I01		4332	—	2955MH0006990031004332C00			14065	6.4	-0.2 0.1		29.6	0.5	63	7
2955MH0006990031004333I01		4333	—	2955MH0006990031004333C00			14095	6.3	-0.1 0.1		28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 07_January_2021

Sol 2955 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		Target Rest_and_Be_Thankful - Stereo-2 - After DRT - APXS Spot 2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff												
Sol Data Were Acquired:			2955			Acquired on Date:			28-Nov-2020					
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:			2955			Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8	Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:			mhli00153		Image Acquisition Sequence:			mhli00699		
2955MH0006990011004335C00		14012					CDPID			Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2955MH0001530001004381R00			4381	This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack						
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2955MH0001530001004382S00			4382	Motor Count Interval:		30				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images			Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
								near	far					
2955MH0006990031004337I01		4337	—	2955MH0006990031004337C00			13892	7.6	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
2955MH0006990031004338I01		4338	x	2955MH0006990031004338C00			13922	7.4	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
2955MH0006990031004339I01		4339	x	2955MH0006990031004339C00			13952	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
2955MH0006990031004340I01		4340	x	2955MH0006990031004340C00			13982	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
2955MH0006990031004341I01		4341	x	2955MH0006990031004341C00			14012	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
2955MH0006990031004342I01		4342	x	2955MH0006990031004342C00			14042	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	85	6
2955MH0006990031004343I01		4343	—	2955MH0006990031004343C00			14072	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
2955MH0006990031004344I01		4344	—	2955MH0006990031004344C00			14102	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

updated: 07_January_2021

Sol 2955 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Rest_and_Be_Thankful** - After DRT - APXS Spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2955		Acquired on Date:		28-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2955		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00153		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00744		
2955MH0007440011004352C00		15124				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	2.8	Best Focus Image:		2955MH0001530001004379R00		4379		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	0.9	Range Map Product:		2955MH0001530001004380S00		4380		Motor Count Interval:		66		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2955MH0007440031004354I01	4354	—	2955MH0007440031004354C00	14860	3.36	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	255	1	
2955MH0007440031004355I01	4355	x	2955MH0007440031004355C00	14926	3.20	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	223	2	
2955MH0007440031004356I01	4356	x	2955MH0007440031004356C00	14992	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	191	3	
2955MH0007440031004357I01	4357	x	2955MH0007440031004357C00	15058	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	159	4	
2955MH0007440031004358I01	4358	x	2955MH0007440031004358C00	15124	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	127	5	
2955MH0007440031004359I01	4359	x	2955MH0007440031004359C00	15190	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	85	6	
2955MH0007440031004360I01	4360	—	2955MH0007440031004360C00	15256	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	63	7	
2955MH0007440031004361I01	4361	—	2955MH0007440031004361C00	15322	2.44	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	31	8	

updated: 07_January_2021

Sol 2955 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

Target **Rest_and_Be_Thankful** - After DRT - APXS Spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2955		Acquired on Date:		28-Nov-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2955		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00153		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00699		
2955MH0006990011004363C00		14007				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2955MH0001530001004377R00		4377		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2955MH0001530001004378S00		4378		Motor Count Interval:		30		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2955MH0006990031004365I01	4365	—	2955MH0006990031004365C00	13887	7.6	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1	
2955MH0006990031004366I01	4366	x	2955MH0006990031004366C00	13917	7.4	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2	
2955MH0006990031004367I01	4367	x	2955MH0006990031004367C00	13947	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3	
2955MH0006990031004368I01	4368	x	2955MH0006990031004368C00	13977	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4	
2955MH0006990031004369I01	4369	x	2955MH0006990031004369C00	14007	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5	
2955MH0006990031004370I01	4370	x	2955MH0006990031004370C00	14037	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	85	6	
2955MH0006990031004371I01	4371	—	2955MH0006990031004371C00	14067	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7	
2955MH0006990031004372I01	4372	—	2955MH0006990031004372C00	14097	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8	

updated: 28_December_2020

Sol 2959 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Edinburrie** - stereo-1 - after APXS retraction - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2959		Acquired on Date:		2-Dec-2020							
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2959		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00265		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00763			
2959MH0007630011004389C00		14022				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic			
computed working distance (cm):	6.7	Best Focus Image:		2959MH0002650001004412R00		4412		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack					
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.8	Range Map Product:		2959MH0002650001004413S00		4413		Motor Count Interval:		24			
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images		Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	Pixel Scale uncertainty ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far					
2959MH0007630031004391I01		4391	—	2959MH0007630031004391C00		13926	7.4	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
2959MH0007630031004392I01		4392	x	2959MH0007630031004392C00		13950	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
2959MH0007630031004393I01		4393	x	2959MH0007630031004393C00		13974	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
2959MH0007630031004394I01		4394	x	2959MH0007630031004394C00		13998	6.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
2959MH0007630031004395I01		4395	x	2959MH0007630031004395C00		14022	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
2959MH0007630031004396I01		4396	x	2959MH0007630031004396C00		14046	6.6	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	85	6
2959MH0007630031004397I01		4397	—	2959MH0007630031004397C00		14070	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
2959MH0007630031004398I01		4398	—	2959MH0007630031004398C00		14094	6.3	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 28_December_2020

Sol 2959 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Edinburrie** - stereo-2 - after APXS retraction - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2959		Acquired on Date:		2-Dec-2020							
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2959		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00265		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00763					
2959MH0007630011004400C00		14024				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic					
computed working distance (cm):	6.7	Best Focus Image:		2959MH0002650001004410R00		4410		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack					
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.8	Range Map Product:		2959MH0002650001004411S00		4411		Motor Count Interval: 24					
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images		Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far					
2959MH0007630031004402I01		4402	—	2959MH0007630031004402C00		13928	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
2959MH0007630031004403I01		4403	x	2959MH0007630031004403C00		13952	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
2959MH0007630031004404I01		4404	x	2959MH0007630031004404C00		13976	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
2959MH0007630031004405I01		4405	x	2959MH0007630031004405C00		14000	6.8	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
2959MH0007630031004406I01		4406	x	2959MH0007630031004406C00		14024	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
2959MH0007630031004407I01		4407	x	2959MH0007630031004407C00		14048	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	85	6
2959MH0007630031004408I01		4408	—	2959MH0007630031004408C00		14072	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
2959MH0007630031004409I01		4409	—	2959MH0007630031004409C00		14096	6.3	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_December_2020

Sol 2965 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Achnasheen** - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2965		Acquired on Date:		8-Dec-2020							
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2965		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00265		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00182			
2965MH0001820011004418C00		14037				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic			
computed working distance (cm):	6.6	Best Focus Image:		2965MH0002650001004439R00		4439		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack					
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.7	Range Map Product:		2965MH0002650001004440S00		4440		Motor Count Interval:		24			
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images		Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far					
2965MH0001820021004419I01		4419	x	2965MH0001820021004419C00		13941	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
2965MH0001820021004420I01		4420	x	2965MH0001820021004420C00		13965	7.1	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
2965MH0001820021004421I01		4421	x	2965MH0001820021004421C00		13989	6.9	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
2965MH0001820021004422I01		4422	x	2965MH0001820021004422C00		14013	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
2965MH0001820021004423I01		4423	x	2965MH0001820021004423C00		14037	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	127	5
2965MH0001820021004424I01		4424	x	2965MH0001820021004424C00		14061	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
2965MH0001820021004425I01		4425	—	2965MH0001820021004425C00		14085	6.3	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
2965MH0001820021004426I01		4426	—	2965MH0001820021004426C00		14109	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_December_2020

Sol 2965 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Achnasheen** - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2965		Acquired on Date:		8-Dec-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2965		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00265		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00182				
2965MH0001820011004428C00		14043				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.6	Best Focus Image:		2965MH0002650001004437R00		4437		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.7	Range Map Product:		2965MH0002650001004438S00		4438		Motor Count Interval: 24				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2965MH0001820021004429I01		4429	x	2965MH0001820021004429C00	13947	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
2965MH0001820021004430I01		4430	x	2965MH0001820021004430C00	13971	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
2965MH0001820021004431I01		4431	x	2965MH0001820021004431C00	13995	6.9	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
2965MH0001820021004432I01		4432	x	2965MH0001820021004432C00	14019	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
2965MH0001820021004433I01		4433	x	2965MH0001820021004433C00	14043	6.6	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
2965MH0001820021004434I01		4434	x	2965MH0001820021004434C00	14067	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	85	6
2965MH0001820021004435I01		4435	—	2965MH0001820021004435C00	14091	6.3	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
2965MH0001820021004436I01		4436	—	2965MH0001820021004436C00	14115	6.1	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_December_2020

Sol 2967 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Dun_Eideann** - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2967		Acquired on Date:		10-Dec-2020							
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2967		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00265		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00723					
2967MH0007230011004445C00		13986				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic					
computed working distance (cm):	6.9	Best Focus Image:		2967MH0002650001004468R00		4468		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack					
computed standoff distance (cm):	5.0	Range Map Product:		2967MH0002650001004469S00		4469		Motor Count Interval: 36					
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images		Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
								near	far				
2967MH0007230031004447I01		4447	x	2967MH0007230031004447C00		13842	8.0	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	255	1
2967MH0007230031004448I01		4448	x	2967MH0007230031004448C00		13878	7.7	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	223	2
2967MH0007230031004449I01		4449	x	2967MH0007230031004449C00		13914	7.4	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	191	3
2967MH0007230031004450I01		4450	x	2967MH0007230031004450C00		13950	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4
2967MH0007230031004451I01		4451	x	2967MH0007230031004451C00		13986	6.9	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
2967MH0007230031004452I01		4452	x	2967MH0007230031004452C00		14022	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
2967MH0007230031004453I01		4453	—	2967MH0007230031004453C00		14058	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
2967MH0007230031004454I01		4454	—	2967MH0007230031004454C00		14094	6.3	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_December_2020

Sol 2967 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Dun_Eideann** - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2967		Acquired on Date:		10-Dec-2020							
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2967		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00265		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00723					
2967MH0007230011004456C00		13993				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic					
computed working distance (cm):	6.9	Best Focus Image:		2967MH0002650001004466R00		4466		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack					
computed standoff distance (cm):	5.0	Range Map Product:		2967MH0002650001004467S00		4467		Motor Count Interval: 36					
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images		Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far					
2967MH0007230031004458I01		4458	x	2967MH0007230031004458C00		13849	8.0	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
2967MH0007230031004459I01		4459	x	2967MH0007230031004459C00		13885	7.7	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
2967MH0007230031004460I01		4460	x	2967MH0007230031004460C00		13921	7.4	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
2967MH0007230031004461I01		4461	x	2967MH0007230031004461C00		13957	7.1	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
2967MH0007230031004462I01		4462	x	2967MH0007230031004462C00		13993	6.9	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
2967MH0007230031004463I01		4463	x	2967MH0007230031004463C00		14029	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	85	6
2967MH0007230031004464I01		4464	—	2967MH0007230031004464C00		14065	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
2967MH0007230031004465I01		4465	—	2967MH0007230031004465C00		14101	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_December_2020

Sol 2969 – MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Coupar_Angus - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff												
Sol Data Were Acquired:			2969			Acquired on Date:			12-Dec-2020					
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:			2970			Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8	Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:			mhli00227		Image Acquisition Sequence:			mhli00699		
2969MH0006990011004474C00		14006					CDPID		Focus Merge Type:			Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2970MH0002270001004539R00		4539	This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack							
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2970MH0002270001004540S00		4540	Motor Count Interval:		30					
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images			Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
2969MH0006990031004476I01		4476	—	2969MH0006990031004476C00			13886	7.7	-0.2 0.2		33.9	0.7	255	1
2969MH0006990031004477I01		4477	x	2969MH0006990031004477C00			13916	7.4	-0.2 0.2		33.1	0.6	223	2
2969MH0006990031004478I01		4478	x	2969MH0006990031004478C00			13946	7.2	-0.2 0.2		32.3	0.6	191	3
2969MH0006990031004479I01		4479	x	2969MH0006990031004479C00			13976	7.0	-0.2 0.2		31.6	0.6	159	4
2969MH0006990031004480I01		4480	x	2969MH0006990031004480C00			14006	6.8	-0.2 0.2		30.9	0.6	127	5
2969MH0006990031004481I01		4481	x	2969MH0006990031004481C00			14036	6.6	-0.2 0.2		30.2	0.5	85	6
2969MH0006990031004482I01		4482	—	2969MH0006990031004482C00			14066	6.4	-0.2 0.1		29.5	0.5	63	7
2969MH0006990031004483I01		4483	—	2969MH0006990031004483C00			14096	6.3	-0.1 0.1		28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_December_2020

Sol 2969 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Coupar_Angus** - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2969		Acquired on Date:		12-Dec-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2970		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00227		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00699		
2969MH0006990011004485C00		14011		CDPID				Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2970MH0002270001004537R00		4537		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2970MH0002270001004538S00		4538		Motor Count Interval:		30		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2969MH0006990031004487I01		4487	—	2969MH0006990031004487C00	13891	7.6	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
2969MH0006990031004488I01		4488	x	2969MH0006990031004488C00	13921	7.4	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
2969MH0006990031004489I01		4489	x	2969MH0006990031004489C00	13951	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
2969MH0006990031004490I01		4490	x	2969MH0006990031004490C00	13981	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
2969MH0006990031004491I01		4491	x	2969MH0006990031004491C00	14011	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
2969MH0006990031004492I01		4492	x	2969MH0006990031004492C00	14041	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
2969MH0006990031004493I01		4493	—	2969MH0006990031004493C00	14071	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
2969MH0006990031004494I01		4494	—	2969MH0006990031004494C00	14101	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 2969 – MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target Coupar_Angus - ~2 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2969		Acquired on Date:		12-Dec-2020							
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2970		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00227		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00813			
2969MH0008130011004496C00		14706				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic			
computed working distance (cm):	3.8	Best Focus Image:		2970MH0002270001004535R00		4535		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack					
computed standoff distance (cm):	1.9	Range Map Product:		2970MH0002270001004536S00		4536		Motor Count Interval:		30			
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images		Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	Pixel Scale uncertainty ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far					
2969MH0008130031004498I01		4498	x	2969MH0008130031004498C00		14586	4.13	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	255	1
2969MH0008130031004499I01		4499	x	2969MH0008130031004499C00		14616	4.04	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	223	2
2969MH0008130031004500I01		4500	x	2969MH0008130031004500C00		14646	3.94	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	191	3
2969MH0008130031004501I01		4501	x	2969MH0008130031004501C00		14676	3.85	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	159	4
2969MH0008130031004502I01		4502	x	2969MH0008130031004502C00		14706	3.77	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	127	5
2969MH0008130031004503I01		4503	x	2969MH0008130031004503C00		14736	3.68	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	85	6
2969MH0008130031004504I01		4504	x	2969MH0008130031004504C00		14766	3.60	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	63	7
2969MH0008130031004505I01		4505	—	2969MH0008130031004505C00		14796	3.52	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	31	8

updated: 29_December_2020

Sol 2969 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Auchnafree_Hill** - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2969		Acquired on Date:		12-Dec-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2970		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00227		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00699				
2969MH0006990011004510C00		14004				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2970MH0002270001004533R00		4533		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2970MH0002270001004534S00		4534		Motor Count Interval:		30		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2969MH0006990031004512I01		4512	—	2969MH0006990031004512C00	13884	7.7	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
2969MH0006990031004513I01		4513	—	2969MH0006990031004513C00	13914	7.4	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	223	2
2969MH0006990031004514I01		4514	x	2969MH0006990031004514C00	13944	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
2969MH0006990031004515I01		4515	x	2969MH0006990031004515C00	13974	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
2969MH0006990031004516I01		4516	x	2969MH0006990031004516C00	14004	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
2969MH0006990031004517I01		4517	x	2969MH0006990031004517C00	14034	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	85	6
2969MH0006990031004518I01		4518	x	2969MH0006990031004518C00	14064	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
2969MH0006990031004519I01		4519	—	2969MH0006990031004519C00	14094	6.3	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_December_2020

Sol 2969 – MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Auchnafree_Hill** - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2969		Acquired on Date:		12-Dec-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2970		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00227		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00699				
2969MH0006990011004521C00		14006				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2970MH0002270001004531R00		4531		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2970MH0002270001004532S00		4532		Motor Count Interval:		30		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
						near	far					
2969MH0006990031004523I01		4523	—	2969MH0006990031004523C00	13886	7.7	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
2969MH0006990031004524I01		4524	—	2969MH0006990031004524C00	13916	7.4	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
2969MH0006990031004525I01		4525	x	2969MH0006990031004525C00	13946	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
2969MH0006990031004526I01		4526	x	2969MH0006990031004526C00	13976	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
2969MH0006990031004527I01		4527	x	2969MH0006990031004527C00	14006	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
2969MH0006990031004528I01		4528	x	2969MH0006990031004528C00	14036	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	85	6
2969MH0006990031004529I01		4529	x	2969MH0006990031004529C00	14066	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
2969MH0006990031004530I01		4530	—	2969MH0006990031004530C00	14096	6.3	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_December_2020

Sol 2972 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Torness** - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2972		Acquired on Date:		15-Dec-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2972		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00265		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00299		
2972MH0002990011004545C00		14001				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2972MH0002650001004566R00		4566		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2972MH0002650001004567S00		4567		Motor Count Interval:		36		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
						near	far					
	2972MH0002990021004546I01	4546	—	2972MH0002990021004546C00	13857	7.9	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	255	1
	2972MH0002990021004547I01	4547	—	2972MH0002990021004547C00	13893	7.6	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2
	2972MH0002990021004548I01	4548	x	2972MH0002990021004548C00	13929	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
	2972MH0002990021004549I01	4549	x	2972MH0002990021004549C00	13965	7.1	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
	2972MH0002990021004550I01	4550	x	2972MH0002990021004550C00	14001	6.8	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
	2972MH0002990021004551I01	4551	x	2972MH0002990021004551C00	14037	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	85	6
	2972MH0002990021004552I01	4552	—	2972MH0002990021004552C00	14073	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
	2972MH0002990021004553I01	4553	—	2972MH0002990021004553C00	14109	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_December_2020

Sol 2972 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Torness - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff												
Sol Data Were Acquired:			2972			Acquired on Date:			15-Dec-2020					
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:			2972			Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8	Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:			mhli00265		Image Acquisition Sequence:			mhli00299		
2972MH0002990011004555C00		14006					CDPID			Focus Merge Type:			Basic	
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2972MH0002650001004564R00			4564	This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack						
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2972MH0002650001004565S00			4565	Motor Count Interval:		36				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images			Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
								near	far					
2972MH0002990021004556I01		4556	—	2972MH0002990021004556C00			13862	7.8	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	255	1
2972MH0002990021004557I01		4557	—	2972MH0002990021004557C00			13898	7.6	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
2972MH0002990021004558I01		4558	x	2972MH0002990021004558C00			13934	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
2972MH0002990021004559I01		4559	x	2972MH0002990021004559C00			13970	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
2972MH0002990021004560I01		4560	x	2972MH0002990021004560C00			14006	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
2972MH0002990021004561I01		4561	x	2972MH0002990021004561C00			14042	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	85	6
2972MH0002990021004562I01		4562	—	2972MH0002990021004562C00			14078	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
2972MH0002990021004563I01		4563	—	2972MH0002990021004563C00			14114	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 30_December_2020

Sol 2974 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target An_Dun - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff													
Sol Data Were Acquired:			2974			Acquired on Date:			18-Dec-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:			2974			Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8	Relative						
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:			mhli00170		Image Acquisition Sequence:			mhli00224			
2974MH0002240011004571C00		14157					CDPID			Focus Merge Type:		Basic			
computed working distance (cm):	5.9	Best Focus Image:		2974MH0001700000904677R00		4677	This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack								
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.0	Range Map Product:		2974MH0001700000904678S00		4678	Motor Count Interval:		42						
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images			Motor Count	Range (cm) based on motor count to working distance equation		Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
								near		far					
2974MH0002240021004572I01		4572	—	2974MH0002240021004572C00			13989	6.9		-0.2 0.2		31.2	0.6	255	1
2974MH0002240021004573I01		4573	—	2974MH0002240021004573C00			14031	6.6		-0.2 0.2		30.3	0.6	223	2
2974MH0002240021004574I01		4574	x	2974MH0002240021004574C00			14073	6.4		-0.2 0.1		29.4	0.5	191	3
2974MH0002240021004575I01		4575	x	2974MH0002240021004575C00			14115	6.1		-0.1 0.1		28.5	0.5	159	4
2974MH0002240021004576I01		4576	x	2974MH0002240021004576C00			14157	5.9		-0.1 0.1		27.7	0.4	127	5
2974MH0002240021004577I01		4577	x	2974MH0002240021004577C00			14199	5.7		-0.1 0.1		27.0	0.4	85	6
2974MH0002240021004578I01		4578	x	2974MH0002240021004578C00			14241	5.5		-0.1 0.1		26.2	0.4	63	7
2974MH0002240021004579I01		4579	x	2974MH0002240021004579C00			14283	5.3		-0.1 0.1		25.5	0.4	31	8

updated: 30_December_2020

Sol 2974 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target An_Dun - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff												
Sol Data Were Acquired:			2974			Acquired on Date:			18-Dec-2020					
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:			2974			Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8	Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:			mhli00170		Image Acquisition Sequence:			mhli00224		
2974MH0002240011004581C00		14143					CDPID			Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	6.0	Best Focus Image:		2974MH0001700000904675R00		4675	This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack							
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.1	Range Map Product:		2974MH0001700000904676S00		4676	Motor Count Interval:		42					
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images			Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
2974MH0002240021004582I01		4582	—	2974MH0002240021004582C00			13975	7.0	-0.2 0.2		31.6	0.6	255	1
2974MH0002240021004583I01		4583	—	2974MH0002240021004583C00			14017	6.7	-0.2 0.2		30.6	0.6	223	2
2974MH0002240021004584I01		4584	—	2974MH0002240021004584C00			14059	6.5	-0.2 0.1		29.7	0.5	191	3
2974MH0002240021004585I01		4585	x	2974MH0002240021004585C00			14101	6.2	-0.1 0.1		28.8	0.5	159	4
2974MH0002240021004586I01		4586	x	2974MH0002240021004586C00			14143	6.0	-0.1 0.1		28.0	0.5	127	5
2974MH0002240021004587I01		4587	x	2974MH0002240021004587C00			14185	5.8	-0.1 0.1		27.2	0.4	85	6
2974MH0002240021004588I01		4588	x	2974MH0002240021004588C00			14227	5.6	-0.1 0.1		26.5	0.4	63	7
2974MH0002240021004589I01		4589	x	2974MH0002240021004589C00			14269	5.4	-0.1 0.1		25.8	0.4	31	8

updated: 30_December_2020

Sol 2974 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Cod_Baa** - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2974		Acquired on Date:		18-Dec-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2974		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00170		Image Acquisition Sequence:		mhli00699		
2974MH0006990011004598C00		14003				CDPID		Focus Merge Type:		Basic		
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2974MH0001700000904673R00		4673		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2974MH0001700000904674S00		4674		Motor Count Interval:		30		
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2974MH0006990031004600I01		4600	—	2974MH0006990031004600C00	13883	7.7	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
2974MH0006990031004601I01		4601	—	2974MH0006990031004601C00	13913	7.5	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	223	2
2974MH0006990031004602I01		4602	—	2974MH0006990031004602C00	13943	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
2974MH0006990031004603I01		4603	x	2974MH0006990031004603C00	13973	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
2974MH0006990031004604I01		4604	x	2974MH0006990031004604C00	14003	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
2974MH0006990031004605I01		4605	x	2974MH0006990031004605C00	14033	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	85	6
2974MH0006990031004606I01		4606	—	2974MH0006990031004606C00	14063	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
2974MH0006990031004607I01		4607	—	2974MH0006990031004607C00	14093	6.3	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 30_December_2020

Sol 2974 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Cod_Baa** - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2974		Acquired on Date:		18-Dec-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2974		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00170		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00699				
2974MH0006990011004609C00		14008				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.8	Best Focus Image:		2974MH0001700000904671R00		4671		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.9	Range Map Product:		2974MH0001700000904672S00		4672		Motor Count Interval: 30				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2974MH0006990031004611I01		4611	—	2974MH0006990031004611C00	13888	7.6	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
2974MH0006990031004612I01		4612	—	2974MH0006990031004612C00	13918	7.4	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
2974MH0006990031004613I01		4613	—	2974MH0006990031004613C00	13948	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
2974MH0006990031004614I01		4614	x	2974MH0006990031004614C00	13978	7.0	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
2974MH0006990031004615I01		4615	x	2974MH0006990031004615C00	14008	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
2974MH0006990031004616I01		4616	x	2974MH0006990031004616C00	14038	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
2974MH0006990031004617I01		4617	—	2974MH0006990031004617C00	14068	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
2974MH0006990031004618I01		4618	—	2974MH0006990031004618C00	14098	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 30_December_2020

Sol 2974 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Cod_Baa - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff											
Sol Data Were Acquired:			2974			Acquired on Date:			18-Dec-2020				
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:			2974			Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8	Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:			mhli00170		Image Acquisition Sequence:			mhli00744	
2974MH0007440011004620C00		15517					CDPID			Focus Merge Type:		Basic	
computed working distance (cm):	2.2	Best Focus Image:		2974MH0001700000904669R00		4669	This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack						
computed standoff distance (cm):	0.3	Range Map Product:		2974MH0001700000904670S00		4670	Motor Count Interval:		66				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images		Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
								near	far				
2974MH0007440031004622I01		4622	—	2974MH0007440031004622C00		14853	3.38	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	255	1
2974MH0007440031004623I01		4623	—	2974MH0007440031004623C00		14919	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	223	2
2974MH0007440031004624I01		4624	—	2974MH0007440031004624C00		14985	3.07	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	191	3
2974MH0007440031004625I01		4625	x	2974MH0007440031004625C00		15051	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	159	4
2974MH0007440031004626I01		4626	x	2974MH0007440031004626C00		15117	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
2974MH0007440031004627I01		4627	x	2974MH0007440031004627C00		15183	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	85	6
2974MH0007440031004628I01		4628	—	2974MH0007440031004628C00		15249	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	63	7
2974MH0007440031004629I01		4629	—	2974MH0007440031004629C00		15315	2.45	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	31	8

updated: 30_December_2020

Sol 2974 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Carn_Mor** - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2974		Acquired on Date:		18-Dec-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2974		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00170		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00182				
2974MH0001820011004634C00		14035				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.6	Best Focus Image:		2974MH0001700000904667R00		4667		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.7	Range Map Product:		2974MH0001700000904668S00		4668		Motor Count Interval: 24				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale <small>(µm/pixel)</small>	Pixel Scale uncertainty <small>(± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)</small>	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
						near	far					
2974MH0001820021004635I01		4635	—	2974MH0001820021004635C00	13939	7.3	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
2974MH0001820021004636I01		4636	x	2974MH0001820021004636C00	13963	7.1	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
2974MH0001820021004637I01		4637	x	2974MH0001820021004637C00	13987	6.9	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
2974MH0001820021004638I01		4638	x	2974MH0001820021004638C00	14011	6.8	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
2974MH0001820021004639I01		4639	x	2974MH0001820021004639C00	14035	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
2974MH0001820021004640I01		4640	x	2974MH0001820021004640C00	14059	6.5	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	85	6
2974MH0001820021004641I01		4641	—	2974MH0001820021004641C00	14083	6.3	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
2974MH0001820021004642I01		4642	—	2974MH0001820021004642C00	14107	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 30_December_2020

Sol 2974 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

target **Carn_Mor** - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff

Sol Data Were Acquired:		2974		Acquired on Date:		18-Dec-2020						
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:		2974		Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8		Relative				
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:		mhli00170		Image Acquisition Sequence: mhli00182				
2974MH0001820011004644C00		14041				CDPID		Focus Merge Type: Basic				
computed working distance (cm):	6.6	Best Focus Image:		2974MH0001700001004665R00		4665		This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack				
computed standoff distance (cm):	4.7	Range Map Product:		2974MH0001700000904666S00		4666		Motor Count Interval: 24				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images	Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
							near	far				
2974MH0001820021004645I01	4645	—	2974MH0001820021004645C00	13945	7.2	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1	
2974MH0001820021004646I01	4646	x	2974MH0001820021004646C00	13969	7.1	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2	
2974MH0001820021004647I01	4647	x	2974MH0001820021004647C00	13993	6.9	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3	
2974MH0001820021004648I01	4648	x	2974MH0001820021004648C00	14017	6.7	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4	
2974MH0001820021004649I01	4649	x	2974MH0001820021004649C00	14041	6.6	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5	
2974MH0001820021004650I01	4650	x	2974MH0001820021004650C00	14065	6.4	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6	
2974MH0001820021004651I01	4651	—	2974MH0001820021004651C00	14089	6.3	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7	
2974MH0001820021004652I01	4652	—	2974MH0001820021004652C00	14113	6.2	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8	

updated: 30_December_2020

Sol 2974 — MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Carn_Mor - ~2 cm standoff												
Sol Data Were Acquired:			2974			Acquired on Date:			18-Dec-2020					
Sol Images Were Focus Merged:			2974			Commanded Stack Depth & Type:		8	Relative					
Corresponding Frame		Motor Count		Merge Sequence:			mhli00170		Image Acquisition Sequence:			mhli00184		
2974MH0001840011004654C00		14654					CDPID			Focus Merge Type:			Basic	
computed working distance (cm):	3.9	Best Focus Image:		2974MH0001700001004663R00			4663	This is a merge of images 1 – 8 of an 8-image focus stack						
computed standoff distance (cm):	2.0	Range Map Product:		2974MH0001700001004664S00			4664	Motor Count Interval:		36				
Focus Stack Parent image Thumbnail IDs		MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Is this image in the merge product? (x = yes)	Individual Focus Stack Images			Motor Count	Range (cm) <small>based on motor count to working distance equation</small>	Depth of Field (cm) range uncertainty		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel) (using Depth of Field)	DN in Range Map	Image n of 8
2974MH0001840021004655I01		4655	—	2974MH0001840021004655C00			14610	4.05	-0.1 0.1		21.2	0.3	255	1
2974MH0001840021004656I01		4656	x	2974MH0001840021004656C00			14646	3.94	-0.1 0.1		20.8	0.3	223	2
2974MH0001840021004657I01		4657	x	2974MH0001840021004657C00			14682	3.84	-0.1 0.1		20.4	0.3	191	3
2974MH0001840021004658I01		4658	x	2974MH0001840021004658C00			14718	3.73	-0.1 0.1		20.0	0.3	159	4
2974MH0001840021004659I01		4659	x	2974MH0001840021004659C00			14754	3.63	-0.1 0.1		19.7	0.3	127	5
2974MH0001840021004660I01		4660	x	2974MH0001840021004660C00			14790	3.54	-0.1 0.1		19.4	0.3	85	6
2974MH0001840021004661I01		4661	—	2974MH0001840021004661C00			14826	3.44	-0.1 0.1		19.0	0.2	63	7
2974MH0001840021004662I01		4662	—	2974MH0001840021004662C00			14862	3.35	-0.1 0.1		18.7	0.2	31	8

updated: 07_January_2021

Sol 2989 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Ronas_Hill - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2989MH0001730010904689C00				
best focus image:	2991MH0008170000704750R00	4750	motor count:		13995	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	2991MH0008170000704751S00	4751	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00817	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		2989	focus merged on sol:		2991	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2989MH0001730020904690C00	4690	13875	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
2989MH0001730020904691C00	4691	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
2989MH0001730020904692C00	4692	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
2989MH0001730020904693C00	4693	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
2989MH0001730020904694C00	4694	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
2989MH0001730020904695C00	4695	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
2989MH0001730020904696C00	4696	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
2989MH0001730020904697C00	4697	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 07_January_2021

Sol 2989 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Ronas_Hill - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2989MH0001730010904699C00				
best focus image:	2991MH0008170000704748R00	4748	motor count:		14000	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	2991MH0008170000704749S00	4749	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00817	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		2989	focus merged on sol:		2991	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2989MH0001730020904700C00	4700	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
2989MH0001730020904701C00	4701	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
2989MH0001730020904702C00	4702	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
2989MH0001730020904703C00	4703	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
2989MH0001730020904704C00	4704	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
2989MH0001730020904705C00	4705	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	85	6
2989MH0001730020904706C00	4706	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
2989MH0001730020904707C00	4707	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 07_January_2021

Sol 2989 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Braewick_Beach - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2989MH0007630010904712C00				
best focus image:	2991MH0008170000704746R00	4746	motor count:		13905	range (cm):	7.5		
range map product:	2991MH0008170000704747S00	4747	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	2-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00817	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		2989	focus merged on sol:		2991	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2989MH0007630030904714C00	4714	13809	8.29	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	255	1
2989MH0007630030904715C00	4715	13833	8.08	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	223	2
2989MH0007630030904716C00	4716	13857	7.89	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	191	3
2989MH0007630030904717C00	4717	13881	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	159	4
2989MH0007630030904718C00	4718	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	127	5
2989MH0007630030904719C00	4719	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	85	6
2989MH0007630030904720C00	4720	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	63	7
2989MH0007630030904721C00	4721	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	31	8

updated: 07_January_2021

Sol 2989 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Braewick_Beach - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2989MH0007630010904723C00				
best focus image:	2991MH0008170000704744R00	4744	motor count:		13922	range (cm):	7.4		
range map product:	2991MH0008170000704745S00	4745	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	2-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00817	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		2989	focus merged on sol:		2991	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2989MH0007630030904725C00	4725	13826	8.14	-0.2	0.2	35.6	0.7	255	1
2989MH0007630030904726C00	4726	13850	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	223	2
2989MH0007630030904727C00	4727	13874	7.75	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	191	3
2989MH0007630030904728C00	4728	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	159	4
2989MH0007630030904729C00	4729	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	127	5
2989MH0007630030904730C00	4730	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	85	6
2989MH0007630030904731C00	4731	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	63	7
2989MH0007630030904732C00	4732	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	31	8

updated: 12_January_2021

Sol 2992 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2992MH0007210010604772C00				
best focus image:	2992MH0007070000604824R00	4824	motor count:		14184	range (cm):		5.8	
range map product:	2992MH0007070000604825S00	4825	acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	5-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00707	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		2992	focus merged on sol:		2992	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2992MH0007210030604774C00	4774	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	255	1
2992MH0007210030604775C00	4775	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	223	2
2992MH0007210030604776C00	4776	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	191	3
2992MH0007210030604777C00	4777	14142	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	159	4
2992MH0007210030604778C00	4778	14184	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	127	5
2992MH0007210030604779C00	4779	14226	5.56	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	85	6
2992MH0007210030604780C00	4780	14268	5.36	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	63	7
2992MH0007210030604781C00	4781	14310	5.17	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	31	8

updated: 12_January_2021

Sol 2992 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2992MH0007210010604783C00				
best focus image:	2992MH0007070000604822R00	4822	motor count:		14181	range (cm):		5.8	
range map product:	2992MH0007070000604823S00	4823	acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	5-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00707	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		2992	focus merged on sol:		2992	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2992MH0007210030604785C00	4785	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	255	1
2992MH0007210030604786C00	4786	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	223	2
2992MH0007210030604787C00	4787	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	191	3
2992MH0007210030604788C00	4788	14139	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	159	4
2992MH0007210030604789C00	4789	14181	5.79	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	127	5
2992MH0007210030604790C00	4790	14223	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	85	6
2992MH0007210030604791C00	4791	14265	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	63	7
2992MH0007210030604792C00	4792	14307	5.19	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	31	8

updated: 12_January_2021

Sol 2992 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	first merge of: target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2992MH0007230010604797C00				
best focus image:	2992MH0007070000604820R00	4820	motor count:		14126	range (cm):		6.1	
range map product:	2992MH0007070000604821S00	4821	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	5-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00707	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		2992	focus merged on sol:		2992	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2992MH0007230030604799C00	4799	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
2992MH0007230030604800C00	4800	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	223	2
2992MH0007230030604801C00	4801	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	191	3
2992MH0007230030604802C00	4802	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	159	4
2992MH0007230030604803C00	4803	14126	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	127	5
2992MH0007230030604804C00	4804	14162	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	85	6
2992MH0007230030604805C00	4805	14198	5.70	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	63	7
2992MH0007230030604806C00	4806	14234	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	31	8

updated: 12_January_2021

Sol 2992 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	second merge of: target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff - merge occurred following Sol 2996 arm fault which prevented new focus stack acquisition on Sol 2996								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2992MH0007230010604797C00				
best focus image:	2998MH0001630001100050R00	50	motor count:		14126	range (cm):		6.1	
range map product:	2998MH0001630001100051S00	51	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	5-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		2992	focus merged on sol:		2998	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2992MH0007230030604799C00	4799	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
2992MH0007230030604800C00	4800	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	223	2
2992MH0007230030604801C00	4801	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	191	3
2992MH0007230030604802C00	4802	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	159	4
2992MH0007230030604803C00	4803	14126	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	127	5
2992MH0007230030604804C00	4804	14162	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	85	6
2992MH0007230030604805C00	4805	14198	5.70	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	63	7
2992MH0007230030604806C00	4806	14234	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	31	8

updated: 12_January_2021

Sol 2992 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	first merge of: target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2992MH0007230010604808C00				
best focus image:	2992MH0007070000604818R00	4818	motor count:		14121	range (cm):		6.1	
range map product:	2992MH0007070000604819S00	4819	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	5-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00707	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		2992	focus merged on sol:		2992	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2992MH0007230030604810C00	4810	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
2992MH0007230030604811C00	4811	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	223	2
2992MH0007230030604812C00	4812	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	191	3
2992MH0007230030604813C00	4813	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	159	4
2992MH0007230030604814C00	4814	14121	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	127	5
2992MH0007230030604815C00	4815	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	85	6
2992MH0007230030604816C00	4816	14193	5.73	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	63	7
2992MH0007230030604817C00	4817	14229	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	31	8

updated: 12_January_2021

Sol 2992 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	second merge of: target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff - merge occurred following Sol 2996 arm fault which prevented new focus stack acquisition on Sol 2996								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2992MH0007230010604808C00				
best focus image:	2998MH0001630001100048R00	48	motor count:		14121	range (cm):		6.1	
range map product:	2998MH0001630001100049S00	49	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	5-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		2992	focus merged on sol:		2998	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2992MH0007230030604810C00	4810	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
2992MH0007230030604811C00	4811	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	223	2
2992MH0007230030604812C00	4812	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	191	3
2992MH0007230030604813C00	4813	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	159	4
2992MH0007230030604814C00	4814	14121	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	127	5
2992MH0007230030604815C00	4815	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	85	6
2992MH0007230030604816C00	4816	14193	5.73	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	63	7
2992MH0007230030604817C00	4817	14229	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	31	8

updated: 13_January_2021

Sol 2993 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		first merge of: target Ratharsair - bedform trough - ~17 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2993MH0007460010604829C00				
best focus image:	2993MH0007030001100005R00	5	motor count:		14760	range (cm):		3.6	
range map product:	2993MH0007030001100006S00	6	acquired sequence:		mhli00746	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Jan-21	merge sequence:		mhli00703	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		2993	focus merged on sol:		2993	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2993MH0007460030504831C00	4831	14568	4.19	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	255	1
2993MH0007460030504832C00	4832	14616	4.04	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	223	2
2993MH0007460030504833C00	4833	14664	3.89	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	191	3
2993MH0007460030504834C00	4834	14712	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	159	4
2993MH0007460030504835C00	4835	14760	3.62	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	127	5
2993MH0007460030504836C00	4836	14808	3.49	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	85	6
2993MH0007460030504837C00	4837	14856	3.37	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	63	7
2993MH0007460030504838C00	4838	14904	3.25	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	31	8

updated: 13_January_2021

Sol 2993 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		second merge of: target Ratharsair - bedform trough - ~17 mm standoff - merge occurred following Sol 2996 arm fault which prevented new focus stack acquisition on Sol 2996							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2993MH0007460010604829C00				
best focus image:	2998MH0001630001100046R00	46	motor count:		14760	range (cm):		3.6	
range map product:	2998MH0001630001100047S00	47	acquired sequence:		mhli00746	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Jan-21	merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		2993	focus merged on sol:		2998	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2993MH0007460030504831C00	4831	14568	4.19	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	255	1
2993MH0007460030504832C00	4832	14616	4.04	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	223	2
2993MH0007460030504833C00	4833	14664	3.89	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	191	3
2993MH0007460030504834C00	4834	14712	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	159	4
2993MH0007460030504835C00	4835	14760	3.62	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	127	5
2993MH0007460030504836C00	4836	14808	3.49	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	85	6
2993MH0007460030504837C00	4837	14856	3.37	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	63	7
2993MH0007460030504838C00	4838	14904	3.25	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	31	8

updated: 13_January_2021

Sol 2993 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	first merge of: target Airor - bedform crest - ~7 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2993MH0007940010504840C00				
best focus image:	2993MH0007030001100003R00	3	motor count:		15206	range (cm):		2.6	
range map product:	2993MH0007030001100004S00	4	acquired sequence:		mhli00794	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Jan-21	merge sequence:		mhli00703	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		2993	focus merged on sol:		2993	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2993MH0007940030504842C00	4842	15014	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	255	1
2993MH0007940030504843C00	4843	15062	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	223	2
2993MH0007940030504844C00	4844	15110	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	191	3
2993MH0007940030504845C00	4845	15158	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	159	4
2993MH0007940030504846C00	4846	15206	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	127	5
2993MH0007940030504847C00	4847	15254	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	85	6
2993MH0007940030504848C00	4848	15302	2.47	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	63	7
2993MH0007940030504849C00	4849	15350	2.40	0.0	0.1	15.3	0.2	31	8

updated: 13_January_2021

Sol 2993 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	second merge of: target Airor - bedform crest - ~7 mm standoff - merge occurred following Sol 2996 arm fault which prevented new focus stack acquisition on Sol 2996								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2993MH0007940010504840C00				
best focus image:	2998MH0001630001100044R00	44	motor count:		15206	range (cm):		2.6	
range map product:	2998MH0001630001100045S00	45	acquired sequence:		mhli00794	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Jan-21	merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		2993	focus merged on sol:		2998	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2993MH0007940030504842C00	4842	15014	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	255	1
2993MH0007940030504843C00	4843	15062	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	223	2
2993MH0007940030504844C00	4844	15110	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	191	3
2993MH0007940030504845C00	4845	15158	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	159	4
2993MH0007940030504846C00	4846	15206	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	127	5
2993MH0007940030504847C00	4847	15254	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	85	6
2993MH0007940030504848C00	4848	15302	2.47	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	63	7
2993MH0007940030504849C00	4849	15350	2.40	0.0	0.1	15.3	0.2	31	8

updated: 13_January_2021

Sol 2994 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		first merge of: target Traquair- stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2994MH0007400011100013C00				
best focus image:	2994MH0007030001100036R00	36	motor count:		14091	range (cm):		6.3	
range map product:	2994MH0007030001100037S00	37	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00703	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		2994	focus merged on sol:		2994	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2994MH0007400031100015C00	15	13875	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
2994MH0007400031100016C00	16	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
2994MH0007400031100017C00	17	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
2994MH0007400031100018C00	18	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	159	4
2994MH0007400031100019C00	19	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	127	5
2994MH0007400031100020C00	20	14145	5.98	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	85	6
2994MH0007400031100021C00	21	14199	5.70	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	63	7
2994MH0007400031100022C00	22	14253	5.43	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	31	8

updated: 13_January_2021

Sol 2994 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		second merge of: target Traquair- stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff - merge occurred following Sol 2996 arm fault which prevented new focus stack acquisition on Sol 2996							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2994MH0007400011100013C00				
best focus image:	2998MH0001630001100042R00	42	motor count:		14091	range (cm):		6.3	
range map product:	2998MH0001630001100043S00	43	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		2994	focus merged on sol:		2998	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2994MH0007400031100015C00	15	13875	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
2994MH0007400031100016C00	16	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
2994MH0007400031100017C00	17	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
2994MH0007400031100018C00	18	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	159	4
2994MH0007400031100019C00	19	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	127	5
2994MH0007400031100020C00	20	14145	5.98	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	85	6
2994MH0007400031100021C00	21	14199	5.70	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	63	7
2994MH0007400031100022C00	22	14253	5.43	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	31	8

updated: 13_January_2021

Sol 2994 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	first merge of: target Traquair- stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2994MH0007400011100024C00				
best focus image:	2994MH0007030001100034R00	34	motor count:		14103	range (cm):		6.2	
range map product:	2994MH0007030001100035S00	35	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-Jan-21	merge sequence:		mhli00703	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		2994	focus merged on sol:		2994	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2994MH0007400031100026C00	26	13887	7.65	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
2994MH0007400031100027C00	27	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
2994MH0007400031100028C00	28	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
2994MH0007400031100029C00	29	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	159	4
2994MH0007400031100030C00	30	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	127	5
2994MH0007400031100031C00	31	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	85	6
2994MH0007400031100032C00	32	14211	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	63	7
2994MH0007400031100033C00	33	14265	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8

updated: 13_January_2021

Sol 2994 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	second merge of: target Traquair- stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff - merge occurred following Sol 2996 arm fault which prevented new focus stack acquisition on Sol 2996								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		2994MH0007400011100024C00				
best focus image:	2998MH0001630001100040R00	40	motor count:		14103	range (cm):		6.2	
range map product:	2998MH0001630001100041S00	41	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-Jan-21	merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		2994	focus merged on sol:		2998	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
2994MH0007400031100026C00	26	13887	7.65	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
2994MH0007400031100027C00	27	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
2994MH0007400031100028C00	28	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
2994MH0007400031100029C00	29	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	159	4
2994MH0007400031100030C00	30	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	127	5
2994MH0007400031100031C00	31	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	85	6
2994MH0007400031100032C00	32	14211	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	63	7
2994MH0007400031100033C00	33	14265	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8

updated: 19_January_2021

Sol 3004 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3004MH0007630011100064C00			
best focus image:	3005MH0001930001100120R00	120	motor count:		14004	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3005MH0001930001100121S00	121	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3004	focus merged on sol:		3005	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3004MH0007630031100066C00	66	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3004MH0007630031100067C00	67	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3004MH0007630031100068C00	68	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3004MH0007630031100069C00	69	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3004MH0007630031100070C00	70	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3004MH0007630031100071C00	71	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3004MH0007630031100072C00	72	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3004MH0007630031100073C00	73	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 19_January_2021

Sol 3004 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3004MH0007630011100075C00			
best focus image:	3005MH0001930001100118R00	118	motor count:		14015	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3005MH0001930001100119S00	119	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3004	focus merged on sol:		3005	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3004MH0007630031100077C00	77	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
3004MH0007630031100078C00	78	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3004MH0007630031100079C00	79	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3004MH0007630031100080C00	80	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3004MH0007630031100081C00	81	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3004MH0007630031100082C00	82	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
3004MH0007630031100083C00	83	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3004MH0007630031100084C00	84	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 19_January_2021

Sol 3004 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3004MH0008010011100086C00				
best focus image:	3005MH0001930001100116R00	116	motor count:		15117	range (cm):		2.8	
range map product:	3005MH0001930001100117S00	117	acquired sequence:		mhli00801	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3004	focus merged on sol:		3005	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3004MH0008010031100088C00	88	14973	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	255	1
3004MH0008010031100089C00	89	15009	3.02	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	223	2
3004MH0008010031100090C00	90	15045	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	191	3
3004MH0008010031100091C00	91	15081	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	159	4
3004MH0008010031100092C00	92	15117	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
3004MH0008010031100093C00	93	15153	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	85	6
3004MH0008010031100094C00	94	15189	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7
3004MH0008010031100095C00	95	15225	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

updated: 21_January_2021

Sol 3007 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3007MH0002970011100125C00				
best focus image:	3008MH0001930001100158R00	158	motor count:		13992	range (cm):	6.9		
range map product:	3008MH0001930001100159S00	159	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3007	focus merged on sol:		3008	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3007MH0002970021100126C00	126	13752	8.81	-0.2	0.2	37.9	0.8	255	1
3007MH0002970021100127C00	127	13812	8.26	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.8	223	2
3007MH0002970021100128C00	128	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	191	3
3007MH0002970021100129C00	129	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	159	4
3007MH0002970021100130C00	130	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3007MH0002970021100131C00	131	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	85	6
3007MH0002970021100132C00	132	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	63	7
3007MH0002970021100133C00	133	14172	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	31	8

updated: 21_January_2021

Sol 3007 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3007MH0002970011100135C00				
best focus image:	3008MH0001930001100156R00	156	motor count:		14005	range (cm):	6.8		
range map product:	3008MH0001930001100157S00	157	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3007	focus merged on sol:		3008	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3007MH0002970021100136C00	136	13765	8.69	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	255	1
3007MH0002970021100137C00	137	13825	8.15	-0.2	0.2	35.6	0.7	223	2
3007MH0002970021100138C00	138	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	191	3
3007MH0002970021100139C00	139	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
3007MH0002970021100140C00	140	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3007MH0002970021100141C00	141	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3007MH0002970021100142C00	142	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	63	7
3007MH0002970021100143C00	143	14185	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8

updated: 21_January_2021

Sol 3007 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Easthouses - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff												
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3007MH0002970011100145C00								
best focus image:		3008MH0001930001100154R00		154		motor count:		14003		range (cm):		6.8		
range map product:		3008MH0001930001100155S00		155		acquired sequence:		mhli00297		stack type:		Relative		
acquired on date:		20-Jan-21				merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:			60		acquired on sol:		3007		focus merged on sol:		3008			
Individual Focus Stack Images		CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
					near	far								
3007MH0002970021100146C00		146	13763	8.71	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	255	1				
3007MH0002970021100147C00		147	13823	8.17	-0.2	0.2	35.7	0.7	223	2				
3007MH0002970021100148C00		148	13883	7.68	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	191	3				
3007MH0002970021100149C00		149	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4				
3007MH0002970021100150C00		150	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5				
3007MH0002970021100151C00		151	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6				
3007MH0002970021100152C00		152	14123	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	63	7				
3007MH0002970021100153C00		153	14183	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8				

updated: 27_January_2021

Sol 3010 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target La_Roque_Gageac - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3010MH0006990011100164C00							
best focus image:		3011MH0002270001100230R00		230		motor count:		14012		range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:		3011MH0002270001100231S00		231		acquired sequence:		mhli00699		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		24-Jan-21				merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		30		acquired on sol:		3010		focus merged on sol:		3011			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3010MH0006990031100166C00	166	13892	7.61	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1				
3010MH0006990031100167C00	167	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2				
3010MH0006990031100168C00	168	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3				
3010MH0006990031100169C00	169	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4				
3010MH0006990031100170C00	170	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5				
3010MH0006990031100171C00	171	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	85	6				
3010MH0006990031100172C00	172	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7				
3010MH0006990031100173C00	173	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8				

updated: 27_January_2021

Sol 3010 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target La_Roque_Gageac - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3010MH0006990011100175C00							
best focus image:		3011MH0002270001100228R00		228		motor count:		14013		range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:		3011MH0002270001100229S00		229		acquired sequence:		mhli00699		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		24-Jan-21				merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		30		acquired on sol:		3010		focus merged on sol:		3011			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3010MH0006990031100177C00	177	13893	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1				
3010MH0006990031100178C00	178	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2				
3010MH0006990031100179C00	179	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3				
3010MH0006990031100180C00	180	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4				
3010MH0006990031100181C00	181	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5				
3010MH0006990031100182C00	182	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	85	6				
3010MH0006990031100183C00	183	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7				
3010MH0006990031100184C00	184	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8				

updated: 27_January_2021

Sol 3010 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target La_Roque_Gageac - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3010MH0007850011100186C00			
best focus image:	3011MH0002270001100226R00	226	motor count:		15148	range (cm):		2.7	
range map product:	3011MH0002270001100227S00	227	acquired sequence:		mhli00785	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3010	focus merged on sol:		3011	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3010MH0007850031100188C00	188	14980	3.08	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	255	1
3010MH0007850031100189C00	189	15022	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	223	2
3010MH0007850031100190C00	190	15064	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	191	3
3010MH0007850031100191C00	191	15106	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4
3010MH0007850031100192C00	192	15148	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
3010MH0007850031100193C00	193	15190	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	85	6
3010MH0007850031100194C00	194	15232	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7
3010MH0007850031100195C00	195	15274	2.52	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8

updated: 27_January_2021

Sol 3010 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3010MH0007210011100200C00			
best focus image:	3011MH0002270001100224R00	224	motor count:		13996	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3011MH0002270001100225S00	225	acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3010	focus merged on sol:		3011	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3010MH0007210031100202C00	202	13828	8.13	-0.2	0.2	35.5	0.7	255	1
3010MH0007210031100203C00	203	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	223	2
3010MH0007210031100204C00	204	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
3010MH0007210031100205C00	205	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3010MH0007210031100206C00	206	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3010MH0007210031100207C00	207	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
3010MH0007210031100208C00	208	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3010MH0007210031100209C00	209	14122	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 27_January_2021

Sol 3010 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3010MH0007210011100211C00				
best focus image:	3011MH0002270001100222R00	222	motor count:		14002	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3011MH0002270001100223S00	223	acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3010	focus merged on sol:		3011	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3010MH0007210031100213C00	213	13834	8.08	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	255	1
3010MH0007210031100214C00	214	13876	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	223	2
3010MH0007210031100215C00	215	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3
3010MH0007210031100216C00	216	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3010MH0007210031100217C00	217	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3010MH0007210031100218C00	218	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	85	6
3010MH0007210031100219C00	219	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3010MH0007210031100220C00	220	14128	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 27_January_2021

Sol 3013 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Champagnac - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3013MH0001820011100235C00				
best focus image:	3013MH0001930001100268R00	268	motor count:		14009	range (cm):	6.8		
range map product:	3013MH0001930001100269S00	269	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	26-Jan-21	merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic				
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3013	focus merged on sol:		3013	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3013MH0001820021100236C00	236	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	255	1
3013MH0001820021100237C00	237	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
3013MH0001820021100238C00	238	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
3013MH0001820021100239C00	239	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3013MH0001820021100240C00	240	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3013MH0001820021100241C00	241	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	85	6
3013MH0001820021100242C00	242	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3013MH0001820021100243C00	243	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

updated: 27_January_2021

Sol 3013 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Champagnac - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3013MH0001820011100245C00				
best focus image:	3013MH0001930001100266R00	266	motor count:		14014	range (cm):	6.8		
range map product:	3013MH0001930001100267S00	267	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	26-Jan-21	merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic				
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3013	focus merged on sol:		3013	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3013MH0001820021100246C00	246	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
3013MH0001820021100247C00	247	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3013MH0001820021100248C00	248	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3013MH0001820021100249C00	249	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3013MH0001820021100250C00	250	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3013MH0001820021100251C00	251	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
3013MH0001820021100252C00	252	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3013MH0001820021100253C00	253	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 27_January_2021

Sol 3013 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Champagnac - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3013MH0001840011100255C00				
best focus image:	3013MH0001930001100264R00	264	motor count:		14715	range (cm):	3.7		
range map product:	3013MH0001930001100265S00	265	acquired sequence:		mhli00184	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	26-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3013	focus merged on sol:		3013	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3013MH0001840021100256C00	256	14571	4.18	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	255	1
3013MH0001840021100257C00	257	14607	4.06	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	223	2
3013MH0001840021100258C00	258	14643	3.95	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	191	3
3013MH0001840021100259C00	259	14679	3.84	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	159	4
3013MH0001840021100260C00	260	14715	3.74	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	127	5
3013MH0001840021100261C00	261	14751	3.64	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	85	6
3013MH0001840021100262C00	262	14787	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
3013MH0001840021100263C00	263	14823	3.45	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.2	31	8

updated: 01_February_2021

Sol 3015 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3015MH0007630011100274C00				
best focus image:	3015MH0001930001100310R00	310	motor count:		13987	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3015MH0001930001100311S00	311	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	28-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3015	focus merged on sol:		3015	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3015MH0007630031100276C00	276	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3015MH0007630031100277C00	277	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
3015MH0007630031100278C00	278	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3015MH0007630031100279C00	279	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3015MH0007630031100280C00	280	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3015MH0007630031100281C00	281	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	85	6
3015MH0007630031100282C00	282	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3015MH0007630031100283C00	283	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_February_2021

Sol 3015 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3015MH0007630011100285C00				
best focus image:	3015MH0001930001100308R00	308	motor count:		13992	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3015MH0001930001100309S00	309	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	28-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3015	focus merged on sol:		3015	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3015MH0007630031100287C00	287	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3015MH0007630031100288C00	288	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3015MH0007630031100289C00	289	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3015MH0007630031100290C00	290	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3015MH0007630031100291C00	291	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3015MH0007630031100292C00	292	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6
3015MH0007630031100293C00	293	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3015MH0007630031100294C00	294	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_February_2021

Sol 3015 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Beaupouyet - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3015MH0007940011100296C00				
best focus image:	3015MH0001930001100306R00	306	motor count:		15084	range (cm):		2.9	
range map product:	3015MH0001930001100307S00	307	acquired sequence:		mhli00794		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	28-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3015	focus merged on sol:		3015	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3015MH0007940031100298C00	298	14892	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	255	1
3015MH0007940031100299C00	299	14940	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	223	2
3015MH0007940031100300C00	300	14988	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	191	3
3015MH0007940031100301C00	301	15036	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	159	4
3015MH0007940031100302C00	302	15084	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	127	5
3015MH0007940031100303C00	303	15132	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	85	6
3015MH0007940031100304C00	304	15180	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7
3015MH0007940031100305C00	305	15228	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8

updated: 01_February_2021

Sol 3017 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Neuvic - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3017MH0007630011100316C00				
best focus image:	3018MH0001930001100370R00	370	motor count:		14038	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3018MH0001930001100371S00	371	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	31-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3017	focus merged on sol:		3018	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3017MH0007630031100318C00	318	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
3017MH0007630031100319C00	319	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
3017MH0007630031100320C00	320	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3017MH0007630031100321C00	321	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
3017MH0007630031100322C00	322	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
3017MH0007630031100323C00	323	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3017MH0007630031100324C00	324	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3017MH0007630031100325C00	325	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_February_2021

Sol 3017 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Neuvic - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3017MH0007630011100327C00				
best focus image:	3018MH0001930001100368R00	368	motor count:		14040	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3018MH0001930001100369S00	369	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	31-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3017	focus merged on sol:		3018	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3017MH0007630031100329C00	329	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
3017MH0007630031100330C00	330	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
3017MH0007630031100331C00	331	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3017MH0007630031100332C00	332	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
3017MH0007630031100333C00	333	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
3017MH0007630031100334C00	334	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3017MH0007630031100335C00	335	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3017MH0007630031100336C00	336	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_February_2021

Sol 3017 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Neuvic - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3017MH0008220011100338C00				
best focus image:	3018MH0001930001100366R00	366	motor count:		15217	range (cm):		2.6	
range map product:	3018MH0001930001100367S00	367	acquired sequence:		mhli00822	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	31-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3017	focus merged on sol:		3018	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3017MH0008220031100340C00	340	15121	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	255	1
3017MH0008220031100341C00	341	15145	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	223	2
3017MH0008220031100342C00	342	15169	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	191	3
3017MH0008220031100343C00	343	15193	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	159	4
3017MH0008220031100344C00	344	15217	2.62	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	127	5
3017MH0008220031100345C00	345	15241	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	85	6
3017MH0008220031100346C00	346	15265	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	63	7
3017MH0008220031100347C00	347	15289	2.49	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	31	8

updated: 04_February_2021

Sol 3020 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Lunas - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3020MH0001820011100376C00				
best focus image:	3020MH0002650001100397R00	397	motor count:		14022	range (cm):	6.7		
range map product:	3020MH0002650001100398S00	398	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	3-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic				
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3020	focus merged on sol:		3020	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3020MH0001820021100377C00	377	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3020MH0001820021100378C00	378	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3020MH0001820021100379C00	379	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3020MH0001820021100380C00	380	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3020MH0001820021100381C00	381	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3020MH0001820021100382C00	382	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	85	6
3020MH0001820021100383C00	383	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3020MH0001820021100384C00	384	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 04_February_2021

Sol 3020 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Lunas - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3020MH0001820011100386C00				
best focus image:	3020MH0002650001100395R00	395	motor count:		14019	range (cm):	6.7		
range map product:	3020MH0002650001100396S00	396	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	3-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic				
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3020	focus merged on sol:		3020	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3020MH0001820021100387C00	387	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3020MH0001820021100388C00	388	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3020MH0001820021100389C00	389	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3020MH0001820021100390C00	390	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3020MH0001820021100391C00	391	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3020MH0001820021100392C00	392	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	85	6
3020MH0001820021100393C00	393	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3020MH0001820021100394C00	394	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 08_February_2021

Sol 3022 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Tammies - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3022MH0001730011100403C00				
best focus image:	3022MH0001930001100436R00	436	motor count:		14009	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3022MH0001930001100437S00	437	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	5-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3022	focus merged on sol:		3022	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3022MH0001730021100404C00	404	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3022MH0001730021100405C00	405	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3022MH0001730021100406C00	406	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3022MH0001730021100407C00	407	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3022MH0001730021100408C00	408	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3022MH0001730021100409C00	409	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
3022MH0001730021100410C00	410	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3022MH0001730021100411C00	411	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 08_February_2021

Sol 3022 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Tammies - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3022MH0001730011100413C00				
best focus image:	3022MH0001930001100434R00	434	motor count:		14017	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3022MH0001930001100435S00	435	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	5-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3022	focus merged on sol:		3022	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3022MH0001730021100414C00	414	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3022MH0001730021100415C00	415	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3022MH0001730021100416C00	416	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3022MH0001730021100417C00	417	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3022MH0001730021100418C00	418	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3022MH0001730021100419C00	419	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	85	6
3022MH0001730021100420C00	420	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3022MH0001730021100421C00	421	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 08_February_2021

Sol 3022 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tammies - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3022MH0007960011100423C00				
best focus image:	3022MH0001930001100432R00	432	motor count:		15142	range (cm):		2.8	
range map product:	3022MH0001930001100433S00	433	acquired sequence:		mhli00796	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	5-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3022	focus merged on sol:		3022	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3022MH0007960021100424C00	424	14974	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	255	1
3022MH0007960021100425C00	425	15016	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	223	2
3022MH0007960021100426C00	426	15058	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
3022MH0007960021100427C00	427	15100	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	159	4
3022MH0007960021100428C00	428	15142	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
3022MH0007960021100429C00	429	15184	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	85	6
3022MH0007960021100430C00	430	15226	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
3022MH0007960021100431C00	431	15268	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8

updated: 11_February_2021

Sol 3024 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Coutures - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3024MH0007090011100442C00				
best focus image:	3025MH0001630001100520R00	520	motor count:		14004	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3025MH0001630001100521S00	521	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic				
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3024	focus merged on sol:		3025	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3024MH0007090031100444C00	444	13812	8.26	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.8	255	1
3024MH0007090031100445C00	445	13860	7.86	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	223	2
3024MH0007090031100446C00	446	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	191	3
3024MH0007090031100447C00	447	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
3024MH0007090031100448C00	448	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3024MH0007090031100449C00	449	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	85	6
3024MH0007090031100450C00	450	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
3024MH0007090031100451C00	451	14148	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 11_February_2021

Sol 3024 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Coutures - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3024MH0007090011100453C00				
best focus image:	3025MH0001630001100518R00	518	motor count:		14008	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3025MH0001630001100519S00	519	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic				
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3024	focus merged on sol:		3025	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3024MH0007090031100455C00	455	13816	8.23	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	255	1
3024MH0007090031100456C00	456	13864	7.83	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	223	2
3024MH0007090031100457C00	457	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
3024MH0007090031100458C00	458	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3024MH0007090031100459C00	459	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3024MH0007090031100460C00	460	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	85	6
3024MH0007090031100461C00	461	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
3024MH0007090031100462C00	462	14152	5.94	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3024 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Coutures - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3024MH0008230011100464C00				
best focus image:	3025MH0001630001100516R00	516	motor count:		15117	range (cm):		2.8	
range map product:	3025MH0001630001100517S00	517	acquired sequence:		mhli00823	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3024	focus merged on sol:		3025	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3024MH0008230031100466C00	466	14877	3.32	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	255	1
3024MH0008230031100467C00	467	14937	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	223	2
3024MH0008230031100468C00	468	14997	3.05	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	191	3
3024MH0008230031100469C00	469	15057	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	159	4
3024MH0008230031100470C00	470	15117	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
3024MH0008230031100471C00	471	15177	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	85	6
3024MH0008230031100472C00	472	15237	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7
3024MH0008230031100473C00	473	15297	2.48	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	31	8

updated: 11_February_2021

Sol 3024 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Biron - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3024MH0006990011100478C00				
best focus image:	3025MH0001630001100514R00	514	motor count:		13988	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3025MH0001630001100515S00	515	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3024	focus merged on sol:		3025	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3024MH0006990031100480C00	480	13868	7.80	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	255	1
3024MH0006990031100481C00	481	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
3024MH0006990031100482C00	482	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3024MH0006990031100483C00	483	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
3024MH0006990031100484C00	484	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3024MH0006990031100485C00	485	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6
3024MH0006990031100486C00	486	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3024MH0006990031100487C00	487	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 11_February_2021

Sol 3024 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Biron - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3024MH0006990011100489C00				
best focus image:	3025MH0001630001100512R00	512	motor count:		13992	range (cm):	6.9		
range map product:	3025MH0001630001100513S00	513	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	7-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3024	focus merged on sol:		3025	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3024MH0006990031100491C00	491	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
3024MH0006990031100492C00	492	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
3024MH0006990031100493C00	493	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
3024MH0006990031100494C00	494	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3024MH0006990031100495C00	495	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3024MH0006990031100496C00	496	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
3024MH0006990031100497C00	497	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3024MH0006990031100498C00	498	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

updated: 11_February_2021

Sol 3024 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Biron - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3024MH0007320011100500C00				
best focus image:	3025MH0001630001100510R00	510	motor count:		14641	range (cm):	4.0		
range map product:	3025MH0001630001100511S00	511	acquired sequence:		mhli00732	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	7-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3024	focus merged on sol:		3025	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3024MH0007320031100502C00	502	14497	4.43	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	255	1
3024MH0007320031100503C00	503	14533	4.31	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	223	2
3024MH0007320031100504C00	504	14569	4.19	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	191	3
3024MH0007320031100505C00	505	14605	4.07	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	159	4
3024MH0007320031100506C00	506	14641	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	127	5
3024MH0007320031100507C00	507	14677	3.85	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	85	6
3024MH0007320031100508C00	508	14713	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	63	7
3024MH0007320031100509C00	509	14749	3.65	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	31	8

updated: 11_February_2021

Sol 3026 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Labouquerie - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3026MH0003060011100526C00			
best focus image:	3026MH0002650001100547R00		547	motor count:		14077	range (cm):	6.4	
range map product:	3026MH0002650001100548S00		548	acquired sequence:		mhli00306	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	9-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3026	focus merged on sol:		3026	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	5	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3026MH0003060021100527C00	527	13861	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	255	1
3026MH0003060021100528C00	528	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
3026MH0003060021100529C00	529	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3026MH0003060021100530C00	530	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
3026MH0003060021100531C00	531	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	127	5
3026MH0003060021100532C00	532	14131	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	85	6
3026MH0003060021100533C00	533	14185	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	63	7
3026MH0003060021100534C00	534	14239	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	31	8

updated: 11_February_2021

Sol 3026 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Labouquerie - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3026MH0003060011100536C00			
best focus image:	3026MH0002650001100545R00		545	motor count:		14089	range (cm):	6.3	
range map product:	3026MH0002650001100546S00		546	acquired sequence:		mhli00306	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	9-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3026	focus merged on sol:		3026	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3026MH0003060021100537C00	537	13873	7.76	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
3026MH0003060021100538C00	538	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3026MH0003060021100539C00	539	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3026MH0003060021100540C00	540	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	159	4
3026MH0003060021100541C00	541	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	127	5
3026MH0003060021100542C00	542	14143	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	85	6
3026MH0003060021100543C00	543	14197	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	63	7
3026MH0003060021100544C00	544	14251	5.44	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	31	8

updated: 11_February_2021

Sol 3027 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Brantome - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3027MH0006990011100553C00				
best focus image:	3027MH0001930001100589R00	589	motor count:		14011	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3027MH0001930001100590S00	590	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	10-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3027	focus merged on sol:		3027	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3027MH0006990031100555C00	555	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3027MH0006990031100556C00	556	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3027MH0006990031100557C00	557	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3027MH0006990031100558C00	558	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3027MH0006990031100559C00	559	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3027MH0006990031100560C00	560	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
3027MH0006990031100561C00	561	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3027MH0006990031100562C00	562	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3027 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Brantome - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3027MH0006990011100564C00				
best focus image:	3027MH0001930001100587R00	587	motor count:		14021	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3027MH0001930001100588S00	588	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	10-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3027	focus merged on sol:		3027	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3027MH0006990031100566C00	566	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3027MH0006990031100567C00	567	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
3027MH0006990031100568C00	568	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
3027MH0006990031100569C00	569	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3027MH0006990031100570C00	570	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3027MH0006990031100571C00	571	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	85	6
3027MH0006990031100572C00	572	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3027MH0006990031100573C00	573	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3027 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Brantome - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3027MH0008240011100575C00				
best focus image:	3027MH0001930001100585R00	585	motor count:		14708	range (cm):		3.8	
range map product:	3027MH0001930001100586S00	586	acquired sequence:		mhli00824	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	10-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3027	focus merged on sol:		3027	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3027MH0008240031100577C00	577	14540	4.28	-0.1	0.1	22.0	0.3	255	1
3027MH0008240031100578C00	578	14582	4.14	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	223	2
3027MH0008240031100579C00	579	14624	4.01	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	191	3
3027MH0008240031100580C00	580	14666	3.88	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	159	4
3027MH0008240031100581C00	581	14708	3.76	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	127	5
3027MH0008240031100582C00	582	14750	3.64	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	85	6
3027MH0008240031100583C00	583	14792	3.53	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	63	7
3027MH0008240031100584C00	584	14834	3.42	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	31	8

updated: [12_February_2021](#)

Sol 3028 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Firbeix - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3028MH0003060011100595C00				
best focus image:	3028MH0002650001100616R00	616	motor count:		14025	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3028MH0002650001100617S00	617	acquired sequence:		mhli00306	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	11-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3028	focus merged on sol:		3028	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3028MH0003060021100596C00	596	13809	8.29	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	255	1
3028MH0003060021100597C00	597	13863	7.84	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	223	2
3028MH0003060021100598C00	598	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3
3028MH0003060021100599C00	599	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3028MH0003060021100600C00	600	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3028MH0003060021100601C00	601	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	85	6
3028MH0003060021100602C00	602	14133	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	63	7
3028MH0003060021100603C00	603	14187	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8

updated: [12_February_2021](#)

Sol 3028 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Firbeix - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3028MH0003060011100605C00				
best focus image:	3028MH0002650001100614R00	614	motor count:		14020	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3028MH0002650001100615S00	615	acquired sequence:		mhli00306	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	11-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3028	focus merged on sol:		3028	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3028MH0003060021100606C00	606	13804	8.33	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	255	1
3028MH0003060021100607C00	607	13858	7.88	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	223	2
3028MH0003060021100608C00	608	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
3028MH0003060021100609C00	609	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3028MH0003060021100610C00	610	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3028MH0003060021100611C00	611	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	85	6
3028MH0003060021100612C00	612	14128	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	63	7
3028MH0003060021100613C00	613	14182	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	31	8

updated: 16_February_2021

Sol 3031 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Dordogne - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3031MH0007230011100622C00				
best focus image:	3031MH0001530001100671R00	671	motor count:		13988	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3031MH0001530001100672S00	672	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3031	focus merged on sol:		3031	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3031MH0007230031100624C00	624	13844	7.99	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	255	1
3031MH0007230031100625C00	625	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
3031MH0007230031100626C00	626	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	191	3
3031MH0007230031100627C00	627	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3031MH0007230031100628C00	628	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3031MH0007230031100629C00	629	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3031MH0007230031100630C00	630	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3031MH0007230031100631C00	631	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 16_February_2021

Sol 3031 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Dordogne - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3031MH0007230011100633C00				
best focus image:	3031MH0001530001100669R00	669	motor count:		13988	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3031MH0001530001100670S00	670	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3031	focus merged on sol:		3031	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3031MH0007230031100635C00	635	13844	7.99	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	255	1
3031MH0007230031100636C00	636	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
3031MH0007230031100637C00	637	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	191	3
3031MH0007230031100638C00	638	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3031MH0007230031100639C00	639	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3031MH0007230031100640C00	640	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3031MH0007230031100641C00	641	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3031MH0007230031100642C00	642	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 16_February_2021

Sol 3031 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Dordogne - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3031MH0008230011100644C00				
best focus image:	3031MH0001530001100667R00	667	motor count:		15048	range (cm):		2.9	
range map product:	3031MH0001530001100668S00	668	acquired sequence:		mhli00823	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3031	focus merged on sol:		3031	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3031MH0008230031100646C00	646	14808	3.49	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	255	1
3031MH0008230031100647C00	647	14868	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	223	2
3031MH0008230031100648C00	648	14928	3.20	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	191	3
3031MH0008230031100649C00	649	14988	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	159	4
3031MH0008230031100650C00	650	15048	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	127	5
3031MH0008230031100651C00	651	15108	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	85	6
3031MH0008230031100652C00	652	15168	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
3031MH0008230031100653C00	653	15228	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8

updated: 16_February_2021

Sol 3031 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Dordogne - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3031MH0007230011100655C00				
best focus image:	3031MH0001530001100665R00	665	motor count:		13974	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3031MH0001530001100666S00	666	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3031	focus merged on sol:		3031	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3031MH0007230031100657C00	657	13830	8.11	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	255	1
3031MH0007230031100658C00	658	13866	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	223	2
3031MH0007230031100659C00	659	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	191	3
3031MH0007230031100660C00	660	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
3031MH0007230031100661C00	661	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	127	5
3031MH0007230031100662C00	662	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	85	6
3031MH0007230031100663C00	663	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3031MH0007230031100664C00	664	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

updated: 22_February_2021

Sol 3034 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Limeyrat - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3034MH0006990011100677C00				
best focus image:	3034MH0001530001100732R00	732	motor count:		13997	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3034MH0001530001100733S00	733	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3034	focus merged on sol:		3034	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3034MH0006990031100679C00	679	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	255	1
3034MH0006990031100680C00	680	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3034MH0006990031100681C00	681	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3034MH0006990031100682C00	682	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3034MH0006990031100683C00	683	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3034MH0006990031100684C00	684	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3034MH0006990031100685C00	685	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3034MH0006990031100686C00	686	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 22_February_2021

Sol 3034 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Limeyrat - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3034MH0006990011100688C00				
best focus image:	3034MH0001530001100730R00	730	motor count:		13998	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3034MH0001530001100731S00	731	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3034	focus merged on sol:		3034	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3034MH0006990031100690C00	690	13878	7.72	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	255	1
3034MH0006990031100691C00	691	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3034MH0006990031100692C00	692	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3034MH0006990031100693C00	693	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3034MH0006990031100694C00	694	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3034MH0006990031100695C00	695	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3034MH0006990031100696C00	696	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3034MH0006990031100697C00	697	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 22_February_2021

Sol 3034 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Limeyrat - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3034MH0007850011100705C00				
best focus image:	3034MH0001530001100728R00	728	motor count:		15085	range (cm):		2.9	
range map product:	3034MH0001530001100729S00	729	acquired sequence:		mhli00785	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3034	focus merged on sol:		3034	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3034MH0007850031100707C00	707	14917	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	255	1
3034MH0007850031100708C00	708	14959	3.13	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	223	2
3034MH0007850031100709C00	709	15001	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	191	3
3034MH0007850031100710C00	710	15043	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	159	4
3034MH0007850031100711C00	711	15085	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	127	5
3034MH0007850031100712C00	712	15127	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	85	6
3034MH0007850031100713C00	713	15169	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
3034MH0007850031100714C00	714	15211	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

updated: 22_February_2021

Sol 3034 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Limeyrat - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3034MH0006990011100716C00				
best focus image:	3034MH0001530001100726R00	726	motor count:		13979	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3034MH0001530001100727S00	727	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3034	focus merged on sol:		3034	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3034MH0006990031100718C00	718	13859	7.87	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	255	1
3034MH0006990031100719C00	719	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	223	2
3034MH0006990031100720C00	720	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3
3034MH0006990031100721C00	721	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4
3034MH0006990031100722C00	722	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3034MH0006990031100723C00	723	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	85	6
3034MH0006990031100724C00	724	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3034MH0006990031100725C00	725	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_March_2021

Sol 3035 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3035MH0006990011100738C00				
best focus image:	3036MH0001530001100791R00	791	motor count:		14045	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3036MH0001530001100792S00	792	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3035	focus merged on sol:		3036	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3035MH0006990031100740C00	740	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3035MH0006990031100741C00	741	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3035MH0006990031100742C00	742	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
3035MH0006990031100743C00	743	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
3035MH0006990031100744C00	744	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
3035MH0006990031100745C00	745	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	85	6
3035MH0006990031100746C00	746	14105	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3035MH0006990031100747C00	747	14135	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_March_2021

Sol 3035 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3035MH0006990011100749C00				
best focus image:	3036MH0001530001100789R00	789	motor count:		14045	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3036MH0001530001100790S00	790	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3035	focus merged on sol:		3036	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3035MH0006990031100751C00	751	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3035MH0006990031100752C00	752	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3035MH0006990031100753C00	753	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
3035MH0006990031100754C00	754	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
3035MH0006990031100755C00	755	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
3035MH0006990031100756C00	756	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	85	6
3035MH0006990031100757C00	757	14105	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3035MH0006990031100758C00	758	14135	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_March_2021

Sol 3035 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - ~45 mm standoff									
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3035MH0006990011100760C00					
best focus image:		3036MH0001530001100787R00		787		motor count:		14048		range (cm): 6.5	
range map product:		3036MH0001530001100788S00		788		acquired sequence:		mhli00699		stack type: Relative	
acquired on date:		18-Feb-21				merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30		acquired on sol:		3035		focus merged on sol:		3036	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8		
				near	far						
3035MH0006990031100762C00	762	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1		
3035MH0006990031100763C00	763	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2		
3035MH0006990031100764C00	764	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3		
3035MH0006990031100765C00	765	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4		
3035MH0006990031100766C00	766	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5		
3035MH0006990031100767C00	767	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	85	6		
3035MH0006990031100768C00	768	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7		
3035MH0006990031100769C00	769	14138	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8		

updated: 25_February_2021

Sol 3036 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Fleurac - APXS Spot 2 - ~3 cm standoff												
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3036MH0008250011100775C00								
best focus image:		3036MH0001530001100785R00		785		motor count:		14359		range (cm):		5.0		
range map product:		3036MH0001530001100786S00		786		acquired sequence:		mhli00825		stack type:		Relative		
acquired on date:		19-Feb-21				merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:			30		acquired on sol:		3036		focus merged on sol:		3036			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8					
				near	far									
3036MH0008250031100777C00	777	14239	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	255	1					
3036MH0008250031100778C00	778	14269	5.36	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	223	2					
3036MH0008250031100779C00	779	14299	5.22	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	191	3					
3036MH0008250031100780C00	780	14329	5.09	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	159	4					
3036MH0008250031100781C00	781	14359	4.96	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	127	5					
3036MH0008250031100782C00	782	14389	4.84	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	85	6					
3036MH0008250031100783C00	783	14419	4.72	-0.1	0.1	23.5	0.3	63	7					
3036MH0008250031100784C00	784	14449	4.61	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	31	8					

updated: 25_February_2021

Sol 3037 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Chalus - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3037MH0007630011100797C00				
best focus image:	3037MH0001530001100846R00	846	motor count:		14017	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3037MH0001530001100847S00	847	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	20-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3037	focus merged on sol:		3037	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3037MH0007630031100799C00	799	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3037MH0007630031100800C00	800	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3037MH0007630031100801C00	801	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3037MH0007630031100802C00	802	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3037MH0007630031100803C00	803	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3037MH0007630031100804C00	804	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
3037MH0007630031100805C00	805	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3037MH0007630031100806C00	806	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 25_February_2021

Sol 3037 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Chalus - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3037MH0007630011100808C00				
best focus image:	3037MH0001530001100844R00	844	motor count:		14026	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3037MH0001530001100845S00	845	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	20-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3037	focus merged on sol:		3037	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3037MH0007630031100810C00	810	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3037MH0007630031100811C00	811	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3037MH0007630031100812C00	812	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
3037MH0007630031100813C00	813	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3037MH0007630031100814C00	814	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3037MH0007630031100815C00	815	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	85	6
3037MH0007630031100816C00	816	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3037MH0007630031100817C00	817	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 25_February_2021

Sol 3037 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Chalus - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3037MH0008130011100819C00			
best focus image:	3037MH0001530001100842R00	842	motor count:		14720	range (cm):	3.7		
range map product:	3037MH0001530001100843S00	843	acquired sequence:		mhli00813	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3037	focus merged on sol:		3037	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3037MH0008130031100821C00	821	14600	4.09	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	255	1
3037MH0008130031100822C00	822	14630	3.99	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	223	2
3037MH0008130031100823C00	823	14660	3.90	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	191	3
3037MH0008130031100824C00	824	14690	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	159	4
3037MH0008130031100825C00	825	14720	3.73	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	127	5
3037MH0008130031100826C00	826	14750	3.64	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	85	6
3037MH0008130031100827C00	827	14780	3.56	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
3037MH0008130031100828C00	828	14810	3.48	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	31	8

updated: 25_February_2021

Sol 3037 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Chalus - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3037MH0007630011100830C00			
best focus image:	3037MH0001530001100840R00	840	motor count:		14004	range (cm):	6.8		
range map product:	3037MH0001530001100841S00	841	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3037	focus merged on sol:		3037	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3037MH0007630031100832C00	832	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3037MH0007630031100833C00	833	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3037MH0007630031100834C00	834	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3037MH0007630031100835C00	835	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3037MH0007630031100836C00	836	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3037MH0007630031100837C00	837	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3037MH0007630031100838C00	838	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3037MH0007630031100839C00	839	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 25_February_2021

Sol 3040 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Plazac - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3040MH0007630011100852C00				
best focus image:	3040MH0002650001100875R00	875	motor count:		14033	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3040MH0002650001100876S00	876	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	23-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3040	focus merged on sol:		3040	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3040MH0007630031100854C00	854	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3040MH0007630031100855C00	855	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
3040MH0007630031100856C00	856	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
3040MH0007630031100857C00	857	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
3040MH0007630031100858C00	858	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
3040MH0007630031100859C00	859	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	85	6
3040MH0007630031100860C00	860	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3040MH0007630031100861C00	861	14105	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 25_February_2021

Sol 3040 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Plazac - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3040MH0007630011100863C00				
best focus image:	3040MH0002650001100873R00	873	motor count:		14042	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3040MH0002650001100874S00	874	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	23-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3040	focus merged on sol:		3040	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3040MH0007630031100865C00	865	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
3040MH0007630031100866C00	866	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
3040MH0007630031100867C00	867	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
3040MH0007630031100868C00	868	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
3040MH0007630031100869C00	869	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	127	5
3040MH0007630031100870C00	870	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	85	6
3040MH0007630031100871C00	871	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3040MH0007630031100872C00	872	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_March_2021

Sol 3042 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Manzac - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3042MH0007230011100881C00				
best focus image:	3042MH0002650001100904R00	904	motor count:		14031	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3042MH0002650001100905S00	905	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3042	focus merged on sol:		3042	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3042MH0007230031100883C00	883	13887	7.65	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3042MH0007230031100884C00	884	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3042MH0007230031100885C00	885	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3042MH0007230031100886C00	886	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3042MH0007230031100887C00	887	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3042MH0007230031100888C00	888	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	85	6
3042MH0007230031100889C00	889	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
3042MH0007230031100890C00	890	14139	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_March_2021

Sol 3042 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Manzac - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3042MH0007230011100892C00				
best focus image:	3042MH0002650001100902R00	902	motor count:		14039	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3042MH0002650001100903S00	903	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3042	focus merged on sol:		3042	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3042MH0007230031100894C00	894	13895	7.59	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3042MH0007230031100895C00	895	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
3042MH0007230031100896C00	896	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3042MH0007230031100897C00	897	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3042MH0007230031100898C00	898	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
3042MH0007230031100899C00	899	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	85	6
3042MH0007230031100900C00	900	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	63	7
3042MH0007230031100901C00	901	14147	5.97	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_March_2021

Sol 3044 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pazayac - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3044MH0007090011100910C00				
best focus image:	3044MH0001630001100988R00	988	motor count:		13943	range (cm):		7.2	
range map product:	3044MH0001630001100989S00	989	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3044	focus merged on sol:		3044	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3044MH0007090031100912C00	912	13751	8.82	-0.2	0.2	37.9	0.8	255	1
3044MH0007090031100913C00	913	13799	8.38	-0.2	0.2	36.4	0.8	223	2
3044MH0007090031100914C00	914	13847	7.97	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	191	3
3044MH0007090031100915C00	915	13895	7.59	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	159	4
3044MH0007090031100916C00	916	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	127	5
3044MH0007090031100917C00	917	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	85	6
3044MH0007090031100918C00	918	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3044MH0007090031100919C00	919	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_March_2021

Sol 3044 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pazayac - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3044MH0007090011100921C00				
best focus image:	3044MH0001630001100986R00	986	motor count:		13966	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3044MH0001630001100987S00	987	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Feb-21	merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3044	focus merged on sol:		3044	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3044MH0007090031100923C00	923	13774	8.60	-0.2	0.2	37.2	0.8	255	1
3044MH0007090031100924C00	924	13822	8.18	-0.2	0.2	35.7	0.7	223	2
3044MH0007090031100925C00	925	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	191	3
3044MH0007090031100926C00	926	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	159	4
3044MH0007090031100927C00	927	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	127	5
3044MH0007090031100928C00	928	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	85	6
3044MH0007090031100929C00	929	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3044MH0007090031100930C00	930	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_March_2021

Sol 3044 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pazayac - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3044MH0007940011100932C00				
best focus image:	3044MH0001630001100984R00	984	motor count:		14958	range (cm):		3.1	
range map product:	3044MH0001630001100985S00	985	acquired sequence:		mhli00794	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3044	focus merged on sol:		3044	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3044MH0007940031100934C00	934	14766	3.60	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	255	1
3044MH0007940031100935C00	935	14814	3.47	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	223	2
3044MH0007940031100936C00	936	14862	3.35	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	191	3
3044MH0007940031100937C00	937	14910	3.24	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	159	4
3044MH0007940031100938C00	938	14958	3.13	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	127	5
3044MH0007940031100939C00	939	15006	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	85	6
3044MH0007940031100940C00	940	15054	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	63	7
3044MH0007940031100941C00	941	15102	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	31	8

updated: 01_March_2021

Sol 3044 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Sadillac - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3044MH0007090011100946C00				
best focus image:	3044MH0001630001100982R00	982	motor count:		13936	range (cm):		7.3	
range map product:	3044MH0001630001100983S00	983	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3044	focus merged on sol:		3044	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3044MH0007090031100948C00	948	13744	8.89	-0.3	0.2	38.2	0.8	255	1
3044MH0007090031100949C00	949	13792	8.44	-0.2	0.2	36.6	0.8	223	2
3044MH0007090031100950C00	950	13840	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	191	3
3044MH0007090031100951C00	951	13888	7.64	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	159	4
3044MH0007090031100952C00	952	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	127	5
3044MH0007090031100953C00	953	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	85	6
3044MH0007090031100954C00	954	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3044MH0007090031100955C00	955	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_March_2021

Sol 3044 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Sadillac - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3044MH0007090011100957C00				
best focus image:	3044MH0001630001100980R00	980	motor count:		13942	range (cm):		7.2	
range map product:	3044MH0001630001100981S00	981	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3044	focus merged on sol:		3044	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3044MH0007090031100959C00	959	13750	8.83	-0.2	0.2	38.0	0.8	255	1
3044MH0007090031100960C00	960	13798	8.39	-0.2	0.2	36.4	0.8	223	2
3044MH0007090031100961C00	961	13846	7.98	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	191	3
3044MH0007090031100962C00	962	13894	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	159	4
3044MH0007090031100963C00	963	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	127	5
3044MH0007090031100964C00	964	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	85	6
3044MH0007090031100965C00	965	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3044MH0007090031100966C00	966	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_March_2021

Sol 3044 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Sadillac - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3044MH0006580011100968C00				
best focus image:	3044MH0001630001100978R00	978	motor count:		14910	range (cm):		3.2	
range map product:	3044MH0001630001100979S00	979	acquired sequence:		mhli00658	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Feb-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		72	acquired on sol:		3044	focus merged on sol:		3044	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3044MH0006580031100970C00	970	14622	4.02	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	255	1
3044MH0006580031100971C00	971	14694	3.80	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	223	2
3044MH0006580031100972C00	972	14766	3.60	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	191	3
3044MH0006580031100973C00	973	14838	3.41	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	159	4
3044MH0006580031100974C00	974	14910	3.24	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	127	5
3044MH0006580031100975C00	975	14982	3.08	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	85	6
3044MH0006580031100976C00	976	15054	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	63	7
3044MH0006580031100977C00	977	15126	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	31	8

updated: 09_March_2021

Sol 3047 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Daglan - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3047MH0006990011100994C00				
best focus image:	3047MH0002650001101017R00	1017	motor count:		14035	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3047MH0002650001101018S00	1018	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Mar-21	merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3047	focus merged on sol:		3047	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3047MH0006990031100996C00	996	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
3047MH0006990031100997C00	997	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3047MH0006990031100998C00	998	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3047MH0006990031100999C00	999	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3047MH0006990031101000C00	1000	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
3047MH0006990031101001C00	1001	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3047MH0006990031101002C00	1002	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	63	7
3047MH0006990031101003C00	1003	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 09_March_2021

Sol 3047 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Daglan - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3047MH0006990011101005C00				
best focus image:	3047MH0002650001101015R00	1015	motor count:		14036	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3047MH0002650001101016S00	1016	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Mar-21	merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3047	focus merged on sol:		3047	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3047MH0006990031101007C00	1007	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
3047MH0006990031101008C00	1008	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3047MH0006990031101009C00	1009	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3047MH0006990031101010C00	1010	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3047MH0006990031101011C00	1011	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	127	5
3047MH0006990031101012C00	1012	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	85	6
3047MH0006990031101013C00	1013	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	63	7
3047MH0006990031101014C00	1014	14126	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 10_March_2021

Sol 3051 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Montrem - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3051MH0007230011101029C00			
best focus image:	3052MH0002270001101094R00	1094	motor count:		14001	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3052MH0002270001101095S00	1095	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-Mar-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3051	focus merged on sol:		3052	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3051MH0007230031101031C00	1031	13857	7.89	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	255	1
3051MH0007230031101032C00	1032	13893	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2
3051MH0007230031101033C00	1033	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3051MH0007230031101034C00	1034	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3051MH0007230031101035C00	1035	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3051MH0007230031101036C00	1036	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	85	6
3051MH0007230031101037C00	1037	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3051MH0007230031101038C00	1038	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 10_March_2021

Sol 3051 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Montrem - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3051MH0007230011101040C00			
best focus image:	3052MH0002270001101092R00	1092	motor count:		14006	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3052MH0002270001101093S00	1093	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-Mar-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3051	focus merged on sol:		3052	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3051MH0007230031101042C00	1042	13862	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	255	1
3051MH0007230031101043C00	1043	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
3051MH0007230031101044C00	1044	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
3051MH0007230031101045C00	1045	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3051MH0007230031101046C00	1046	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3051MH0007230031101047C00	1047	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	85	6
3051MH0007230031101048C00	1048	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3051MH0007230031101049C00	1049	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 10_March_2021

Sol 3051 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Montrem - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3051MH0007850011101051C00			
best focus image:	3052MH0002270001101090R00	1090	motor count:		15111	range (cm):	2.8		
range map product:	3052MH0002270001101091S00	1091	acquired sequence:		mhli00785	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	7-Mar-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3051	focus merged on sol:		3052	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3051MH0007850031101053C00	1053	14943	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	255	1
3051MH0007850031101054C00	1054	14985	3.07	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	223	2
3051MH0007850031101055C00	1055	15027	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	191	3
3051MH0007850031101056C00	1056	15069	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	159	4
3051MH0007850031101057C00	1057	15111	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
3051MH0007850031101058C00	1058	15153	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	85	6
3051MH0007850031101059C00	1059	15195	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	63	7
3051MH0007850031101060C00	1060	15237	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8

updated: 10_March_2021

Sol 3051 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Peyrat - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3051MH0007230011101065C00			
best focus image:	3052MH0002270001101088R00	1088	motor count:		14144	range (cm):	6.0		
range map product:	3052MH0002270001101089S00	1089	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	7-Mar-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3051	focus merged on sol:		3052	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3051MH0007230031101067C00	1067	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	255	1
3051MH0007230031101068C00	1068	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	223	2
3051MH0007230031101069C00	1069	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	191	3
3051MH0007230031101070C00	1070	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	159	4
3051MH0007230031101071C00	1071	14144	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	127	5
3051MH0007230031101072C00	1072	14180	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	85	6
3051MH0007230031101073C00	1073	14216	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	63	7
3051MH0007230031101074C00	1074	14252	5.44	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	31	8

updated: 10_March_2021

Sol 3051 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Peyrat- stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3051MH0007230011101076C00				
best focus image:	3052MH0002270001101086R00	1086	motor count:		14132	range (cm):		6.1	
range map product:	3052MH0002270001101087S00	1087	acquired sequence:		mhli00723		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	7-Mar-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3051	focus merged on sol:		3052	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3051MH0007230031101078C00	1078	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1
3051MH0007230031101079C00	1079	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	223	2
3051MH0007230031101080C00	1080	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	191	3
3051MH0007230031101081C00	1081	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	159	4
3051MH0007230031101082C00	1082	14132	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	127	5
3051MH0007230031101083C00	1083	14168	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	85	6
3051MH0007230031101084C00	1084	14204	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	63	7
3051MH0007230031101085C00	1085	14240	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	31	8

updated: 15_March_2021

Sol 3054 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nontron - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3054MH0007630011101104C00			
best focus image:	3054MH0001530001101155R00	1155	motor count:		14001	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3054MH0001530001101156S00	1156	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	10-Mar-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3054	focus merged on sol:		3054	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3054MH0007630031101106C00	1106	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3054MH0007630031101107C00	1107	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
3054MH0007630031101108C00	1108	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3054MH0007630031101109C00	1109	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3054MH0007630031101110C00	1110	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3054MH0007630031101111C00	1111	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3054MH0007630031101112C00	1112	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3054MH0007630031101113C00	1113	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 15_March_2021

Sol 3054 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nontron - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3054MH0007630011101115C00			
best focus image:	3054MH0001530001101153R00	1153	motor count:		14004	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3054MH0001530001101154S00	1154	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	10-Mar-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3054	focus merged on sol:		3054	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3054MH0007630031101117C00	1117	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3054MH0007630031101118C00	1118	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3054MH0007630031101119C00	1119	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3054MH0007630031101120C00	1120	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3054MH0007630031101121C00	1121	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3054MH0007630031101122C00	1122	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3054MH0007630031101123C00	1123	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3054MH0007630031101124C00	1124	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 15_March_2021

Sol 3054 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Nontron- after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~1 cm standoff									
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3054MH0007850011101126C00					
best focus image:		3054MH0001530001101151R00		1151		motor count:		15102		range (cm):	2.8
range map product:		3054MH0001530001101152S00		1152		acquired sequence:		mhli00785	stack type:		Relative
acquired on date:		10-Mar-21				merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42		acquired on sol:		3054		focus merged on sol:		3054	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8		
				near	far						
3054MH0007850031101128C00	1128	14934	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	255	1		
3054MH0007850031101129C00	1129	14976	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	223	2		
3054MH0007850031101130C00	1130	15018	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	191	3		
3054MH0007850031101131C00	1131	15060	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	159	4		
3054MH0007850031101132C00	1132	15102	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	127	5		
3054MH0007850031101133C00	1133	15144	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	85	6		
3054MH0007850031101134C00	1134	15186	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7		
3054MH0007850031101135C00	1135	15228	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8		

updated: 15_March_2021

Sol 3054 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Nontron- after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3054MH0007630011101137C00					
best focus image:		3054MH0001530001101149R00		1149		motor count:		13991		range (cm):	6.9
range map product:		3054MH0001530001101150S00		1150		acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative
acquired on date:		10-Mar-21				merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24		acquired on sol:		3054		focus merged on sol:		3054	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8		
				near	far						
3054MH0007630031101139C00	1139	13895	7.59	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1		
3054MH0007630031101140C00	1140	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2		
3054MH0007630031101141C00	1141	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3		
3054MH0007630031101142C00	1142	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4		
3054MH0007630031101143C00	1143	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5		
3054MH0007630031101144C00	1144	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6		
3054MH0007630031101145C00	1145	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7		
3054MH0007630031101146C00	1146	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8		

6 Image comment, purpose, RATIONALE_DESC

A RATIONALE_DESC accompanies each MAHLI image and each focus merge product archived with the NASA PDS. It is found in in each archived image label file (.LBL).

The RATIONALE_DESC is a text description of the purpose (rationale) behind the acquisition of each MAHLI parent image.

For onboard focus merge products, the RATIONALE_DESC includes information regarding when the merge was performed and which parent images were merged. This information is not automatically tracked by the instrument or ground data system and thus requires human intervention; this is the only pathway by which this information is conveyed to the data user through the NASA PDS archival products.

The MAHLI PI and his assistants draft each RATIONALE_DESC as the data are acquired and returned to Earth. Final editing of each RATIONALE_DESC is performed a few months before the data are archived with the NASA PDS. In some cases, an error might be detected in a RATIONALE_DESC some time after the data are first archived; in such a case, the corrections are made in a later release of MAHLI data to the PDS (as long as the mission continues and funding is available to do so).

The pages that follow capture the RATIONALE_DESC for each MAHLI image acquired and lists the ID for the best available image or focus merge product returned to Earth. Note that the RATIONALE_DESC also applies to any other child images spawned by a given parent image and thus there might be additional images, not listed here, that correspond to a given RATIONALE_DESC. In some cases, it was only necessary to return a thumbnail image; the IDs for these are given in orange text. As noted earlier, purple text indicates Image IDs for which the last two characters might differ from those in the NASA PDS archives.

Note that the text on the pages that follow is tiny. We highly recommend that the reader view this document electronically (*i.e.*, PDF file on a computer screen) and magnify the view $\geq 400\%$.

The *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* that follow include data acquired Sol 2935–3068. During this period, the instrument obtained images and/or performed focus merges on **Sols 2935, 2938, 2940, 2942, 2943, 2945, 2949, 2951, 2955, 2959, 2965, 2967, 2969, 2970, 2972, 2974, 2977, 2989, 2990, 2991, 2992, 2993, 2994, 2995, 2998, 2999, 3004, 3005, 3007, 3008, 3010, 3011, 3013, 3015, 3017, 3018, 3020, 3022, 3024, 3025, 3026, 3027, 3028, 3031, 3034, 3035, 3036, 3037, 3040, 3042, 3044, 3047, 3049, 3051, 3052, 3054, 3056, 3068.**

last update: 16_November_2020

Sol 2935 - MAHLI Images

Total parent images	63	acquired/performed date(s)
focus merge performance	5	8-Nov-20
Total focus merge products	19	camera positions:
total parent images + focus merge products	73	8

Summary of MAHLI activities
The REMS UV sensor was imaged to inspect dust accumulation. Then, MAHLI imaged the APXS targets Hunt_Hill and Muckie_Min after Hunt_Hill was brushed by the DRT. Later, the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Position	Image ID	MCA_CAMERA PRODUCT ID (MAHLI CODE)	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
nh00095	REMS UV sensor -15 cm working distance	2935MH00095000100397C00	3927	Autofocus sub-frame for REMS UV Sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		2935MH00095000100398C00	3928	REMS UV Sensor - characterize dust accumulation
nh00706	Hunt_Hill After DRT APXS target -25 cm standoff	2935MH0007060001003929C00	3929	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 25 cm
		2935MH0007060001003930C00	3930	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 25 cm
nh00763	Hunt_Hill After DRT APXS target Stereo-1 -5 cm standoff	2935MH0007630001003931C00	3931	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2935MH0007630001003932C00	3932	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2935MH0007630001003933C00	3933	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2935MH0007630001003934C00	3934	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2935MH0007630001003935C00	3935	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003936C00	3936	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003937C00	3937	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003938C00	3938	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003939C00	3939	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003940C00	3940	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003941C00	3941	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003942C00	3942	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00763	Hunt_Hill After DRT APXS target Stereo-2 -5 cm standoff	2935MH0007630001003943C00	3943	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2935MH0007630001003944C00	3944	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2935MH0007630001003945C00	3945	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2935MH0007630001003946C00	3946	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003947C00	3947	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003948C00	3948	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003949C00	3949	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003950C00	3950	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003951C00	3951	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003952C00	3952	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007630001003953C00	3953	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		nh00732	Hunt_Hill After DRT APXS target -2 cm standoff	2935MH0007320001003954C00
2935MH0007320001003955C00	3955			Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm
2935MH0007320001003956C00	3956			Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
2935MH0007320001003957C00	3957			Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
2935MH0007320001003958C00	3958			Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
2935MH0007320001003959C00	3959			Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
2935MH0007320001003960C00	3960			Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
2935MH0007320001003961C00	3961			Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
2935MH0007320001003962C00	3962			Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
2935MH0007320001003963C00	3963			Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
2935MH0007320001003964C00	3964			Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_HP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00706	Muckie_Min APXS target -25 cm standoff			2935MH0007060001003965C00
		2935MH0007060001003966C00	3966	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - standoff near 25 cm
nh00721	Muckie_Min APXS target 1 -5 cm standoff	2935MH0007210001003967C00	3967	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2935MH0007210001003968C00	3968	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2935MH0007210001003969C00	3969	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2935MH0007210001003970C00	3970	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2935MH0007210001003971C00	3971	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003972C00	3972	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003973C00	3973	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003974C00	3974	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003975C00	3975	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003976C00	3976	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003977C00	3977	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003978C00	3978	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00721	Muckie_Min APXS target 2 -5 cm standoff	2935MH0007210001003979C00	3979	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2935MH0007210001003980C00	3980	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2935MH0007210001003981C00	3981	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2935MH0007210001003982C00	3982	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003983C00	3983	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003984C00	3984	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003985C00	3985	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003986C00	3986	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003987C00	3987	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003988C00	3988	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2935MH0007210001003989C00	3989	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_HP - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

nh00027	Focus Merges	2935MH0002270001003990P00	3990	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_BP - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2935 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3982-3989 - best focus image product
		2935MH0002270001003991S00	3991	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_BP - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2935 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3982-3989 - range map product
		2935MH0002270001003992P00	3992	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_BP - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2935 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3971-3978 - best focus image product
		2935MH0002270001003993S00	3993	Rock target Muckie_Min - also called Muckie_Min_BP - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2935 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3971-3978 - range map product
		2935MH0002270001003994P00	3994	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_BP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2935 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3957-3964 - best focus image product
		2935MH0002270001003995S00	3995	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_BP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2935 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3957-3964 - range map product
		2935MH0002270001003996P00	3996	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_BP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2935 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3946-3953 - best focus image product
		2935MH0002270001003997S00	3997	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_BP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2935 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3946-3953 - range map product
		2935MH0002270001003998P00	3998	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_BP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2935 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3935-3942 - best focus image product
		2935MH0002270001003999S00	3999	Rock target Hunt_Hill - also called Hunt_Hill_BP - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2935 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3935-3942 - range map product

last update: 16_November_2020

Sol 2940 - MAHLI Images

Total parent Images:	23	acquired/performed date(s)
Focus merge performance:	2	12-Nov-2013-Nov-20
Total focus merge products:	4	camera positions
Total parent images + focus merge products:	27	3

Summary of MAHLI observations

MAHLI imaged the APXS target West_Loch after APXS acquired observations of and retracted from the target. Later, the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Position	Image ID <small>link to best, best merged version of the image next set of data in open URL image - only 1-2 characters in MAHLI_PDS archive. Image ID may differ</small>	MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CODE)	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
nh00706	West_Loch after APXS retraction -25 cm standoff	2940MH0007060001004027C00	4027	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - standoff near 25 cm
		2940MH00070600011004028C00	4028	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - standoff near 25 cm
		2940MH0007060001004029C00	4029	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
nh00299	West_Loch after APXS retraction Stereo-1 -5 cm standoff	2940MH0002990001004030C00	4030	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2940MH00029900011004031C00	4031	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2940MH00029900011004032C00	4032	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2940MH00029900011004033C00	4033	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2940MH00029900011004034C00	4034	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2940MH00029900011004035C00	4035	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2940MH00029900011004036C00	4036	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2940MH00029900011004037C00	4037	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2940MH00029900011004038C00	4038	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2940MH00029900011004039C00	4039	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		nh00299	West_Loch after APXS retraction Stereo-2 -5 cm standoff	2940MH00029900011004040C00
2940MH00029900011004041C00	4041			Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
2940MH00029900011004042C00	4042			Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
2940MH00029900011004043C00	4043			Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
2940MH00029900011004044C00	4044			Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
2940MH00029900011004045C00	4045			Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
2940MH00029900011004046C00	4046			Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
2940MH00029900011004047C00	4047			Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
2940MH00029900011004048C00	4048			Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
2940MH00029900011004049C00	4049			Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00285	Focus Merges			2940MH0002850001004050P00
		2940MH0002850001004051S00	4051	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2940 with MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4042-4049 - range map product
		2940MH0002850001004052P00	4052	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2940 with MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4032-4039 - best focus image product
		2940MH0002850001004053S00	4053	Rock target West_Loch - also called West_Loch_rp - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2940 with MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4032-4039 - range map product

last update: 18_November_2020

Sol 2942 – MAHLI Images

Total parent images	72	acquired/performed date(s)
focus merge performance	0	18-Nov-20
Total focus merge products	0	camera positions:
		#
Total parent images + focus merge products	72	

MAHLI targeted APXS targets St_Ninian and Geesa_Water.

Sequence	Position	Image ID	MSL_CAMERA PRODUCT ID (MAHLI CODE)	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
nhl00706	St_Ninian APXS target ~25 cm standoff	2942MH007060001004054C00	4054	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 25 cm
		2942MH007060011004055C00	4055	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 25 cm
		2942MH007060021004056C00	4056	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
nhl00709	St_Ninian APXS target Stereo 1 ~5 cm standoff	2942MH007090001004057C00	4057	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2942MH007090011004058C00	4058	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2942MH007090021004059C00	4059	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2942MH007090031004060C00	4060	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004061C00	4061	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004062C00	4062	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004063C00	4063	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004064C00	4064	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004065C00	4065	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004066C00	4066	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004067C00	4067	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nhl00709	St_Ninian APXS target Stereo 2 ~5 cm standoff	2942MH007090041004068C00	4068	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2942MH007090011004069C00	4069	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2942MH007090021004070C00	4070	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004071C00	4071	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004072C00	4072	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004073C00	4073	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004074C00	4074	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004075C00	4075	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004076C00	4076	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007090031004077C00	4077	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nhl00705	St_Ninian APXS target ~2 cm standoff	2942MH007950001004079C00	4079	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm
		2942MH007950011004080C00	4080	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm
		2942MH007950021004081C00	4081	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2942MH007950031004082C00	4082	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007950031004083C00	4083	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007950031004084C00	4084	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007950031004085C00	4085	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007950031004086C00	4086	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007950031004087C00	4087	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007950031004088C00	4088	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH007950031004089C00	4089	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nhl00706	Geesa_Water APXS target ~25 cm standoff	2942MH007060001004090C00	4090	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 25 cm
		2942MH007060011004091C00	4091	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 25 cm
		2942MH007060021004092C00	4092	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
nhl00803	Geesa_Water APXS target Stereo 1 ~5 cm standoff	2942MH008030011004093C00	4093	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2942MH008030011004094C00	4094	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2942MH008030011004095C00	4095	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004096C00	4096	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004097C00	4097	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004098C00	4098	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004099C00	4099	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004100C00	4100	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004101C00	4101	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004102C00	4102	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004103C00	4103	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - image 9 in 8-image relative focus stack
nhl00803	Geesa_Water APXS target Stereo 2 ~5 cm standoff	2942MH008030041004104C00	4104	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2942MH008030011004105C00	4105	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2942MH008030021004106C00	4106	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030021004107C00	4107	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004108C00	4108	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004109C00	4109	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004110C00	4110	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004111C00	4111	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004112C00	4112	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004113C00	4113	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH008030031004114C00	4114	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - image 9 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mri00795	Geesa_Water APXS target -2 cm standoff	2942MH0007950001004119C00	4115	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm
		2942MH0007950011004116C00	4116	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm
		2942MH0007950021004117C00	4117	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2942MH0007950031004118C00	4118	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH0007950031004119C00	4119	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH0007950031004120C00	4120	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH0007950031004121C00	4121	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH0007950031004122C00	4122	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH0007950031004123C00	4123	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH0007950031004124C00	4124	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2942MH0007950031004125C00	4125	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

last update: 16_November_2020

Sol 2943 – MAHLI images	Total parent images:	0	acquired/performed date(s)
	focus merges performed:	0	16-Nov-20
	Total focus merge products:	12	camera positions:
	Total parent images + focus merge products:	12	0

Summary of MAHLI activities
Focus stack images from Sol 2942 were merged

Sequence	Position	Image ID	MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CODE)	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m100163	Focus Merges	2943MH0001630001004126R00	4126	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2942 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4118-4125 - best focus image product
		2943MH0001630001004127S00	4127	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2942 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4118-4125 - range map product
		2943MH0001630001004128R00	4128	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2942 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4107-4114 - best focus image product
		2943MH0001630001004129S00	4129	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2942 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4107-4114 - range map product
		2943MH0001630001004130R00	4130	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2942 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4096-4103 - best focus image product
		2943MH0001630001004131S00	4131	Rock target Geesa_Water - also called Geesa_Water_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2942 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4096-4103 - range map product
		2943MH0001630001004132R00	4132	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2942 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4082-4089 - best focus image product
		2943MH0001630001004133S00	4133	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2942 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4082-4089 - range map product
		2943MH0001630001004134R00	4134	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2942 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4071-4078 - best focus image product
		2943MH0001630001004135S00	4135	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2942 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4071-4078 - range map product
		2943MH0001630001004136R00	4136	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2942 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4060-4067 - best focus image product
		2943MH0001630001004137S00	4137	Rock target St_Ninian - also called St_Ninian_rp - APXS target - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2942 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4060-4067 - range map product

nh00426	Ingliston APXS and ChemCam target -1 cm standoff	2945MH0004260001004200C00	4200	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - standoff near 1 cm
		2945MH00042600011004201C00	4201	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - standoff near 1 cm
		2945MH00042600021004202C00	4202	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2945MH00042600021004203C00	4203	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2945MH00042600021004204C00	4204	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2945MH00042600021004205C00	4205	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2945MH00042600021004206C00	4206	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2945MH00042600021004207C00	4207	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2945MH00042600021004208C00	4208	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2945MH00042600021004209C00	4209	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00163	Focus Merges	2945MH00016300001004210R00	4210	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2945 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4202-4209 - best focus image product
		2945MH00016300001004211S00	4211	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2945 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4202-4209 - range map product
		2945MH00016300001004212R00	4212	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2945 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4192-4199 - best focus image product
		2945MH00016300001004213S00	4213	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2945 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4192-4199 - range map product
		2945MH00016300001004214R00	4214	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2945 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4182-4189 - best focus image product
		2945MH00016300001004215S00	4215	Rock target Ingliston - also called Ingliston_tkw_rp - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Ingliston_ccam - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2945 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4182-4189 - range map product
		2945MH00016300001004216R00	4216	Rock target Lasswade - also called Lasswade_rp - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Lasswade_ccam - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2945 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4170-4177 - best focus image product
		2945MH00016300001004217S00	4217	Rock target Lasswade - also called Lasswade_rp - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Lasswade_ccam - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2945 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4159-4166 - best focus image product
		2945MH00016300001004218R00	4218	Rock target Lasswade - also called Lasswade_rp - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Lasswade_ccam - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2945 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4159-4166 - best focus image product
		2945MH00016300001004219S00	4219	Rock target Lasswade - also called Lasswade_rp - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Lasswade_ccam - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2945 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4159-4166 - range map product
		2945MH00016300001004220R00	4220	Rock target Lasswade - also called Lasswade_rp - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Lasswade_ccam - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2945 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4148-4155 - best focus image product
		2945MH00016300001004221S00	4221	Rock target Lasswade - also called Lasswade_rp - After Dust Removal Tool (DRT) - APXS target - Sol 2945 ChemCam target Lasswade_ccam - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2945 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4148-4155 - range map product

last update: 10_December_2020

Sol 2951 - MAHLI Images

Total parent images	33	acquired/performed date(s)
Focus merges performed	3	24-Nov-20
Total focus merge products	8	camera positions:
		4

Summary of MAHLI activities

MAHLI imaged the target Saughieside_Hill after APXS acquired observations of and retracted from the target. Later, the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Position	Image ID	MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CODE)	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL. DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
nr100706	Saughieside_Hill after APXS retraction ~25 cm standoff	2951MH0007060001004291C00	4281	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 25 cm
		2951MH00070600011004282C00	4282	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 25 cm
		2951MH00070600021004283C00	4283	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
nr100182	Saughieside_Hill after APXS retraction Stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	2951MH0001820001004284C00	4284	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2951MH0001820001004285C00	4285	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2951MH00018200021004286C00	4286	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00018200021004287C00	4287	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00018200021004288C00	4288	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00018200021004289C00	4289	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00018200021004290C00	4290	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00018200021004291C00	4291	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00018200021004292C00	4292	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
2951MH00018200021004293C00	4293	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
nr100182	Saughieside_Hill after APXS retraction Stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	2951MH0001820001004294C00	4294	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2951MH00018200011004295C00	4295	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2951MH00018200021004296C00	4296	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00018200021004297C00	4297	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00018200021004298C00	4298	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00018200021004299C00	4299	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00018200021004300C00	4300	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00018200021004301C00	4301	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00018200021004302C00	4302	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
2951MH00018200021004303C00	4303	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
nr100202	Saughieside_Hill after APXS retraction ~2 cm standoff	2951MH0003020001004304C00	4304	Autofocus sub-frame for Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 2 cm
		2951MH00030200011004305C00	4305	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 2 cm
		2951MH00030200021004306C00	4306	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00030200021004307C00	4307	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00030200021004308C00	4308	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00030200021004309C00	4309	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00030200021004310C00	4310	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00030200021004311C00	4311	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2951MH00030200021004312C00	4312	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
2951MH00030200021004313C00	4313	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
nr100193	Focus Merges	2951MH0001930001004314R00	4314	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2951 with MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4306-4313 - best focus image product
		2951MH0001930001004315S00	4315	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2951 with MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4306-4313 - range map product
		2951MH0001930001004316R00	4316	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2951 with MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4296-4303 - best focus image product
		2951MH0001930001004317S00	4317	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2951 with MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4296-4303 - range map product
		2951MH0001930001004318R00	4318	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2951 with MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4286-4293 - best focus image product
		2951MH0001930001004319S00	4319	Rock target Saughieside_Hill - also called Saughieside_Hill_Rp_tweak - after APXS retraction - Stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired Sol 2951 with MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4286-4293 - range map product

last update: 28_December_2020

Total parent images	25	acquired/performed date(s)
Focus merge performed	2	2-Dec-20
Total focus merge products	4	camera positions:
		3
Total parent images + focus merge products		
	25	3

MAHLI imaged the APXS target Edinburrie after APXS acquired observations of and retracted from the target. Later, the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Position	Image ID	MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CODE)	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
nh00706	Edinburrie after APXS retraction ~25 cm standoff	2959MH007060001004385C00	4385	autofocus sub-frame for rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - standoff near 25 cm
		2959MH0070600011004386C00	4386	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - standoff near 25 cm
		2959MH007060001004387C00	4387	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
nh00763	Edinburrie after APXS retraction stance1 ~5 cm standoff	2959MH007630001004388C00	4388	autofocus sub-frame for rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2959MH007630001004389C00	4389	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2959MH007630001004390C00	4390	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2959MH007630001004391C00	4391	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2959MH007630001004392C00	4392	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2959MH007630001004393C00	4393	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2959MH007630001004394C00	4394	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2959MH007630001004395C00	4395	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2959MH007630001004396C00	4396	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2959MH007630001004397C00	4397	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00763	Edinburrie after APXS retraction stance2 ~5 cm standoff	2959MH007630001004398C00	4398	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2959MH007630001004399C00	4399	autofocus sub-frame for rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2959MH007630001004400C00	4400	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2959MH007630001004401C00	4401	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2959MH007630001004402C00	4402	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2959MH007630001004403C00	4403	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2959MH007630001004404C00	4404	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2959MH007630001004405C00	4405	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2959MH007630001004406C00	4406	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2959MH007630001004407C00	4407	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00265	Focus Merges	2959MH002650001004410P00	4410	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2959 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4402-4409 - best focus image product
		2959MH002650001004411S00	4411	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2959 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4402-4409 - range map product
		2959MH002650001004412P00	4412	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2959 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4391-4398 - best focus image product
		2959MH002650001004413S00	4413	rock target Edinburrie - also called Edinburrie_rp - after APXS retraction - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2959 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4391-4398 - range map product

last update: 29_December_2020

Sol 2965 – MAHLI Images

Total parent images:	23	acquired/performed date(s)
Focus merge performance:	2	8-Dec-20
Total focus merge products:	4	camera positions:
Total parent images + focus merge products:	27	3

Summary of MAHLI activities

MAHLI merged the target Achnasheen and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Position	Image ID	NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CODE)	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
nh00706	Achnasheen -32 cm standoff	2965MH000706001004414C00	4414	autofocus sub-frame for target Achnasheen - standoff near 25 cm
		2965MH000706001004415C00	4415	target Achnasheen - standoff near 25 cm
		2965MH0007060021004416C00	4416	target Achnasheen - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
nh00162	Achnasheen stereo-1 -5 cm standoff	2965MH001820021004417C00	4417	autofocus sub-frame for target Achnasheen - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2965MH001820011004418C00	4418	target Achnasheen - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2965MH001820021004419C00	4419	target Achnasheen - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2965MH001820021004420C00	4420	target Achnasheen - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2965MH001820021004421C00	4421	target Achnasheen - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2965MH001820021004422C00	4422	target Achnasheen - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2965MH001820021004423C00	4423	target Achnasheen - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2965MH001820021004424C00	4424	target Achnasheen - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2965MH001820021004425C00	4425	target Achnasheen - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2965MH001820021004426C00	4426	target Achnasheen - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00182	Achnasheen stereo-2 -5 cm standoff	2965MH001820011004427C00	4427	autofocus sub-frame for target Achnasheen - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2965MH001820011004428C00	4428	target Achnasheen - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2965MH001820021004429C00	4429	target Achnasheen - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2965MH001820021004430C00	4430	target Achnasheen - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2965MH001820021004431C00	4431	target Achnasheen - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2965MH001820021004432C00	4432	target Achnasheen - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2965MH001820021004433C00	4433	target Achnasheen - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2965MH001820021004434C00	4434	target Achnasheen - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2965MH001820021004435C00	4435	target Achnasheen - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
2965MH001820021004436C00	4436	target Achnasheen - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
nh00265	Focus Merges	2965MH0002650001004437F00	4437	target Achnasheen - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2965 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4429-4436 - best focus image product
		2965MH0002650001004438S00	4438	target Achnasheen - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2965 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4429-4436 - range map product
		2965MH0002650001004439F00	4439	target Achnasheen - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2965 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4419-4426 - best focus image product
		2965MH0002650001004440S00	4440	target Achnasheen - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2965 with NSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4419-4426 - range map product

last update: 29_December_2020

Total parent Images	25	acquired/performed date(s)
Focus merges performed	2	16-Dec-20
Total focus merge products	4	camera positions
Total parent images + focus merge products	29	3

Summary of MAHLI activities
 MAHLI imaged the target Dun_Eidemann and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Position	Image ID	MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CODE)	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
<small>link to best, best combined version of the image set is at end of data in open table Image ID is the product ID for the PDS archive Image ID may differ</small>				
nh00706	Dun_Eidemann -25 cm standoff	2967MH0070600100441C00	4441	autofocus sub-frame for target Dun_Eidemann - standoff near 25 cm
		2967MH0070600100442C00	4442	target Dun_Eidemann - standoff near 25 cm
		2967MH0070600100443C00	4443	target Dun_Eidemann - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
nh00723	Dun_Eidemann stereo-1 -5 cm standoff	2967MH0072300100444C00	4444	autofocus sub-frame for target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2967MH0072300100445C00	4445	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2967MH00723002100446C00	4446	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2967MH00723003100447C00	4447	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100448C00	4448	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100449C00	4449	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100450C00	4450	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100451C00	4451	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100452C00	4452	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100453C00	4453	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100454C00	4454	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00723	Dun_Eidemann stereo-2 -5 cm standoff	2967MH0072300100445C00	4455	autofocus sub-frame for target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2967MH0072300100446C00	4456	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2967MH00723002100447C00	4457	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2967MH00723003100448C00	4458	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100449C00	4459	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100450C00	4460	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100451C00	4461	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100452C00	4462	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100453C00	4463	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100454C00	4464	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2967MH00723003100455C00	4465	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00265	Focus Merges	2967MH00265000100446R00	4466	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired soi 2967 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4458-4465 - best focus image product
		2967MH00265000100447S00	4467	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired soi 2967 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4458-4465 - range map product
		2967MH00265000100448R00	4468	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired soi 2967 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4447-4454 - best focus image product
		2967MH00265000100449S00	4469	target Dun_Eidemann - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired soi 2967 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4447-4454 - range map product

last update: 29_December_2020

Sol 2969 - MAHLI Images

Total parent Images	61	acquired/performed date(s)
focus merge performed	0	12-Dec-20
Total focus merge products	0	camera positions:
		7
Summary of MAHLI 20/20/20		

Sequence	Position	Image ID	MHL_CAMERA PRODUCT ID (MAHLI CODE)	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
MAHLI imaged the targets Cougar_Angus and Auchnafree_Hill				
<small>link to best, best combined version of the image next to set of data on page left image name: 12-2020-01-04-47-7C00 product name: 12-2020-01-04-47-7C00 archive image ID may differ</small>				
nh00706	Cougar_Angus -25 cm standoff	2969MH00706001004479C00	4470	autofocus sub-frame for target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 25 cm
		2969MH00706001004471C00	4471	target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 25 cm
		2969MH007060021004472C00	4472	target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
nh00699	Cougar_Angus stereo-1 -5 cm standoff	2969MH00699001004473C00	4473	autofocus sub-frame for target Cougar_Angus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2969MH00699001004474C00	4474	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2969MH006990021004475C00	4475	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2969MH006990031004476C00	4476	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004477C00	4477	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004478C00	4478	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004479C00	4479	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004480C00	4480	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004481C00	4481	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004482C00	4482	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004483C00	4483	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00699	Cougar_Angus stereo-2 -5 cm standoff	2969MH00699001004484C00	4484	autofocus sub-frame for target Cougar_Angus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2969MH00699001004485C00	4485	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2969MH006990021004486C00	4486	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2969MH006990031004487C00	4487	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004488C00	4488	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004489C00	4489	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004490C00	4490	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004491C00	4491	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004492C00	4492	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004493C00	4493	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004494C00	4494	target Cougar_Angus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00813	Cougar_Angus -2 cm standoff	2969MH008130001004495C00	4495	autofocus sub-frame for target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 2 cm
		2969MH008130011004496C00	4496	target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 2 cm
		2969MH008130021004497C00	4497	target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2969MH008130031004498C00	4498	target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH008130031004499C00	4499	target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH008130031004500C00	4500	target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH008130031004501C00	4501	target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH008130031004502C00	4502	target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH008130031004503C00	4503	target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH008130031004504C00	4504	target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH008130031004505C00	4505	target Cougar_Angus - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00706	Auchnafree_Hill -25 cm standoff	2969MH007060001004506C00	4506	autofocus sub-frame for target Auchnafree_Hill - standoff near 25 cm
		2969MH007060011004507C00	4507	target Auchnafree_Hill - standoff near 25 cm
		2969MH007060021004508C00	4508	target Auchnafree_Hill - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
nh00699	Auchnafree_Hill stereo-1 -5 cm standoff	2969MH00699001004509C00	4509	autofocus sub-frame for target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2969MH006990011004510C00	4510	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2969MH006990021004511C00	4511	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2969MH006990031004512C00	4512	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004513C00	4513	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004514C00	4514	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004515C00	4515	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004516C00	4516	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004517C00	4517	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004518C00	4518	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004519C00	4519	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00699	Auchnafree_Hill stereo-2 -5 cm standoff	2969MH00699001004520C00	4520	autofocus sub-frame for target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2969MH006990011004521C00	4521	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2969MH006990021004522C00	4522	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2969MH006990031004523C00	4523	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004524C00	4524	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004525C00	4525	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004526C00	4526	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004527C00	4527	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004528C00	4528	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004529C00	4529	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2969MH006990031004530C00	4530	target Auchnafree_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

last update: 14_December_2020

Sol 2970 - MAHLI images	Total parent Images	0	acquired/performed date(s)
	Focus merges performed	0	14-Dec-20
	Total focus merge products	10	camera positions:
	Total parent images + focus merge products	10	0

Summary of MAHLI activities
Focus stack images from Sol 2969 were merged

Sequence	Position	Image ID <small>link to best, best comparison version of the image next set of data in open table orange = only comparison in table purple = full - 0 dimension in table active Image ID may differ</small>	MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CODE)	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
nh00027	Focus Merges	2970MH0002270001004531R00	4531	target Auchnafree_Hill1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2969 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4523-4530 - best focus image product
		2970MH0002270001004532S00	4532	target Auchnafree_Hill1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2969 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4523-4530 - range map product
		2970MH0002270001004533R00	4533	target Auchnafree_Hill1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2969 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4512-4519 - best focus image product
		2970MH0002270001004534S00	4534	target Auchnafree_Hill1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2969 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4512-4519 - range map product
		2970MH0002270001004535R00	4535	target Coupar_Angus - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2969 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4498-4505 - best focus image product
		2970MH0002270001004536S00	4536	target Coupar_Angus - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2969 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4498-4505 - range map product
		2970MH0002270001004537R00	4537	target Coupar_Angus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2969 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4487-4494 - best focus image product
		2970MH0002270001004538S00	4538	target Coupar_Angus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2969 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4487-4494 - range map product
		2970MH0002270001004539R00	4539	target Coupar_Angus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2969 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4476-4483 - best focus image product
		2970MH0002270001004540S00	4540	target Coupar_Angus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2969 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4476-4483 - range map product

last update: 29_December_2020

Total parent images:	23	acquired/performed date(s)
Focus merges performed:	2	16-Dec-20
Total focus merge products:	4	camera positions:
Total parent images + focus merge products:	27	3

Summary of MAHLI activities
MAHLI merged the target Torrness and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Position	Image ID <small>link to best, best combined version of the image next to it of date in open URL image ID: 2972MH0007060011004542C00 parent ID: 2972MH0007060011004542C00 active Image ID may differ</small>	MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (MAHLI CODE)	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
nh00706	Torrness -25 cm standoff	2972MH0007060011004541C00	4541	autofocus sub-frame for target Torrness - standoff near 25 cm
		2972MH0007060011004542C00	4542	target Torrness - standoff near 25 cm
		2972MH0007060011004543C00	4543	target Torrness - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
nh00299	Torrness stereo-1 -5 cm standoff	2972MH0002990001004544C00	4544	autofocus sub-frame for target Torrness - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2972MH0002990011004545C00	4545	target Torrness - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2972MH0002990021004546C00	4546	target Torrness - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990031004547C00	4547	target Torrness - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990041004548C00	4548	target Torrness - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990051004549C00	4549	target Torrness - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990061004550C00	4550	target Torrness - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990071004551C00	4551	target Torrness - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990081004552C00	4552	target Torrness - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990091004553C00	4553	target Torrness - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00299	Torrness stereo-2 -5 cm standoff	2972MH0002990001004554C00	4554	autofocus sub-frame for target Torrness - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2972MH0002990011004555C00	4555	target Torrness - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2972MH0002990021004556C00	4556	target Torrness - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990031004557C00	4557	target Torrness - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990041004558C00	4558	target Torrness - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990051004559C00	4559	target Torrness - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990061004560C00	4560	target Torrness - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990071004561C00	4561	target Torrness - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990081004562C00	4562	target Torrness - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2972MH0002990091004563C00	4563	target Torrness - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00265	Focus Merges	2972MH0002650001004564P00	4564	target Torrness - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2972 with MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4556-4563 - best focus image product
		2972MH0002650001004565S00	4565	target Torrness - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2972 with MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4556-4563 - range map product
		2972MH0002650001004566P00	4566	target Torrness - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2972 with MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4546-4553 - best focus image product
		2972MH0002650001004567S00	4567	target Torrness - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2972 with MHL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4546-4553 - range map product

last update: 30_December_2020

Sol 2974 - MAHLI Images

Total parent images	95	acquired/performed date(s)
focus merge performance	8	18-Dec-20
Total focus merge products	18	camera positions
Total parent images + focus merge products	111	13

Summary of MAHLI activities

MAHLI imaged the targets An_Dun, Cod_Baa (before and after DRT), and Cam_Mor; later, the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Position	Image ID	MSL_CAMERA PRODUCT ID (MAHLI CODE)	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
nh00190	An_Dun ~25 cm standoff	2974MH001900001004569C00	4569	autofocus sub-frame for target An_Dun - standoff near 25 cm
		2974MH001900011004569C00	4569	target An_Dun - standoff near 25 cm
nh00224	An_Dun stereo 1 ~5 cm standoff	2974MH002240001004579C00	4570	autofocus sub-frame for target An_Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2974MH002240011004571C00	4571	target An_Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2974MH002240021004572C00	4572	target An_Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240031004573C00	4573	target An_Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240041004574C00	4574	target An_Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240051004575C00	4575	target An_Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240061004576C00	4576	target An_Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240071004577C00	4577	target An_Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240081004578C00	4578	target An_Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240091004579C00	4579	target An_Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00224	An_Dun stereo 2 ~5 cm standoff	2974MH002240001004580C00	4580	autofocus sub-frame for target An_Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2974MH002240011004581C00	4581	target An_Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2974MH002240021004582C00	4582	target An_Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240031004583C00	4583	target An_Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240041004584C00	4584	target An_Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240051004585C00	4585	target An_Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240061004586C00	4586	target An_Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240071004587C00	4587	target An_Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240081004588C00	4588	target An_Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH002240091004589C00	4589	target An_Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00190	Cod_Baa before DRT ~25 cm standoff	2974MH001900001004590C00	4590	autofocus sub-frame for target Cod_Baa - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		2974MH001900011004591C00	4591	target Cod_Baa - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
nh00122	Cod_Baa before DRT ~5 cm standoff	2974MH001220001004592C00	4592	autofocus sub-frame for target Cod_Baa - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
		2974MH001220011004593C00	4593	target Cod_Baa - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
nh00276	Cod_Baa after DRT ~25 cm standoff	2974MH002760001004594C00	4594	autofocus sub-frame for target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		2974MH002760011004595C00	4595	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		2974MH002760021004596C00	4596	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2974MH002760031004597C00	4597	autofocus sub-frame for target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
nh00699	Cod_Baa after DRT stereo 1 ~5 cm standoff	2974MH006990001004598C00	4598	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2974MH006990011004599C00	4599	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2974MH006990021004600C00	4600	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH006990031004601C00	4601	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH006990041004602C00	4602	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH006990051004603C00	4603	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH006990061004604C00	4604	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH006990071004605C00	4605	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH006990081004606C00	4606	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH006990091004607C00	4607	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00699	Cod_Baa after DRT stereo 2 ~5 cm standoff	2974MH006990001004608C00	4608	autofocus sub-frame for target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2974MH006990011004609C00	4609	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2974MH006990021004610C00	4610	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2974MH006990031004611C00	4611	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH006990041004612C00	4612	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH006990051004613C00	4613	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH006990061004614C00	4614	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH006990071004615C00	4615	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH006990081004616C00	4616	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH006990091004617C00	4617	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
nh00744	Cod_Baa after DRT ~1 cm standoff	2974MH007440001004619C00	4619	autofocus sub-frame for target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		2974MH007440011004620C00	4620	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		2974MH007440021004621C00	4621	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2974MH007440031004622C00	4622	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH007440041004623C00	4623	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH007440051004624C00	4624	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH007440061004625C00	4625	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH007440071004626C00	4626	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH007440081004627C00	4627	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH007440091004628C00	4628	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
2974MH007440101004629C00	4629	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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nm00706	Cam_Mor -25 cm standoff	2974MH007060001004630C00	4630	autofocus sub-frame for target Carr_Mor - standoff near 25 cm
		2974MH007060011004631C00	4631	target Carr_Mor - standoff near 25 cm
		2974MH007060021004632C00	4632	target Carr_Mor - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
nm00182	Cam_Mor stereo-1 -5 cm standoff	2974MH001820001004633C00	4633	autofocus sub-frame for target Carr_Mor - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2974MH001820011004634C00	4634	target Carr_Mor - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2974MH001820021004635C00	4635	target Carr_Mor - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820031004636C00	4636	target Carr_Mor - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820041004637C00	4637	target Carr_Mor - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820051004638C00	4638	target Carr_Mor - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820061004639C00	4639	target Carr_Mor - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820071004640C00	4640	target Carr_Mor - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820081004641C00	4641	target Carr_Mor - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820091004642C00	4642	target Carr_Mor - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nm00182	Cam_Mor stereo-2 -5 cm standoff	2974MH001820001004643C00	4643	autofocus sub-frame for target Carr_Mor - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2974MH001820011004644C00	4644	target Carr_Mor - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2974MH001820021004645C00	4645	target Carr_Mor - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820031004646C00	4646	target Carr_Mor - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820041004647C00	4647	target Carr_Mor - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820051004648C00	4648	target Carr_Mor - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820061004649C00	4649	target Carr_Mor - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820071004650C00	4650	target Carr_Mor - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820081004651C00	4651	target Carr_Mor - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001820091004652C00	4652	target Carr_Mor - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nm00184	Cam_Mor -2 cm standoff	2974MH001840001004653C00	4653	autofocus sub-frame for target Carr_Mor - standoff near 2 cm
		2974MH001840011004654C00	4654	target Carr_Mor - standoff near 2 cm
		2974MH001840021004655C00	4655	target Carr_Mor - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001840031004656C00	4656	target Carr_Mor - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001840041004657C00	4657	target Carr_Mor - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001840051004658C00	4658	target Carr_Mor - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001840061004659C00	4659	target Carr_Mor - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001840071004660C00	4660	target Carr_Mor - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001840081004661C00	4661	target Carr_Mor - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2974MH001840091004662C00	4662	target Carr_Mor - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
nm00170	Focus Marges	2974MH001700001004663P00	4663	target Carr_Mor - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4655-4662 - best focus image product
		2974MH001700001004664S00	4664	target Carr_Mor - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4655-4662 - range map product
		2974MH001700001004665P00	4665	target Carr_Mor - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4645-4652 - best focus image product
		2974MH001700000904666S00	4666	target Carr_Mor - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4645-4652 - range map product
		2974MH001700000904667P00	4667	target Carr_Mor - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4635-4642 - best focus image product
		2974MH001700000904668S00	4668	target Carr_Mor - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4635-4642 - range map product
		2974MH001700000904669P00	4669	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4622-4629 - best focus image product
		2974MH001700000904670S00	4670	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4622-4629 - range map product
		2974MH001700000904671P00	4671	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4611-4618 - best focus image product
		2974MH001700000904672S00	4672	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4611-4618 - range map product
		2974MH001700000904673P00	4673	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4600-4607 - best focus image product
		2974MH001700000904674S00	4674	target Cod_Baa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4600-4607 - range map product
		2974MH001700000904675P00	4675	target An_Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4582-4589 - best focus image product
		2974MH001700000904676S00	4676	target An_Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4582-4589 - range map product
		2974MH001700000904677P00	4677	target An_Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4572-4579 - best focus image product
		2974MH001700000904678S00	4678	target An_Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2974 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4572-4579 - range map product

last update: 30_December_2020

Total parent images:	6	acquired/performed date(s)
focus merges performed:	0	26-Dec-20
Total focus merge products:	0	camera positions:
Total parent images + focus merge products:	6	3

Summary of MAHLI activities

MAHLI imaged the target An_Dun with the dust cover closed due to restrictions on cover actuation for the holiday plans.

Sequence	Position	Image ID <small>Mark a best, best comparison images of the image set as of date in grey text. Orange = flag - 0 dimension in MAHLI PDS purple = flag - 0 dimension in MAHLI PDS yellow = Image ID may differ</small>	MSL_CAMERA PRODUCT ID (MAHLI CODE)	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
nh000553	An_Dun APXS spot 1 dust cover closed -65 mm standoff	2977MH000553000904679C00 2977MH0005530010904680C00	4679 4680	autofocus sub-frame for target An_Dun - APXS spot 1 - dust cover closed - standoff near 65 mm target An_Dun - APXS spot 1 - dust cover closed - standoff near 65 mm
nh000553	An_Dun APXS spot 2 dust cover closed -65 mm standoff	2977MH000553000904681C00 2977MH0005530010904682C00	4681 4682	autofocus sub-frame for target An_Dun - APXS spot 2 - dust cover closed - standoff near 65 mm target An_Dun - APXS spot 2 - dust cover closed - standoff near 65 mm
nh000553	An_Dun APXS spot 3 dust cover closed -65 mm standoff	2977MH000553000904683C00 2977MH0005530010904684C00	4683 4684	autofocus sub-frame for target An_Dun - APXS spot 3 - dust cover closed - standoff near 65 mm target An_Dun - APXS spot 3 - dust cover closed - standoff near 65 mm

updated: 07_January_2021

Sol 2989 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	2-Jan-21
camera position:	6
total parent images:	48
focus merges performed:	0
total focus merge products:	0
total parent images + focus merge products:	48

Image ID:
 black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the targets Ronas_Hill and Braevick_Beach at the Sands of Forvie.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mhl00706	Ronas_Hill ~25 cm standoff	2989MH000706002090485C0D	4685	autofocus sub-frame for target Ronas_Hill - standoff near 25 cm
		2989MH0007060010904686C0D	4686	target Ronas_Hill - standoff near 25 cm
		2989MH000706002090467C0D	4687	target Ronas_Hill - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl00073	Ronas_Hill stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	2989MH0001730020904688C0D	4688	autofocus sub-frame for target Ronas_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2989MH0001730020904690C0D	4689	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		2989MH0001730020904690C0D	4690	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904691C0D	4691	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904692C0D	4692	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904693C0D	4693	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904694C0D	4694	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904695C0D	4695	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904696C0D	4696	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904697C0D	4697	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00073	Ronas_Hill stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	2989MH0001730020904698C0D	4698	autofocus sub-frame for target Ronas_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2989MH0001730020904699C0D	4699	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		2989MH0001730020904700C0D	4700	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904701C0D	4701	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904702C0D	4702	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904703C0D	4703	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904704C0D	4704	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904705C0D	4705	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904706C0D	4706	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0001730020904707C0D	4707	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00706	Braevick_Beach ~25 cm standoff	2989MH0007060000904708C0D	4708	autofocus sub-frame for target Braevick_Beach - standoff near 25 cm
		2989MH0007060020904709C0D	4709	target Braevick_Beach - standoff near 25 cm
		2989MH0007060020904710C0D	4710	target Braevick_Beach - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl00763	Braevick_Beach stereo-1 ~55 mm standoff	2989MH0007630020904711C0D	4711	autofocus sub-frame for target Braevick_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		2989MH0007630020904712C0D	4712	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		2989MH0007630020904713C0D	4713	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		2989MH0007630020904714C0D	4714	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0007630020904715C0D	4715	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0007630020904716C0D	4716	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0007630020904717C0D	4717	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0007630020904718C0D	4718	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0007630020904719C0D	4719	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0007630020904720C0D	4720	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00763	Braevick_Beach stereo-2 ~55 mm standoff	2989MH0007630020904721C0D	4721	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0007630020904722C0D	4722	autofocus sub-frame for target Braevick_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		2989MH0007630020904723C0D	4723	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		2989MH0007630020904724C0D	4724	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		2989MH0007630020904725C0D	4725	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0007630020904726C0D	4726	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0007630020904727C0D	4727	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0007630020904728C0D	4728	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0007630020904729C0D	4729	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2989MH0007630020904730C0D	4730	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
2989MH0007630020904731C0D	4731	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
2989MH0007630020904732C0D	4732	target Braevick_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 05_January_2021

Sol 2990 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	3-Jan-21
camera positions:	0
total parent images:	11
focus merges performed:	0
total focus merge products:	0
total parent images + focus merge products:	11

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: The target Braewick_Beach and the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets were imaged at the Sands of Forvie.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00122	Braewick_Beach ~55 mm standoff	2990MH00122000904733C00	4733	autofocus sub-frame for target Braewick_Beach - standoff near 55 mm
		2990MH001220010904734C00	4734	target Braewick_Beach - standoff near 55 mm
mN00371	MAHLI cal target - centered on bar target ~5 cm working distance	2990MH00371000904735C00	4735	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
		2990MH003710010804736C00	4736	MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
mN00372	MAHLI cal target - centered on cent target ~5 cm working distance	2990MH00372000904737C00	4737	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
		2990MH003720010704738C00	4738	MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
mN00374	MAHLI cal target = wheel + surface ~30 cm working distance from target	2990MH00374000704739C00	4739	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		2990MH003740010704740C00	4740	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		2990MH003740020704741C00	4741	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - manual focus at infinity
mN00373	APXS cal target ~5 cm standoff	2990MH00373000704742C00	4742	autofocus sub-frame for APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
		2990MH003730010704743C00	4743	APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm

updated: 05_January_2021

Sol 2991 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	4-Jan-21
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	4
total focus merge products:	8
total parent images + focus merge products:	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 2989 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1H00817	Focus Merges	2991MH000817000704744800	4744	target Braewick_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2989 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4725-4732 - best focus image product
		2991MH000817000704745500	4745	target Braewick_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2989 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4725-4732 - range map product
		2991MH000817000704746800	4746	target Braewick_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2989 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4714-4721 - best focus image product
		2991MH000817000704747500	4747	target Braewick_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2989 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4714-4721 - range map product
		2991MH000817000704748800	4748	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2989 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4700-4707 - best focus image product
		2991MH000817000704749500	4749	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2989 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4700-4707 - range map product
		2991MH000817000704750800	4750	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2989 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4690-4697 - best focus image product
		2991MH000817000704751500	4751	target Ronas_Hill - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2989 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4690-4697 - range map product

updated: 08_January_2021

Sol 2992 - MAHLI Images

		acquired(performed date(s))	5-Jan-21	
		camera positions	65	Image ID:
		total parent images	65	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	4	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	74	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the targets Airor and Ratharsair at the Sands of Forvie campaign site and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00157	Airor ~25 cm standoff	2992MH000197000704752C00	4752	autofocus sub-frame for target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 25 cm
		2992MH0001970010704753C00	4753	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 25 cm
mN00676	Airor ~4 cm standoff	2992MH000676000704754C00	4754	autofocus and first range-finding sub-frame - target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 4 cm
		2992MH0006760010704755C00	4755	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 4 cm
		2992MH0006760020704756C00	4756	second range-finding sub-frame - target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 4 cm
		2992MH0006760030704757C00	4757	third range-finding sub-frame - target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 4 cm
		2992MH0006760040704758C00	4758	fourth range-finding sub-frame - target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 4 cm
		2992MH0006760050704759C00	4759	fifth range-finding sub-frame - target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 4 cm
mN00157	Ratharsair ~25 cm standoff	2992MH000197000704760C00	4760	autofocus sub-frame for target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 25 cm
		2992MH0001970010704761C00	4761	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 25 cm
mN00676	Ratharsair ~45 cm standoff	2992MH000676000704762C00	4762	autofocus and first range-finding sub-frame - target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 45 cm
		2992MH0006760010604763C00	4763	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 45 mm
		2992MH0006760020604764C00	4764	second range-finding sub-frame - target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 45 mm
		2992MH0006760030604765C00	4765	third range-finding sub-frame - target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 45 mm
		2992MH0006760040604766C00	4766	fourth range-finding sub-frame - target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 45 mm
		2992MH0006760050604767C00	4767	fifth range-finding sub-frame - target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 45 mm
mN00706	Airor ~25 cm standoff	2992MH000706000604768C00	4768	autofocus sub-frame for target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 25 cm
		2992MH0007060010604769C00	4769	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 25 cm
mN00721	Airor stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	2992MH000721000604770C00	4770	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2992MH000721000604771C00	4771	autofocus sub-frame for target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		2992MH0007210010604772C00	4772	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		2992MH0007210020604773C00	4773	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2992MH0007210030604774C00	4774	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604775C00	4775	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604776C00	4776	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604777C00	4777	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604778C00	4778	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604779C00	4779	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604780C00	4780	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604781C00	4781	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604782C00	4782	autofocus sub-frame for target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		2992MH0007210010604783C00	4783	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
mN00721	Airor stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	2992MH0007210020604784C00	4784	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2992MH0007210030604785C00	4785	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604786C00	4786	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604787C00	4787	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604788C00	4788	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604789C00	4789	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604790C00	4790	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604791C00	4791	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604792C00	4792	target Airor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007210030604793C00	4793	autofocus sub-frame for target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 25 cm
mN00706	Ratharsair ~25 cm standoff	2992MH000706000604794C00	4794	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 25 cm
		2992MH0007060010604795C00	4795	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00723	Ratharsair stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	2992MH000723000604796C00	4796	autofocus sub-frame for target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		2992MH0007230010604797C00	4797	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		2992MH0007230020604798C00	4798	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2992MH0007230030604799C00	4799	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007230030604800C00	4800	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007230030604801C00	4801	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007230030604802C00	4802	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007230030604803C00	4803	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007230030604804C00	4804	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007230030604805C00	4805	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00723	Ratharsair stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	2992MH0007230030604806C00	4806	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007230030604807C00	4807	autofocus sub-frame for target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		2992MH0007230010604808C00	4808	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		2992MH0007230020604809C00	4809	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2992MH0007230030604810C00	4810	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007230030604811C00	4811	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007230030604812C00	4812	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2992MH0007230030604813C00	4813	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
2992MH0007230030604814C00	4814	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
2992MH0007230030604815C00	4815	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
2992MH0007230030604816C00	4816	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
2992MH0007230030604817C00	4817	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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mnh00707	Focus Merges	2992MH00070700006064818900	4818	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2992 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4810-4817 - best focus image product
		2992MH00070700006064819500	4819	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2992 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4810-4817 - range map product
		2992MH00070700006064820800	4820	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2992 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4799-4806 - best focus image product
		2992MH00070700006064821500	4821	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2992 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4799-4806 - range map product
		2992MH00070700006064822800	4822	target Airox - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2992 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4785-4792 - best focus image product
		2992MH00070700006064823500	4823	target Airox - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2992 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4785-4792 - range map product
		2992MH00070700006064824800	4824	target Airox - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2992 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4774-4781 - best focus image product
		2992MH00070700006064825500	4825	target Airox - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2992 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4774-4781 - range map product

updated: 13_January_2021

Sol 2993 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	6-Jan-21
camera position:	4
total parent images:	25
focus merges performed:	2
total focus merge products:	4
total parent images + focus merge products:	30

MAHLI imaged the targets Ratharsair and Air or as well as the REMS UV sensor at the Sands of Forvie campaign site and the focus stack images were merged. MAHLI images that correspond to COPDs 1 through 3926 (data from Sols 2992-2993) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	COPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00122	Ratharsair ~5 cm standoff	2993MH001120030604826C0D	4826	autofocus sub-frame for target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 5 cm
		2993MH001120010604827C0D	4827	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 5 cm
mN00746	Ratharsair ~17 mm standoff	2993MH007460030604828C0D	4828	autofocus sub-frame for target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm
		2993MH007460010604829C0D	4829	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm
		2993MH00746002030604830C0D	4830	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		2993MH007460030504831C0D	4831	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2993MH007460030504832C0D	4832	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2993MH007460030504833C0D	4833	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2993MH007460030504834C0D	4834	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2993MH007460030504835C0D	4835	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2993MH007460030504836C0D	4836	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2993MH007460030504837C0D	4837	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
2993MH007460030504838C0D	4838	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00794	Airor ~7 mm standoff	2993MH007940000504839C0D	4839	autofocus sub-frame for target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm
		2993MH007940010504840C0D	4840	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm
		2993MH007940020504841C0D	4841	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		2993MH007940030504842C0D	4842	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2993MH007940030504843C0D	4843	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2993MH007940030504844C0D	4844	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2993MH007940030504845C0D	4845	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2993MH007940030504846C0D	4846	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2993MH007940030504847C0D	4847	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2993MH007940030504848C0D	4848	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
2993MH007940030504849C0D	4849	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00095	REMS UV sensor ~15 cm standoff	2993MH00095001100001C0D	1	autofocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		2993MH00095001100002C0D	2	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
mN00703	Focus Merges	2993MH0070300110000300D	3	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2993 with NEI CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4842-4849 - best focus image product
		2993MH0070300110000450D	4	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2993 with NEI CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4842-4849 - range map product
		2993MH0070300110000500D	5	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2993 with NEI CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4831-4838 - best focus image product
		2993MH0070300110000650D	6	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2993 with NEI CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4831-4838 - range map product

updated: 13_January_2021

Sol 2994 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	7 Jan 21
camera position:	6
total parent images:	27
focus merges performed:	2
total focus merge products:	4
total parent images + focus merge products:	31

MAHLI imaged the targets Airor and Traquair at the Sands of Forvie campaign site and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00122	Airor ~5 cm standoff	2994MH00122001100070C0	7	autofocus sub-frame for target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 5 cm
		2994MH00122001100080C0	8	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 5 cm
mN00706	Traquair ~25 cm standoff	2994MH007060001100090C0	9	autofocus sub-frame for target Traquair - small bedform crest - standoff near 25 cm
		2994MH00706001100010C0	10	target Traquair - small bedform crest - standoff near 25 cm
mN00740	Traquair stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	2994MH007060021100011C0	11	target Traquair - small bedform crest - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		2994MH007400001100012C0	12	autofocus sub-frame for target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		2994MH00740001100013C0	13	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		2994MH00740001100014C0	14	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		2994MH00740001100015C0	15	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100016C0	16	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100017C0	17	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100018C0	18	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100019C0	19	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100020C0	20	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100021C0	21	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100022C0	22	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00740	Traquair stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	2994MH007400021100023C0	23	autofocus sub-frame for target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		2994MH00740001100024C0	24	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		2994MH00740001100025C0	25	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		2994MH00740001100026C0	26	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100027C0	27	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100028C0	28	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100029C0	29	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100030C0	30	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100031C0	31	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100032C0	32	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		2994MH00740001100033C0	33	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00703	Focus Merges	2994MH007030001100034R00
2994MH007030001100035S00	35			target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2994 with HSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 26-33 - range map product
2994MH007030001100036R00	36			target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2994 with HSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 15-22 - best focus image product
2994MH007030001100037S00	37			target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2994 with HSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 15-22 - range map product

updated: 10_January_2021

Sol 2995 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0-Jan-21			
camera positions:	0	Image ID:		
total parent images:	2	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
focus merges performed:	0	CDPID:		
total focus merge products:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total parent images + focus merge products:	2			
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Traquair at the Sands of Forvie campaign site.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00122	Traquair -5 cm standoff	2995MH00122001100038C00	38	autofocus sub-frame for target Traquair - small bedform crest - standoff near 5 cm
		2995MH00122001100039C00	39	target Traquair - small bedform crest - standoff near 5 cm

updated: 12_January_2021

Sol 2998 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	15_Aug-21
camera positions:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	12
total parent images + focus merge products:	12

summary of MAHLI activities: The focus stack images from Sol 2992, 2993 and 2994 were merged again due to an arm fault on Sol 2996 which prevented acquisition of new MAHLI data.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00163	Focus Merges	2998MH001630001100040R0	40	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2994 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 26-33 - best focus image product
		2998MH001630001100041S0	41	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2994 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 26-33 - range map product
		2998MH001630001100042R0	42	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2994 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 15-22 - best focus image product
		2998MH001630001100043S0	43	target Traquair - small bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2994 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 15-22 - range map product
		2998MH001630001100044R0	44	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2993 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4842-4849 - best focus image product
		2998MH001630001100045S0	45	target Airor - bedform crest - standoff near 7 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2993 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4842-4849 - range map product
		2998MH001630001100046R0	46	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2993 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4831-4838 - best focus image product
		2998MH001630001100047S0	47	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - standoff near 17 mm - focus stack acquired sol 2993 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4831-4838 - range map product
		2998MH001630001100048R0	48	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2992 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4810-4817 - best focus image product
		2998MH001630001100049S0	49	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2992 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4810-4817 - range map product
		2998MH001630001100050R0	50	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2992 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4799-4806 - best focus image product
		2998MH001630001100051S0	51	target Ratharsair - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 2992 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4799-4806 - range map product

updated: 30_June_2021

Sol 2999 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI imaged the targets Kieber and Nugarth. MAHLI also imaged the wheel surface interfaces of the two rover front wheels.		
acquired/performed date(s)	23_Jan_21	Image ID:		
camera position:	4	Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
total parent images:	8	CDPID:		
focus merges performed:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total focus merge products:	0			
total parent images + focus merge products:	8			
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00705	Kieber ~25 cm standoff	2999MH00706001100052C00	52	autofocus sub-frame for target Kieber - standoff near 25 cm
		2999MH00706001100053C00	53	target Kieber - standoff near 25 cm
		2999MH007060021100054C00	54	target Kieber - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00706	Nugarth ~25 cm standoff	2999MH00706001100055C00	55	autofocus sub-frame for target Nugarth - standoff near 25 cm
		2999MH007060021100056C00	56	target Nugarth - standoff near 25 cm
		2999MH007060021100057C00	57	target Nugarth - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00239	Rover Right Front Wheel	2999MH00239001100058C00	58	rover right front wheel contact with surface - rover stability assessment - target at about 140 cm - manual focus at motor count 12660
mN00262	Rover Left Front Wheel	2999MH00262001100059C00	59	rover left front wheel contact with surface - rover stability assessment - target at about 112 cm - manual focus at motor count 12660

updated: 18_January_2021

Sol 3004 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	17_Jan_21
camera position	6
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	35

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

MAHLI imaged the target Tomb_of_the_Eagles.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN100705	Tomb_of_the_Eagles ~25 cm standoff	3004MH00760001100960C00	60	autofocus sub-frame for target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 25 cm
		3004MH00760011100961C00	61	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 25 cm
		3004MH00760021100962C00	62	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN100763	Tomb_of_the_Eagles stereo 1 ~5 cm standoff	3004MH00763001100963C00	63	autofocus sub-frame for target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3004MH00763001100964C00	64	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3004MH00763001100965C00	65	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3004MH00763001100966C00	66	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00763001100967C00	67	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00763001100968C00	68	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00763001100969C00	69	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00763001100970C00	70	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00763001100971C00	71	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00763001100972C00	72	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00763001100973C00	73	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN100763	Tomb_of_the_Eagles stereo 2 ~5 cm standoff	3004MH00763001100974C00
3004MH00763001100975C00	75			target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3004MH00763001100976C00	76			target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3004MH00763001100977C00	77			target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3004MH00763001100978C00	78			target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3004MH00763001100979C00	79			target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3004MH00763001100980C00	80			target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3004MH00763001100981C00	81			target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3004MH00763001100982C00	82			target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3004MH00763001100983C00	83			target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3004MH00763001100984C00	84			target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100801	Tomb_of_the_Eagles ~1 cm standoff			3004MH00801001100985C00
		3004MH00801001100986C00	86	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 1 cm
		3004MH00801001100987C00	87	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3004MH00801001100988C00	88	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00801001100989C00	89	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00801001100990C00	90	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00801001100991C00	91	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00801001100992C00	92	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00801001100993C00	93	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00801001100994C00	94	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3004MH00801001100995C00	95	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 19_January_2021

Sol 3005 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Jan-21
camera position	25
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	30

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities
 MAHLI imaged 2 3007 of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel. The focus stack images from Sol 3004 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3005MH0076900110009601	96	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3005MH0077000110009701	97	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3005MH0077100110009801	98	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3005MH0077200110009901	99	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3005MH0076900110010001	100	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3005MH0077000110010101	101	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3005MH0077100110010201	102	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3005MH0077200110010301	103	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3005MH0076900110010401	104	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3005MH0077000110010501	105	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3005MH0077100110010601	106	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3005MH0077200110010701	107	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3005MH0076900110010801	108	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3005MH0077000110010901	109	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3005MH0077100110011001	110	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3005MH0077200110011101	111	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3005MH0076900110011201	112	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3005MH0077000110011301	113	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3005MH0077100110011401	114	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3005MH0077200110011501	115	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3005 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00189	Focus Merges	3005MH0018900010011600	116	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3004 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 88-95 - best focus image product
		3005MH0018900010011700	117	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3004 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 88-95 - range map product
		3005MH0018900010011800	118	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3004 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 77-84 - best focus image product
		3005MH0018900010011900	119	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3004 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 77-84 - range map product
		3005MH0018900010012000	120	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3004 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 66-73 - best focus image product
		3005MH0018900010012100	121	target Tomb_of_the_Eagles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3004 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 66-73 - range map product

updated: 18_March_2021

Sol 3007 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	20 Jan 21
camera position	6
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	33

MAHLI imaged the target Easthouses.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Easthouses ~25 cm standoff	3007MH0019000110012200	122	autofocus sub-frame for target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3007MH0019000110012300	123	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00297	Easthouses APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3007MH00297002110012400	124	autofocus sub-frame for target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3007MH00297002110012500	125	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3007MH00297002110012600	126	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110012700	127	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110012800	128	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110012900	129	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110013000	130	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110013100	131	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110013200	132	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110013300	133	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00297	Easthouses APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3007MH00297002110013400	134	autofocus sub-frame for target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3007MH00297002110013500	135	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3007MH00297002110013600	136	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110013700	137	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110013800	138	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110013900	139	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110014000	140	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110014100	141	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110014200	142	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110014300	143	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00297	Easthouses APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3007MH00297002110014400	144	autofocus sub-frame for target Easthouses - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3007MH00297002110014500	145	target Easthouses - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3007MH00297002110014600	146	target Easthouses - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110014700	147	target Easthouses - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110014800	148	target Easthouses - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110014900	149	target Easthouses - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110015000	150	target Easthouses - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110015100	151	target Easthouses - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110015200	152	target Easthouses - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3007MH00297002110015300	153	target Easthouses - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 21_January_2021

Sol 3008 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	21-Jan-21
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	6

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3007 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00189	Focus Merges	3008MH001930001100154N00	154	target Easthouses - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3007 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 146-153 - best focus image product
		3008MH001930001100155S00	155	target Easthouses - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3007 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 146-153 - range map product
		3008MH001930001100156R00	156	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3007 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 136-143 - best focus image product
		3008MH001930001100157S00	157	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3007 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 136-143 - range map product
		3008MH001930001100158R00	158	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3007 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 126-133 - best focus image product
		3008MH001930001100159S00	159	target Easthouses - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3007 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 126-133 - range map product

Sol 3010 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	26 Jan 21			
		Camera position	7	Image ID:		
		Total parent images	61	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received		
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:		
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
		Total parent images + focus merge products	61			
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT target La_Roque_Gageac and the target Gageac_et_Rouillac.						
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mhl00706	La_Roque_Gageac after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3010MH0007060001100160C00	160	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		3010MH000706001100161C00	161	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		3010MH0007060021100162C00	162	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mhl00699	La_Roque_Gageac after DRT stereo 1 ~5 cm standoff	3010MH0006990001100163C00	163	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3010MH000699001100164C00	164	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3010MH0006990021100165C00	165	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3010MH0006990031100166C00	166	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0006990041100167C00	167	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0006990051100168C00	168	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0006990061100169C00	169	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0006990071100170C00	170	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0006990081100171C00	171	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0006990091100172C00	172	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0006990101100173C00	173	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mhl00699	La_Roque_Gageac after DRT stereo 2 ~5 cm standoff	3010MH0006990001100174C00	174	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3010MH000699001100175C00	175	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3010MH0006990021100176C00	176			target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3010MH0006990031100177C00	177			target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH0006990041100178C00	178			target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH0006990051100179C00	179			target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH0006990061100180C00	180			target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH0006990071100181C00	181			target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH0006990081100182C00	182			target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH0006990091100183C00	183			target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH0006990101100184C00	184			target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mhl00785	La_Roque_Gageac after DRT ~1 cm standoff			3010MH0007850001100185C00	185	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
				3010MH000785001100186C00	186	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3010MH0007850021100187C00	187	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3010MH0007850031100188C00	188	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0007850041100189C00	189	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0007850051100190C00	190	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0007850061100191C00	191	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0007850071100192C00	192	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0007850081100193C00	193	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0007850091100194C00	194	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH0007850101100195C00	195	target La_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mhl00706	Gageac_et_Rouillac ~25 cm standoff	3010MH0007060001100196C00	196	autofocus sub-frame for target Gageac_et_Rouillac - standoff near 25 cm
				3010MH000706001100197C00	197	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - standoff near 25 cm
3010MH0007060021100198C00	198			target Gageac_et_Rouillac - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mhl00721	Gageac_et_Rouillac stereo 1 ~5 cm standoff	3010MH000710001100200C00	199	autofocus sub-frame for target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3010MH000710002100201C00	200	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3010MH000710003100202C00	201	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3010MH000710004100203C00	202	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH000710005100204C00	203	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH000710006100205C00	204	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH000710007100206C00	205	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH000710008100207C00	206	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH000710009100208C00	207	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH000710010100209C00	208	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3010MH000710011100210C00	209	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mhl00721	Gageac_et_Rouillac stereo 2 ~5 cm standoff	3010MH000710001100211C00	210	autofocus sub-frame for target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3010MH0007100021100212C00	211	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3010MH0007100031100213C00	212			target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3010MH0007100041100214C00	213			target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH0007100051100215C00	214			target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH0007100061100216C00	215			target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH0007100071100217C00	216			target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH0007100081100218C00	217			target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH0007100091100219C00	218			target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH0007100101100220C00	219			target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3010MH000710011100221C00	220			target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 25_January_2021

Sol 3011 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26 Jan 21
camera positions	5
total parent images	1
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	11

MAHLI imaged the left middle wheel and the focus stack images from Sol 3010 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00213	Left Middle Wheel	3011MH00081800110021101	221	cover left middle wheel inspection - manual focus assumes standoff about 189 cm
mN00227	Focus Merges	3011MH0002270001100222800	222	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3010 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 213-220 - best focus image product
		3011MH0002270001100222900	223	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3010 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 213-220 - range map product
		3011MH0002270001100224800	224	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3010 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 202-209 - best focus image product
		3011MH0002270001100225900	225	target Gageac_et_Rouillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3010 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 202-209 - range map product
		3011MH0002270001100226800	226	target Ia_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3010 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 188-195 - best focus image product
		3011MH0002270001100227900	227	target Ia_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3010 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 188-195 - range map product
		3011MH0002270001100228800	228	target Ia_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3010 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 177-184 - best focus image product
		3011MH0002270001100229900	229	target Ia_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3010 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 177-184 - range map product
		3011MH0002270001100230800	230	target Ia_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3010 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 166-173 - best focus image product
		3011MH0002270001100231900	231	target Ia_Roque_Gageac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3010 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 166-173 - range map product

updated: 27_January_2021

Sol 3013 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	01-Jan-2013
camera position	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Champagnac and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00586	Champagnac ~15 cm standoff	3013MH0005860001100232C0D	232	autofocus sub-frame for target Champagnac - standoff near 15 cm
		3013MH000586001100233C0D	233	target Champagnac - standoff near 15 cm
mN00182	Champagnac stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3013MH0001820001100234C0D	234	autofocus sub-frame for target Champagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3013MH0001820001100235C0D	235	target Champagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3013MH0001820001100236C0D	236	target Champagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100237C0D	237	target Champagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100238C0D	238	target Champagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100239C0D	239	target Champagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100240C0D	240	target Champagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100241C0D	241	target Champagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100242C0D	242	target Champagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100243C0D	243	target Champagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Champagnac stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3013MH0001820001100244C0D	244	autofocus sub-frame for target Champagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3013MH0001820001100245C0D	245	target Champagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3013MH0001820001100246C0D	246	target Champagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100247C0D	247	target Champagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100248C0D	248	target Champagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100249C0D	249	target Champagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100250C0D	250	target Champagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100251C0D	251	target Champagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100252C0D	252	target Champagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001820001100253C0D	253	target Champagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00184	Champagnac ~2 cm standoff	3013MH0001840001100254C0D	254	autofocus sub-frame for target Champagnac - standoff near 2 cm
		3013MH0001840001100255C0D	255	target Champagnac - standoff near 2 cm
		3013MH0001840001100256C0D	256	target Champagnac - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001840001100257C0D	257	target Champagnac - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001840001100258C0D	258	target Champagnac - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001840001100259C0D	259	target Champagnac - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001840001100260C0D	260	target Champagnac - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001840001100261C0D	261	target Champagnac - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001840001100262C0D	262	target Champagnac - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3013MH0001840001100263C0D	263	target Champagnac - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus merges	3013MH0001930001100264R0D	264	target Champagnac - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3013 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 256-263 - best focus image product
		3013MH0001930001100265S0D	265	target Champagnac - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3013 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 256-263 - range map product
		3013MH0001930001100266R0D	266	target Champagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3013 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 246-253 - best focus image product
		3013MH0001930001100267S0D	267	target Champagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3013 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 246-253 - range map product
		3013MH0001930001100268R0D	268	target Champagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3013 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 236-243 - best focus image product
		3013MH0001930001100269S0D	269	target Champagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3013 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 236-243 - range map product

updated: 01_February_2021

Sol 3015 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	01-Feb-2021
camera positions	4
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	41

MAHLI imaged the target Beapouyet and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00706	Beapouyet ~25 cm standoff	3015MH00070600110027000	270	autofocus sub-frame for target Beapouyet - standoff near 25 cm
		3015MH00070600110027100	271	target Beapouyet - standoff near 25 cm
		3015MH00070600110027200	272	target Beapouyet - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00707	Beapouyet ~5 cm standoff	3015MH00070600110027300	273	autofocus sub-frame for target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3015MH00070600110027400	274	target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3015MH00070600110027500	275	target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3015MH00070600110027600	276	target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110027700	277	target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110027800	278	target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110027900	279	target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110028000	280	target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110028100	281	target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110028200	282	target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110028300	283	target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00708	Beapouyet stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3015MH00070600110028400	284	autofocus sub-frame for target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3015MH00070600110028500	285	target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3015MH00070600110028600	286	target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3015MH00070600110028700	287	target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110028800	288	target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110028900	289	target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110029000	290	target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110029100	291	target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110029200	292	target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110029300	293	target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00070600110029400	294	target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00709	Beapouyet ~1 cm standoff	3015MH00079400110029500	295	autofocus sub-frame for target Beapouyet - standoff near 1 cm
		3015MH00079400110029600	296	target Beapouyet - standoff near 1 cm
		3015MH00079400110029700	297	target Beapouyet - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3015MH00079400110029800	298	target Beapouyet - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00079400110029900	299	target Beapouyet - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00079400110030000	300	target Beapouyet - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00079400110030100	301	target Beapouyet - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00079400110030200	302	target Beapouyet - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00079400110030300	303	target Beapouyet - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00079400110030400	304	target Beapouyet - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3015MH00079400110030500	305	target Beapouyet - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus Merges	3015MH00019300110030600	306	target Beapouyet - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3015 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 298-305 - best focus image product
		3015MH00019300110030700	307	target Beapouyet - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3015 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 298-305 - range map product
		3015MH00019300110030800	308	target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3015 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 287-294 - best focus image product
		3015MH00019300110030900	309	target Beapouyet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3015 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 287-294 - range map product
		3015MH00019300110031000	310	target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3015 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 276-283 - best focus image product
		3015MH00019300110031100	311	target Beapouyet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3015 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 276-283 - range map product

updated: 15_February_2021

Sol 3017 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	20 Jan 21	
		camera position:	54	Image ID:
		total parent images:	0	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed:	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products:	54	
<p>MAHLI imaged a target named Neuvic after it was brushed by the DRT. After that, the robotic arm was positioned high above the rover and pointed southwestward, toward the Sands of Forvie sand sheet. There, it acquired a daylight context image of the scene, followed by 17 images (1 test set-up and 16 images commanded as video), at night, in an experiment to help constrain the upper threshold on whether sputtering sands on Mars spark a visible triboelectric discharge (triboluminescence). The camera position for this was described by Figgett et al. (2012, http://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-012-9910-4) as "periscope and grill's eye view" - this is the first time it has been used since landing.</p>				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mnh00706	Neuvic after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3017MHD00760600110031200	312	autofocus sub-frame for target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3017MHD00760601110031300	313	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3017MHD00760602110031400	314	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mnh007063	Neuvic after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3017MHD00763000110031500	315	autofocus sub-frame for target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3017MHD00763001110031600	316	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3017MHD00763002110031700	317	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3017MHD00763003110031800	318	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00763004110031900	319	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00763005110032000	320	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00763006110032100	321	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00763007110032200	322	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00763008110032300	323	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00763009110032400	324	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00763010110032500	325	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mnh007063	Neuvic after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3017MHD00763001110032600	326	autofocus sub-frame for target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3017MHD00763002110032700	327	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3017MHD00763003110032800	328	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3017MHD00763004110032900	329	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00763005110033000	330	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00763006110033100	331	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00763007110033200	332	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00763008110033300	333	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00763009110033400	334	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00763010110033500	335	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD0076301110033600	336	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mnh00802	Neuvic after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3017MHD0082000110033700	337	autofocus sub-frame for target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3017MHD00820002110033800	338	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3017MHD00820003110033900	339	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3017MHD00820004110034000	340	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00820005110034100	341	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00820006110034200	342	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00820007110034300	343	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00820008110034400	344	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00820009110034500	345	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD00820010110034600	346	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3017MHD0082001110034700	347	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mnh00819	daylight context - Sands of Forvie triboluminescence experiment	3017MHD0081900110034800	348	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - daylight context image - manual focus at infinity
mnh00820	night test set-up - Sands of Forvie triboluminescence experiment	3017MHD0082000110034900	349	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - test set-up
mnh00821	night video - Sands of Forvie triboluminescence experiment	3017MHD00821000110035000	350	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 1 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100351000	351	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 2 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100352000	352	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 3 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100353000	353	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 4 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100354000	354	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 5 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100355000	355	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 6 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100356000	356	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 7 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100357000	357	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 8 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100358000	358	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 9 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100359000	359	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 10 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100360000	360	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 11 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100361000	361	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 12 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100362000	362	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 13 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100363000	363	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 14 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100364000	364	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 15 of 16-frame video
		3017MHD008210001100365000	365	solian triboelectric discharge threshold investigation - Sands of Forvie sand sheet - night image with no LED and no Phobos illumination - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity - 16 of 16-frame video

updated: 01_February_2021

Sol 3018 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0 # 0 21
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	3
total focus merge products:	6
total parent images + focus merge products:	6

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: The focus stack images from Sol 3017 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00189	Focus Merges	3018MH00193000110036800	366	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3017 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 340-347 - best focus image product
		3018MH001930001100367500	367	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3017 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 340-347 - range map product
		3018MH00193000110036800	368	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3017 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 329-336 - best focus image product
		3018MH001930001100369500	369	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3017 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 329-336 - range map product
		3018MH001930001100370000	370	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3017 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 318-325 - best focus image product
		3018MH001930001100371500	371	target Neuvic - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3017 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 318-325 - range map product

updated: 04_February_2021

Sol 3020 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	8-Feb-21
camera positions	2
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	27

MAHLI imaged the target Lunas and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00706	Lunas -25 cm standoff	3020MH0007060001100376C00	372	autofocus sub-frame for target Lunas - standoff near 25 cm
		3020MH000706001100373C00	373	target Lunas - standoff near 25 cm
		3020MH0007060021100374C00	374	target Lunas - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00182	Lunas stereo-1 -5 cm standoff	3020MH0001820001100375C00	375	autofocus sub-frame for target Lunas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3020MH0001820011100376C00	376	target Lunas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3020MH0001820021100377C00	377	target Lunas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820031100378C00	378	target Lunas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820041100379C00	379	target Lunas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820051100380C00	380	target Lunas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820061100381C00	381	target Lunas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820071100382C00	382	target Lunas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820081100383C00	383	target Lunas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820091100384C00	384	target Lunas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Lunas stereo-2 -5 cm standoff	3020MH0001820001100385C00	385	autofocus sub-frame for target Lunas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3020MH0001820011100386C00	386	target Lunas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3020MH0001820021100387C00	387	target Lunas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820031100388C00	388	target Lunas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820041100389C00	389	target Lunas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820051100390C00	390	target Lunas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820061100391C00	391	target Lunas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820071100392C00	392	target Lunas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820081100393C00	393	target Lunas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3020MH0001820091100394C00	394	target Lunas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges	3020MH0002650001100395R00	395	target Lunas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3020 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 387-394 - best focus image product
		3020MH0002650001100396S00	396	target Lunas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3020 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 387-394 - range map product
		3020MH0002650001100397R00	397	target Lunas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3020 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 377-384 - best focus image product
		3020MH0002650001100398S00	398	target Lunas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3020 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 377-384 - range map product

updated: 08_February_2021

Sol 3022 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	5-Feb-21
camera positions	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Tammies and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mHN00706	Tammies ~25 cm standoff	3022MH0007960021100399KCD	399	autofocus sub-frame for target Tammies - standoff near 25 cm
		3022MH0007960011100400KCD	400	target Tammies - standoff near 25 cm
		3022MH0007960021100401KCD	401	target Tammies - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mHN00073	Tammies stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3022MH000173001100402KCD	402	autofocus sub-frame for target Tammies - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3022MH000173001100403KCD	403	target Tammies - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3022MH000173001100404KCD	404	target Tammies - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100405KCD	405	target Tammies - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100406KCD	406	target Tammies - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100407KCD	407	target Tammies - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100408KCD	408	target Tammies - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100409KCD	409	target Tammies - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100410KCD	410	target Tammies - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100411KCD	411	target Tammies - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mHN00073	Tammies stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3022MH000173001100412KCD	412	autofocus sub-frame for target Tammies - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3022MH000173001100413KCD	413	target Tammies - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3022MH000173001100414KCD	414	target Tammies - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100415KCD	415	target Tammies - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100416KCD	416	target Tammies - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100417KCD	417	target Tammies - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100418KCD	418	target Tammies - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100419KCD	419	target Tammies - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100420KCD	420	target Tammies - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000173001100421KCD	421	target Tammies - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mHN000796	Tammies ~1 cm standoff	3022MH000796001100422KCD	422	autofocus sub-frame for target Tammies - standoff near 1 cm
		3022MH0007960021100423KCD	423	target Tammies - standoff near 1 cm
		3022MH000796001100424KCD	424	target Tammies - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH0007960021100425KCD	425	target Tammies - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000796001100426KCD	426	target Tammies - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH0007960021100427KCD	427	target Tammies - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000796001100428KCD	428	target Tammies - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH0007960021100429KCD	429	target Tammies - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH000796001100430KCD	430	target Tammies - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3022MH0007960021100431KCD	431	target Tammies - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mHN00039	Focus Merges	3022MH000193001100432KCD	432	target Tammies - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3022 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 424-431 - best focus image product
		3022MH000193001100433KCD	433	target Tammies - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3022 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 424-431 - range map product
		3022MH000193001100434KCD	434	target Tammies - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3022 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 414-421 - best focus image product
		3022MH000193001100435KCD	435	target Tammies - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3022 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 414-421 - range map product
		3022MH000193001100436KCD	436	target Tammies - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3022 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 404-411 - best focus image product
		3022MH000193001100437KCD	437	target Tammies - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3022 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 404-411 - range map product

Sol 3024 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	0 Feb 21
camera positions	0
total parent images	72
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	72

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT target COUTURES and the target BIRON.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNID0706	COUTURES after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3024MH0007060001100430C00	438	autofocus sub-frame for target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3024MH000706001100439C00	439	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3024MH0007060021100440C00	440	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNID0709	COUTURES after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3024MH000709001100441C00	441	autofocus sub-frame for target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3024MH0007090011100442C00	442	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3024MH0007090021100443C00	443	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3024MH0007090031100444C00	444	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007090041100445C00	445	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007090051100446C00	446	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007090061100447C00	447	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007090071100448C00	448	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007090081100449C00	449	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007090091100450C00	450	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNID0709	COUTURES after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3024MH0007090011100451C00	451	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007090011100452C00	452	autofocus sub-frame for target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3024MH0007090011100453C00	453	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3024MH0007090021100454C00	454	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3024MH0007090031100455C00	455	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007090041100456C00	456	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007090051100457C00	457	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007090061100458C00	458	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007090071100459C00	459	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007090081100460C00	460	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNID0823	COUTURES after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3024MH000823001100461C00	461	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0008230021100462C00	462	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0008230011100463C00	463	autofocus sub-frame for target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3024MH0008230011100464C00	464	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3024MH0008230011100465C00	465	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3024MH0008230011100466C00	466	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0008230011100467C00	467	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0008230011100468C00	468	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0008230011100469C00	469	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0008230011100470C00	470	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNID0706	BIRON ~25 cm standoff	3024MH0007060011100471C00	471	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007060011100472C00	472	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0007060011100473C00	473	target COUTURES - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNID0699	BIRON stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3024MH0006990011100474C00	474	autofocus sub-frame for target BIRON - standoff near 25 cm
		3024MH0006990011100475C00	475	target BIRON - standoff near 25 cm
		3024MH0006990011100476C00	476	target BIRON - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3024MH0006990011100477C00	477	autofocus sub-frame for target BIRON - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3024MH0006990011100478C00	478	target BIRON - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3024MH0006990011100479C00	479	target BIRON - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3024MH0006990011100480C00	480	target BIRON - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0006990011100481C00	481	target BIRON - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0006990011100482C00	482	target BIRON - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0006990011100483C00	483	target BIRON - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNID0699	BIRON stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3024MH0006990011100484C00	484	target BIRON - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0006990011100485C00	485	target BIRON - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0006990011100486C00	486	target BIRON - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0006990011100487C00	487	target BIRON - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0006990011100488C00	488	autofocus sub-frame for target BIRON - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3024MH0006990011100489C00	489	target BIRON - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3024MH0006990011100490C00	490	target BIRON - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3024MH0006990011100491C00	491	target BIRON - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0006990011100492C00	492	target BIRON - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0006990011100493C00	493	target BIRON - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNID0699	BIRON stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3024MH0006990011100494C00	494	target BIRON - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0006990011100495C00	495	target BIRON - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0006990011100496C00	496	target BIRON - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0006990011100497C00	497	target BIRON - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH0006990011100498C00	498	target BIRON - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00712	Biron -2 cm standoff	3024MH00712001100499C00	499	autofocus sub-frame for target Biron - standoff near 2 cm
		3024MH007120011100500C00	500	target Biron - standoff near 2 cm
		3024MH007120021100501C00	501	target Biron - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3024MH007120031100502C00	502	target Biron - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH007120031100503C00	503	target Biron - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH007120031100504C00	504	target Biron - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH007120031100505C00	505	target Biron - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH007120031100506C00	506	target Biron - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH007120031100507C00	507	target Biron - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3024MH007120031100508C00	508	target Biron - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3024MH007120031100509C00	509	target Biron - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 08_February_2021

Sol 3025 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	0-Feb-21
camera positions	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

summary of MAHLI activities: The focus stack images from Sol 3024 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00163	Focus Merges	3025MH001630001100510N00	510	target Biron - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3024 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 502-509 - best focus image product
		3025MH001630001100511S00	511	target Biron - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3024 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 502-509 - range map product
		3025MH001630001100512N00	512	target Biron - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3024 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 491-499 - best focus image product
		3025MH001630001100513S00	513	target Biron - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3024 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 491-499 - range map product
		3025MH001630001100514N00	514	target Biron - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3024 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 480-487 - best focus image product
		3025MH001630001100515S00	515	target Biron - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3024 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 480-487 - range map product
		3025MH001630001100516N00	516	target Coutures - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3024 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 466-473 - best focus image product
		3025MH001630001100517S00	517	target Coutures - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3024 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 466-473 - range map product
		3025MH001630001100518N00	518	target Coutures - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3024 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 455-462 - best focus image product
		3025MH001630001100519S00	519	target Coutures - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3024 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 455-462 - range map product
		3025MH001630001100520N00	520	target Coutures - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3024 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 444-451 - best focus image product
		3025MH001630001100521S00	521	target Coutures - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3024 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 444-451 - range map product

updated: 11_February_2021

Sol 3026 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	0-Feb-21
camera positions	2
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	27

MAHLI imaged the target Labouquerie and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00705	Labouquerie ~22 cm standoff	3026MH0070600110052000	522	autofocus sub-frame for target Labouquerie - standoff near 22 cm
		3026MH0070600110052300	523	target Labouquerie - standoff near 22 cm
		3026MH0070600110052400	524	target Labouquerie - standoff near 22 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3026MH0030600110052500	525	autofocus sub-frame for target Labouquerie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
mN00306	Labouquerie stereo 1 ~45 mm standoff	3026MH0030600110052600	526	target Labouquerie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3026MH0030600110052700	527	target Labouquerie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3026MH0030600110052800	528	target Labouquerie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3026MH0030600110052900	529	target Labouquerie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3026MH0030600110053000	530	target Labouquerie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3026MH0030600110053100	531	target Labouquerie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3026MH0030600110053200	532	target Labouquerie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3026MH0030600110053300	533	target Labouquerie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3026MH0030600110053400	534	target Labouquerie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00306	Labouquerie stereo 2 ~45 mm standoff	3026MH0030600110053500
3026MH0030600110053600	536			target Labouquerie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
3026MH0030600110053700	537			target Labouquerie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3026MH0030600110053800	538			target Labouquerie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3026MH0030600110053900	539			target Labouquerie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3026MH0030600110054000	540			target Labouquerie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3026MH0030600110054100	541			target Labouquerie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3026MH0030600110054200	542			target Labouquerie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3026MH0030600110054300	543			target Labouquerie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3026MH0030600110054400	544			target Labouquerie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges	3026MH0026500110054500	545	target Labouquerie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3026 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 537-544 - best focus image product
		3026MH0026500110054600	546	target Labouquerie - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3026 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 537-544 - range map product
		3026MH0026500110054700	547	target Labouquerie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3026 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 527-534 - best focus image product
		3026MH0026500110054800	548	target Labouquerie - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3026 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 527-534 - range map product

updated: 11_February_2021

Sol 3027 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	10-Feb-21
camera positions	4
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	41

MAHLI imaged the target Brantome and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mhl00705	Brantome ~25 cm standoff	3027MH000706001100549000	549	autofocus sub-frame for target Brantome - standoff near 25 cm
		3027MH000706001100550000	550	target Brantome - standoff near 25 cm
		3027MH000706001100551000	551	target Brantome - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl00699	Brantome stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3027MH000699001100552000	552	autofocus sub-frame for target Brantome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3027MH000699001100553000	553	target Brantome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3027MH000699001100554000	554	target Brantome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3027MH000699001100555000	555	target Brantome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100556000	556	target Brantome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100557000	557	target Brantome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100558000	558	target Brantome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100559000	559	target Brantome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100560000	560	target Brantome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100561000	561	target Brantome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100562000	562	target Brantome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00699	Brantome stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3027MH000699001100563000	563	autofocus sub-frame for target Brantome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3027MH000699001100564000	564	target Brantome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3027MH000699001100565000	565	target Brantome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3027MH000699001100566000	566	target Brantome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100567000	567	target Brantome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100568000	568	target Brantome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100569000	569	target Brantome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100570000	570	target Brantome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100571000	571	target Brantome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100572000	572	target Brantome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000699001100573000	573	target Brantome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00824	Brantome ~2 cm standoff	3027MH000824001100574000	574	autofocus sub-frame for target Brantome - standoff near 2 cm
		3027MH000824001100575000	575	target Brantome - standoff near 2 cm
		3027MH000824001100576000	576	target Brantome - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3027MH000824001100577000	577	target Brantome - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000824001100578000	578	target Brantome - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000824001100579000	579	target Brantome - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000824001100580000	580	target Brantome - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000824001100581000	581	target Brantome - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000824001100582000	582	target Brantome - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000824001100583000	583	target Brantome - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3027MH000824001100584000	584	target Brantome - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00193	Focus Merges	3027MH000193001100585000	585	target Brantome - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3027 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 577-584 - best focus image product
		3027MH000193001100586000	586	target Brantome - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3027 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 577-584 - range map product
		3027MH000193001100587000	587	target Brantome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3027 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 566-573 - best focus image product
		3027MH000193001100588000	588	target Brantome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3027 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 566-573 - range map product
		3027MH000193001100589000	589	target Brantome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3027 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 555-562 - best focus image product
3027MH000193001100590000	590	target Brantome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3027 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 555-562 - range map product		

updated: 12_February_2021

Sol 3028 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	11-Feb-21
camera positions	8
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	27

MAHLI imaged the target Firbeix and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00705	Firbeix ~25 cm standoff	3028MH0007060001100591C00	591	autofocus sub-frame for target Firbeix - standoff near 25 cm
		3028MH000706001100592C00	592	target Firbeix - standoff near 25 cm
		3028MH0007060021100593C00	593	target Firbeix - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00306	Firbeix stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3028MH0003060001100594C00	594	autofocus sub-frame for target Firbeix - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3028MH0003060021100595C00	595	target Firbeix - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3028MH0003060021100596C00	596	target Firbeix - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100597C00	597	target Firbeix - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100598C00	598	target Firbeix - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100599C00	599	target Firbeix - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100600C00	600	target Firbeix - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100601C00	601	target Firbeix - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100602C00	602	target Firbeix - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100603C00	603	target Firbeix - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00306	Firbeix stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3028MH0003060001100604C00	604	autofocus sub-frame for target Firbeix - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3028MH0003060021100605C00	605	target Firbeix - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3028MH0003060021100606C00	606	target Firbeix - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100607C00	607	target Firbeix - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100608C00	608	target Firbeix - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100609C00	609	target Firbeix - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100610C00	610	target Firbeix - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100611C00	611	target Firbeix - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100612C00	612	target Firbeix - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3028MH0003060021100613C00	613	target Firbeix - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00265	Focus Merges	3028MH0002650001100614R00	614	target Firbeix - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3028 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 606-613 - best focus image product
		3028MH0002650001100615S00	615	target Firbeix - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3028 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 606-613 - range map product
		3028MH0002650001100616R00	616	target Firbeix - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3028 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 596-603 - best focus image product
		3028MH0002650001100617S00	617	target Firbeix - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3028 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 596-603 - range map product

updated: 16_February_2021

Sol 3031 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16-Feb-21
camera positions	6
total parent images	47
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	55

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Dordogne and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00706	Dordogne after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3031MH0007060001100618C00	618	autofocus sub-frame for target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3031MH000706001100619C00	619	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3031MH0007060021100620C00	620	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00723	Dordogne after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3031MH000723001100621C00	621	autofocus sub-frame for target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3031MH000723001100622C00	622	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3031MH000723001100623C00	623	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3031MH000723001100624C00	624	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100625C00	625	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100626C00	626	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100627C00	627	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100628C00	628	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100629C00	629	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100630C00	630	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00723	Dordogne after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3031MH000723001100631C00	631	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100632C00	632	autofocus sub-frame for target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3031MH000723001100633C00	633	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3031MH000723001100634C00	634	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3031MH000723001100635C00	635	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100636C00	636	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100637C00	637	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100638C00	638	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100639C00	639	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100640C00	640	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00823	Dordogne after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~1 cm standoff	3031MH000823001100641C00	641	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000823001100642C00	642	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000823001100643C00	643	autofocus sub-frame for target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3031MH000823001100644C00	644	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3031MH000823001100645C00	645	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3031MH000823001100646C00	646	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000823001100647C00	647	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000823001100648C00	648	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000823001100649C00	649	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000823001100650C00	650	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00723	Dordogne after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3031MH000823001100651C00	651	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000823001100652C00	652	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000823001100653C00	653	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100654C00	654	autofocus sub-frame for target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3031MH000723001100655C00	655	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3031MH000723001100656C00	656	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3031MH000723001100657C00	657	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100658C00	658	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100659C00	659	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100660C00	660	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00153	Focus Merges	3031MH000723001100661C00	661	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100662C00	662	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100663C00	663	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000723001100664C00	664	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3031MH000153001100665R00	665	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3031 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 657-664 - best focus image product
		3031MH000153001100666S00	666	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3031 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 657-664 - range map product
		3031MH000153001100667R00	667	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3031 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 646-653 - best focus image product
		3031MH000153001100668S00	668	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3031 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 635-642 - best focus image product
mNI00153	Focus Merges	3031MH000153001100669R00	669	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3031 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 635-642 - range map product
		3031MH000153001100670S00	670	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3031 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 635-642 - range map product
		3031MH000153001100671R00	671	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3031 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 624-631 - best focus image product
		3031MH000153001100672S00	672	target Dordogne - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3031 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 624-631 - range map product

Sol 3034 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	17-Feb-21	
		camera position	6	Image ID:
		total parent images	53	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	4	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	61	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT / brushed target Limeyrat and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN100705	Limeyrat after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3034MH00706000110067300	673	autofocus sub-frame for target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3034MH0070600110067400	674	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3034MH00706002110067500	675	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN100699	Limeyrat after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	3034MH0069900110067600	676	autofocus sub-frame for target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3034MH00699002110067700	677	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3034MH00699003110067800	678	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3034MH00699004110067900	679	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699005110068000	680	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699006110068100	681	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699007110068200	682	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699008110068300	683	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699009110068400	684	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699010110068500	685	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100699	Limeyrat after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~5 cm standoff	3034MH0069900110068600	686	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699002110068700	687	autofocus sub-frame for target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3034MH00699003110068800	688	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3034MH00699004110068900	689	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3034MH00699005110069000	690	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699006110069100	691	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699007110069200	692	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699008110069300	693	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699009110069400	694	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699010110069500	695	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100705	Limeyrat after DRT APXS spot 3 relief model position 3 ~5 cm standoff	3034MH0070500110069600	696	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00705002110069700	697	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00705003110069800	698	autofocus sub-frame for target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
mN100705	Limeyrat after DRT APXS spot 2 relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff	3034MH00705004110069900	699	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		3034MH00705005110070000	700	autofocus sub-frame for target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
mN100705	Limeyrat after DRT APXS spot 2 relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	3034MH00705006110070100	701	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		3034MH00705007110070200	702	autofocus sub-frame for target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
mN100705	Limeyrat after DRT APXS spot 2 relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	3034MH00705008110070300	703	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		3034MH00705009110070400	704	autofocus sub-frame for target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3034MH00705010110070500	705	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3034MH0070501110070600	706	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3034MH00705012110070700	707	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00705013110070800	708	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00705014110070900	709	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00705015110071000	710	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00705016110071100	711	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00705017110071200	712	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100699	Limeyrat after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3034MH00705018110071300	713	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00705019110071400	714	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH0069900110071500	715	autofocus sub-frame for target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3034MH00699002110071600	716	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3034MH00699003110071700	717	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3034MH00699004110071800	718	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699005110071900	719	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699006110072000	720	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699007110072100	721	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00699008110072200	722	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100153	Focus Merges	3034MH00153000110072300	723	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00153000110072400	724	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00153000110072500	725	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3034MH00153000110072600	726	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3034 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 718-725 - best focus image product
		3034MH00153000110072700	727	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3034 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 718-725 - range map product
		3034MH00153000110072800	728	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3034 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 707-714 - best focus image product
		3034MH00153000110072900	729	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3034 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 707-714 - range map product
		3034MH00153000110073000	730	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3034 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 690-697 - best focus image product
		3034MH00153000110073100	731	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3034 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 690-697 - range map product
		3034MH00153000110073200	732	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3034 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 679-686 - best focus image product
3034MH00153000110073300	733	target Limeyrat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3034 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 679-686 - range map product		

updated: 01_March_2021

Sol 3035 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Feb-21
camera positions	4
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	35

MAHLI imaged the target Fleurac.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN100705	Fleurac ~25 cm standoff	3035MH000760001100734C00	734	autofocus sub-frame for target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3035MH000760011100735C00	735	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3035MH000760021100736C00	736	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3035MH000699001100737C00	737	autofocus sub-frame for target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
mN100699	Fleurac APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3035MH0006990011100738C00	738	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3035MH0006990011100739C00	739	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3035MH0006990011100740C00	740	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100741C00	741	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100742C00	742	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100743C00	743	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100744C00	744	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100745C00	745	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100746C00	746	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100747C00	747	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100699	Fleurac APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3035MH0006990011100748C00	748	autofocus sub-frame for target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3035MH0006990011100749C00	749	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3035MH0006990011100750C00	750	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3035MH0006990011100751C00	751	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100752C00	752	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100753C00	753	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100754C00	754	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100755C00	755	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100756C00	756	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100757C00	757	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3035MH0006990011100758C00	758	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN100699	Fleurac APXS spot 1 ~45 mm standoff	3035MH0006990011100759C00	759	autofocus sub-frame for target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3035MH0006990011100760C00	760	target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3035MH0006990011100761C00	761	target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3035MH0006990011100762C00	762	target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100763C00	763	target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100764C00	764	target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100765C00	765	target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100766C00	766	target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100767C00	767	target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3035MH0006990011100768C00	768	target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3035MH0006990011100769C00	769	target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 25_February_2021

Sol 3036 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Feb-21
camera positions	8
total parent images	15
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	23

MAHLI imaged the target Fleurac and the focus stack images from Sol 3035 and 3036 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mIN00122	Fleurac APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3036MH000122001100770C00	770	autofocus sub-frame for target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3036MH000122001100771C00	771	target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
mIN00122	Fleurac APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3036MH000122001100772C00	772	autofocus sub-frame for target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3036MH000122001100773C00	773	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
mIN00825	Fleurac APXS spot 2 ~3 cm standoff	3036MH000825001100774C00	774	autofocus sub-frame for target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm
		3036MH000825001100775C00	775	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm
		3036MH000825001100776C00	776	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3036MH000825001100777C00	777	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3036MH000825001100778C00	778	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3036MH000825001100779C00	779	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3036MH000825001100780C00	780	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3036MH000825001100781C00	781	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3036MH000825001100782C00	782	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3036MH000825001100783C00	783	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mIN00153	Focus Merges	3036MH000825001100784C00	784	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3036MH0001530001100785R00	785	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3036 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 777-784 - best focus image product
		3036MH0001530001100786S00	786	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3036 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 777-784 - range map product
		3036MH0001530001100787R00	787	target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3035 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 762-769 - best focus image product
		3036MH0001530001100788S00	788	target Fleurac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3035 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 762-769 - range map product
		3036MH0001530001100789R00	789	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3035 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 751-758 - best focus image product
		3036MH0001530001100790S00	790	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3035 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 751-758 - range map product
		3036MH0001530001100791R00	791	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3035 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 740-747 - best focus image product
		3036MH0001530001100792S00	792	target Fleurac - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3035 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 740-747 - range map product

updated: 25_February_2021

Sol 3037 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	20-Feb-21
camera position	6
total parent images	47
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	55

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Chalus and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00705	Chalus after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3037MH000760001100793C00	793	autofocus sub-frame for target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3037MH000760001100794C00	794	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3037MH000760001100795C00	795	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00763	Chalus after DRT APXS spot 1 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3037MH000763001100796C00	796	autofocus sub-frame for target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3037MH000763001100797C00	797	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3037MH000763001100798C00	798	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3037MH000763001100799C00	799	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100800C00	800	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100801C00	801	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100802C00	802	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100803C00	803	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100804C00	804	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100805C00	805	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00763	Chalus after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3037MH000763001100806C00	806	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100807C00	807	autofocus sub-frame for target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3037MH000763001100808C00	808	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3037MH000763001100809C00	809	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3037MH000763001100810C00	810	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100811C00	811	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100812C00	812	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100813C00	813	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100814C00	814	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100815C00	815	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00813	Chalus after DRT APXS spot 2 ~2 cm standoff	3037MH000813001100816C00	816	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000813001100817C00	817	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000813001100818C00	818	autofocus sub-frame for target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm
		3037MH000813001100819C00	819	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm
		3037MH000813001100820C00	820	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3037MH000813001100821C00	821	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000813001100822C00	822	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000813001100823C00	823	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000813001100824C00	824	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000813001100825C00	825	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00763	Chalus after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3037MH000813001100826C00	826	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000813001100827C00	827	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000813001100828C00	828	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100829C00	829	autofocus sub-frame for target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3037MH000763001100830C00	830	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3037MH000763001100831C00	831	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3037MH000763001100832C00	832	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100833C00	833	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100834C00	834	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100835C00	835	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00153	Focus Merges	3037MH000763001100836C00	836	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100837C00	837	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100838C00	838	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000763001100839C00	839	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3037MH000153001100840R00	840	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3037 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 832-839 - best focus image product
		3037MH000153001100841S00	841	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3037 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 832-839 - range map product
		3037MH000153001100842R00	842	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3037 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 821-828 - best focus image product
		3037MH000153001100843S00	843	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3037 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 821-828 - range map product
		3037MH000153001100844R00	844	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3037 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 810-817 - best focus image product
		3037MH000153001100845S00	845	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3037 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 810-817 - range map product
3037MH000153001100846R00	846	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3037 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 799-806 - best focus image product		
3037MH000153001100847S00	847	target Chalus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3037 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 799-806 - range map product		

updated: 25_February_2021

Sol 3040 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-Feb-21
camera positions	8
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Plazac and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00705	Plazac ~25 cm standoff	3040MH000760001100848C0D	848	autofocus sub-frame for target Plazac - standoff near 25 cm		
		3040MH000760011100849C0D	849	target Plazac - standoff near 25 cm		
		3040MH000760021100850C0D	850	target Plazac - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN00763	Plazac stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3040MH000763001100851C0D	851	autofocus sub-frame for target Plazac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3040MH000763001100852C0D	852	target Plazac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3040MH000763001100853C0D	853	target Plazac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3040MH000763001100854C0D	854	target Plazac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3040MH000763001100855C0D	855	target Plazac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3040MH000763001100856C0D	856	target Plazac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3040MH000763001100857C0D	857	target Plazac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3040MH000763001100858C0D	858	target Plazac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3040MH000763001100859C0D	859	target Plazac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3040MH000763001100860C0D	860	target Plazac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3040MH000763001100861C0D	861	target Plazac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00763	Plazac stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3040MH000763001100862C0D	862	autofocus sub-frame for target Plazac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3040MH000763001100863C0D	863	target Plazac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3040MH000763001100864C0D	864			target Plazac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3040MH000763001100865C0D	865			target Plazac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3040MH000763001100866C0D	866			target Plazac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3040MH000763001100867C0D	867			target Plazac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3040MH000763001100868C0D	868			target Plazac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3040MH000763001100869C0D	869			target Plazac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3040MH000763001100870C0D	870			target Plazac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3040MH000763001100871C0D	871			target Plazac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3040MH000763001100872C0D	872			target Plazac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00265	Focus Merges			3040MH0002650001100873R0D	873	target Plazac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3040 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 865-872 - best focus image product
				3040MH0002650001100874S0D	874	target Plazac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3040 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 865-872 - range map product
		3040MH0002650001100875R0D	875	target Plazac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3040 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 854-861 - best focus image product		
		3040MH0002650001100876S0D	876	target Plazac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3040 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 854-861 - range map product		

updated: 01_March_2021

Sol 3042 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-Feb-21
camera positions	8
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Manzac and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00706	Manzac ~25 cm standoff	3042MH000706001100879C00	877	autofocus sub-frame for target Manzac - standoff near 25 cm
		3042MH000706001100878C00	878	target Manzac - standoff near 25 cm
		3042MH000706001100879C00	879	target Manzac - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00723	Manzac ~5 cm standoff	3042MH000723001100880C00	880	autofocus sub-frame for target Manzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3042MH000723001100881C00	881	target Manzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3042MH000723001100882C00	882	target Manzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3042MH000723001100883C00	883	target Manzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100884C00	884	target Manzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100885C00	885	target Manzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100886C00	886	target Manzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100887C00	887	target Manzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100888C00	888	target Manzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100889C00	889	target Manzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100890C00	890	target Manzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00723	Manzac stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3042MH000723001100891C00	891	autofocus sub-frame for target Manzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3042MH000723001100892C00	892	target Manzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3042MH000723001100893C00	893	target Manzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3042MH000723001100894C00	894	target Manzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100895C00	895	target Manzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100896C00	896	target Manzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100897C00	897	target Manzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100898C00	898	target Manzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100899C00	899	target Manzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100900C00	900	target Manzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3042MH000723001100901C00	901	target Manzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges	3042MH0002650001100902R00	902	target Manzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3042 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 894-901 - best focus image product
		3042MH0002650001100903S00	903	target Manzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3042 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 894-901 - range map product
		3042MH0002650001100904R00	904	target Manzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3042 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 883-890 - best focus image product
		3042MH0002650001100905S00	905	target Manzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3042 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 883-890 - range map product

Sol 3044 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	07-Feb-2021
camera position	6
total parent images	75
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	13
total parent images + focus merge products	88

MAHLI imaged the targets Pazayac and Sadillac and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00706	Pazayac ~25 cm standoff	304MH000706001100906C00	906	autofocus sub-frame for target Pazayac - standoff near 25 cm
		304MH000706001100907C00	907	target Pazayac - standoff near 25 cm
		304MH000706001100908C00	908	target Pazayac - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00709	Pazayac stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	304MH000709001100909C00	909	autofocus sub-frame for target Pazayac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		304MH000709001100910C00	910	target Pazayac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		304MH000709001100911C00	911	target Pazayac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		304MH000709001100912C00	912	target Pazayac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100913C00	913	target Pazayac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100914C00	914	target Pazayac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100915C00	915	target Pazayac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100916C00	916	target Pazayac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100917C00	917	target Pazayac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100918C00	918	target Pazayac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100919C00	919	target Pazayac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00709	Pazayac stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	304MH000709001100920C00	920	autofocus sub-frame for target Pazayac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		304MH000709001100921C00	921	target Pazayac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		304MH000709001100922C00	922	target Pazayac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		304MH000709001100923C00	923	target Pazayac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100924C00	924	target Pazayac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100925C00	925	target Pazayac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100926C00	926	target Pazayac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100927C00	927	target Pazayac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100928C00	928	target Pazayac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100929C00	929	target Pazayac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100930C00	930	target Pazayac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00704	Pazayac ~1 cm standoff	304MH000704001100931C00	931	autofocus sub-frame for target Pazayac - standoff near 1 cm
		304MH000704001100932C00	932	target Pazayac - standoff near 1 cm
		304MH000704001100933C00	933	target Pazayac - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		304MH000704001100934C00	934	target Pazayac - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000704001100935C00	935	target Pazayac - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000704001100936C00	936	target Pazayac - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000704001100937C00	937	target Pazayac - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000704001100938C00	938	target Pazayac - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000704001100939C00	939	target Pazayac - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000704001100940C00	940	target Pazayac - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000704001100941C00	941	target Pazayac - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00706	Sadillac ~25 cm standoff	304MH000706001100942C00	942	autofocus sub-frame for target Sadillac - standoff near 25 cm
		304MH000706001100943C00	943	target Sadillac - standoff near 25 cm
		304MH000706001100944C00	944	target Sadillac - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00709	Sadillac stereo-1 ~55 mm standoff	304MH000709001100945C00	945	autofocus sub-frame for target Sadillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		304MH000709001100946C00	946	target Sadillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		304MH000709001100947C00	947	target Sadillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		304MH000709001100948C00	948	target Sadillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100949C00	949	target Sadillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100950C00	950	target Sadillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100951C00	951	target Sadillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100952C00	952	target Sadillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100953C00	953	target Sadillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100954C00	954	target Sadillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100955C00	955	target Sadillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00709	Sadillac stereo-2 ~55 mm standoff	304MH000709001100956C00	956	autofocus sub-frame for target Sadillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		304MH000709001100957C00	957	target Sadillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		304MH000709001100958C00	958	target Sadillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		304MH000709001100959C00	959	target Sadillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100960C00	960	target Sadillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100961C00	961	target Sadillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100962C00	962	target Sadillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100963C00	963	target Sadillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100964C00	964	target Sadillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100965C00	965	target Sadillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		304MH000709001100966C00	966	target Sadillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH000658	Sadillac ~15 mm standoff	3044MH000658001100967C00	967	autofocus sub-frame for target Sadillac - standoff near 15 mm
		3044MH000658001100968C00	968	target Sadillac - standoff near 15 mm
		3044MH000658001100969C00	969	target Sadillac - standoff near 15 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3044MH000658001100970C00	970	target Sadillac - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3044MH000658001100971C00	971	target Sadillac - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3044MH000658001100972C00	972	target Sadillac - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3044MH000658001100973C00	973	target Sadillac - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3044MH000658001100974C00	974	target Sadillac - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3044MH000658001100975C00	975	target Sadillac - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3044MH000658001100976C00	976	target Sadillac - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3044MH000658001100977C00	977	target Sadillac - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00163	Focus Merges	3044MH001630001100978R00	978	target Sadillac - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3044 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 970-977 - best focus image product
		3044MH001630001100979S00	979	target Sadillac - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3044 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 970-977 - range map product
		3044MH001630001100980R00	980	target Sadillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3044 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 959-966 - best focus image product
		3044MH001630001100981S00	981	target Sadillac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3044 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 959-966 - range map product
		3044MH001630001100982R00	982	target Sadillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3044 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 948-955 - best focus image product
		3044MH001630001100983S00	983	target Sadillac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3044 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 948-955 - range map product
		3044MH001630001100984R00	984	target Pazayac - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3044 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 934-941 - best focus image product
		3044MH001630001100985S00	985	target Pazayac - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3044 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 934-941 - range map product
		3044MH001630001100986R00	986	target Pazayac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3044 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 923-930 - best focus image product
		3044MH001630001100987S00	987	target Pazayac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3044 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 923-930 - range map product
3044MH001630001100988R00	988	target Pazayac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3044 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 912-919 - best focus image product		
3044MH001630001100989S00	989	target Pazayac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3044 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 912-919 - range map product		

updated: 09_March_2021

Sol 3047 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	0-see 43/44/45
camera positions	2
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Daglein and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN100705	Daglein ~25 cm standoff	3047MH000706001100990C00	990	autofocus sub-frame for target Daglein - standoff near 25 cm
		3047MH000706001100991C00	991	target Daglein - standoff near 25 cm
		3047MH000706001100992C00	992	target Daglein - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN100699	Daglein stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3047MH000699001100993C00	993	autofocus sub-frame for target Daglein - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3047MH000699001100994C00	994	target Daglein - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3047MH000699001100995C00	995	target Daglein - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3047MH000699001100996C00	996	target Daglein - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3047MH000699001100997C00	997	target Daglein - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3047MH000699001100998C00	998	target Daglein - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3047MH000699001100999C00	999	target Daglein - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3047MH000699001101000C00	1000	target Daglein - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3047MH000699001101001C00	1001	target Daglein - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3047MH000699001101002C00	1002	target Daglein - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3047MH000699001101003C00	1003	target Daglein - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN100699	Daglein stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3047MH000699001101004C00
3047MH000699001101005C00	1005			target Daglein - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3047MH000699001101006C00	1006			target Daglein - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3047MH000699001101007C00	1007			target Daglein - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3047MH000699001101008C00	1008			target Daglein - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3047MH000699001101009C00	1009			target Daglein - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3047MH000699001101010C00	1010			target Daglein - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3047MH000699001101011C00	1011			target Daglein - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3047MH000699001101012C00	1012			target Daglein - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3047MH000699001101013C00	1013			target Daglein - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3047MH000699001101014C00	1014			target Daglein - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100265	Focus Merges			3047MH0002650001101015R00
		3047MH0002650001101016S00	1016	target Daglein - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3047 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1007-1014 - range map product
		3047MH0002650001101017R00	1017	target Daglein - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3047 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 996-1003 - best focus image product
		3047MH0002650001101018S00	1018	target Daglein - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3047 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 996-1003 - range map product

updated: 09_March_2021

Sol 3049 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		0 Mar '21		
camera positions:	0	Image ID:		
total parent images:	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
focus merges performed:	0	CCPFD:		
total focus merge products:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total parent images + focus merge products:	0			
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the targets Marval and Valojoux.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CCPFD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00705	Marval -25 cm standoff	3049MH00706001101019C00	1019	autofocus sub-frame for target Marval - standoff near 25 cm
		3049MH00706001101020C00	1020	target Marval - standoff near 25 cm
		3049MH007060021101021C00	1021	target Marval - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00706	Valojoux -25 cm standoff	3049MH00706001101022C00	1022	autofocus sub-frame for target Valojoux - standoff near 25 cm
		3049MH00706001101023C00	1023	target Valojoux - standoff near 25 cm
		3049MH007060021101024C00	1024	target Valojoux - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure

Sol 3051- MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		acquired/performed date(s)	7 Mar 21			
		camera positions	61	Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
		total parent images	0			
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:		
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
		total parent images + focus merge products	61			
MAHLI imaged the DRT target Montrem and the target Peyrat.						
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN100706	Montrem after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3051MH0007060001101025000	1025	autofocus sub-frame for target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		3051MH0007060011101026000	1026	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		3051MH0007060021101027000	1027	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN100723	Montrem after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3051MH000730001101028000	1028	autofocus sub-frame for target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3051MH000730011101029000	1029	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3051MH000730021101030000	1030	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3051MH000730031101031000	1031	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730041101032000	1032	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730051101033000	1033	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730061101034000	1034	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730071101035000	1035	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730081101036000	1036	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730091101037000	1037	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730101101038000	1038	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN100723	Montrem after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3051MH000730001101039000	1039	autofocus sub-frame for target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3051MH000730011101040000	1040	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3051MH000730021101041000	1041			target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3051MH000730031101042000	1042			target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3051MH000730041101043000	1043			target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3051MH000730051101044000	1044			target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3051MH000730061101045000	1045			target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3051MH000730071101046000	1046			target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3051MH000730081101047000	1047			target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3051MH000730091101048000	1048			target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN100785	Montrem after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3051MH0007850001101050000	1050	autofocus sub-frame for target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm		
		3051MH0007850011101051000	1051	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm		
		3051MH0007850021101052000	1052	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3051MH0007850031101053000	1053	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH0007850041101054000	1054	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH0007850051101055000	1055	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH0007850061101056000	1056	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH0007850071101057000	1057	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH0007850081101058000	1058	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH0007850091101059000	1059	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN100706	Peyrat ~25 cm standoff	3051MH0007060001101061000	1061	autofocus sub-frame for target Peyrat - standoff near 25 cm		
		3051MH0007060011101062000	1062	target Peyrat - standoff near 25 cm		
		3051MH0007060021101063000	1063	target Peyrat - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN100723	Peyrat stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3051MH000730001101064000	1064	autofocus sub-frame for target Peyrat - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3051MH000730011101065000	1065	target Peyrat - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3051MH000730021101066000	1066	target Peyrat - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3051MH000730031101067000	1067	target Peyrat - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730041101068000	1068	target Peyrat - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730051101069000	1069	target Peyrat - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730061101070000	1070	target Peyrat - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730071101071000	1071	target Peyrat - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730081101072000	1072	target Peyrat - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730091101073000	1073	target Peyrat - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN100723	Peyrat stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3051MH000730001101074000	1074	target Peyrat - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730001101075000	1075	autofocus sub-frame for target Peyrat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3051MH000730011101076000	1076	target Peyrat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3051MH000730021101077000	1077	target Peyrat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3051MH000730031101078000	1078	target Peyrat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730041101079000	1079	target Peyrat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730051101080000	1080	target Peyrat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730061101081000	1081	target Peyrat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730071101082000	1082	target Peyrat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3051MH000730081101083000	1083	target Peyrat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3051MH000730091101084000	1084	target Peyrat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack				
3051MH000730101101085000	1085	target Peyrat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack				

updated: 10_March_2021

Sol 3052 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	8 Mar '21
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

summary of MAHLI activities: The focus stack images from Sol 3051 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3052MH0002270001101086R00	1086	target Peyrat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3051 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1078-1085 - best focus image product
		3052MH0002270001101087S00	1087	target Peyrat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3051 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1078-1085 - range map product
		3052MH0002270001101088R00	1088	target Peyrat - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3051 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1067-1074 - best focus image product
		3052MH0002270001101089S00	1089	target Peyrat - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3051 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1067-1074 - range map product
		3052MH0002270001101090R00	1090	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3051 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1053-1060 - best focus image product
		3052MH0002270001101091S00	1091	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3051 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1053-1060 - range map product
		3052MH0002270001101092R00	1092	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3051 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1042-1049 - best focus image product
		3052MH0002270001101093S00	1093	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3051 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1042-1049 - range map product
		3052MH0002270001101094R00	1094	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3051 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1031-1038 - best focus image product
		3052MH0002270001101095S00	1095	target Montrem - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3051 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1031-1038 - range map product

Sol 3054 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	10-Mar-21	
		camera positions	6	Image ID:
		total parent images	53	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	4	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	61	
summary of MAHLI activities				
MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Nontron before and after DRT and a drill bit preload test; then the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Nontron before DRT ~25 cm standoff	3054MH0001900001101096C00	1096	autofocus sub-frame for intended Nontron drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		3054MH0001900001101097C00	1097	intended Nontron drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00212	Nontron before DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3054MH0001210001101098C00	1098	autofocus sub-frame for intended Nontron drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3054MH0001210001101099C00	1099	intended Nontron drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00706	Nontron after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3054MH0007060001101100C00	1100	autofocus sub-frame for intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		3054MH0007060001101101C00	1101	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		3054MH0007060001101102C00	1102	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00763	Nontron after DRT APXS spot 1 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3054MH0007630001101103C00	1103	autofocus sub-frame for intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3054MH0007630001101104C00	1104	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3054MH0007630001101105C00	1105	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3054MH0007630001101106C00	1106	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101107C00	1107	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101108C00	1108	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101109C00	1109	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101110C00	1110	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101111C00	1111	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101112C00	1112	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101113C00	1113	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101114C00	1114	autofocus sub-frame for intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3054MH0007630001101115C00	1115	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3054MH0007630001101116C00	1116	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3054MH0007630001101117C00	1117	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00763	Nontron after DRT APXS spot 1 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3054MH0007630001101118C00	1118	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101119C00	1119	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101120C00	1120	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101121C00	1121	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101122C00	1122	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101123C00	1123	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101124C00	1124	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101125C00	1125	autofocus sub-frame for intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm
mN00785	Nontron after DRT APXS spot 1 ~1 cm standoff	3054MH0007850001101126C00	1126	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm
		3054MH0007850001101127C00	1127	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3054MH0007850001101128C00	1128	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007850001101129C00	1129	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007850001101130C00	1130	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007850001101131C00	1131	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007850001101132C00	1132	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007850001101133C00	1133	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007850001101134C00	1134	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007850001101135C00	1135	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00763	Nontron after DRT APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3054MH0007630001101136C00	1136	autofocus sub-frame for intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3054MH0007630001101137C00	1137	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3054MH0007630001101138C00	1138	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3054MH0007630001101139C00	1139	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101140C00	1140	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101141C00	1141	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101142C00	1142	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101143C00	1143	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3054MH0007630001101144C00	1144	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00465	Nontron after DRT after drill bit preload test ~35 cm standoff	3054MH0004650001101147C00	1147	autofocus sub-frame for intended Nontron drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3054 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		3054MH0004650001101148C00	1148	intended Nontron drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3054 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
mN002153	Focus Merges	3054MH0001530001101149R00	1149	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3054 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1139-1146 - best focus image product
		3054MH0001530001101150S00	1150	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3054 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1129-1146 - range map product
		3054MH0001530001101151R00	1151	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3054 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1128-1135 - best focus image product
		3054MH0001530001101152S00	1152	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3054 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1128-1135 - range map product
		3054MH0001530001101153R00	1153	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3054 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1117-1124 - best focus image product
		3054MH0001530001101154S00	1154	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3054 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1117-1124 - range map product
mN002153	Focus Merges	3054MH0001530001101155R00	1155	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3054 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1106-1113 - best focus image product
		3054MH0001530001101156S00	1156	intended Nontron drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3054 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1106-1113 - range map product

updated: 15_March_2021

Sol 3056 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		12-Mar-21
camera positions	0	Image ID:
total parent images	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
focus merges performed	0	CDPID:
total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
total parent images + focus merge products	0	

summary of MAHLI activities:		Drill preparation activities at the planned Nontron sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Nontron sample discard pile and the alternate and intended "Portion Characterization" sites.	
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Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Intended Nontron Drill Sample Discard Site Before Discard ~25 cm standoff	3056MH00190001101157C00	1157	autofocus sub-frame for intended Nontron drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 25 cm
		3056MH00190001101158C00	1158	intended Nontron drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 25 cm
mN00197	Alternate Nontron Drill Sample Portion Characterization Site ~25 cm standoff	3056MH00197001101159C00	1159	autofocus sub-frame for alternate Nontron drill sample portion characterization site - before drill attempt - standoff near 25 cm
		3056MH00197001101160C00	1160	alternate Nontron drill sample portion characterization site - before drill attempt - standoff near 25 cm
mN00197	Intended Nontron Drill Sample Portion Characterization Site Before Portion Deposition ~25 cm standoff	3056MH00197001101161C00	1161	autofocus sub-frame for intended Nontron drill sample portion characterization site - before drill attempt and before deposition - standoff near 25 cm
		3056MH00197001101162C00	1162	intended Nontron drill sample portion characterization site - before drill attempt and before deposition - standoff near 25 cm

updated: 25_March_2021

Sol 3068 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	24-Mar-21
camera position	6
total parent images	13
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	13

Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID:	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the Nontron sample discard pile, the Nontron drill hole and the surfaces surrounding SAM inlet #1, with the inlet cover open, a follow-up to Nontron sample drop-offs.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00619	Nontron sample discard pile ~25 cm standoff	3068MH000619001101163C00	1163	autofocus sub-frame for Nontron sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		3068MH000619001101164C00	1164	Nontron sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
mNI00619	Nontron drill hole drilled on Sol 3056 ~25 cm standoff	3068MH000619001101165C00	1165	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Nontron - drilled sol 3056 - standoff near 25 cm
		3068MH000619001101166C00	1166	drill hole in rock named Nontron - drilled sol 3056 - standoff near 25 cm
mNI00774	Nontron drill hole drilled on Sol 3056 ~10 cm standoff	3068MH000774001101167C00	1167	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Nontron - drilled sol 3056 - sub-frame positioned to focus on surface outside hole - standoff near 10 cm
		3068MH000774001101168C00	1168	drill hole in rock named Nontron - drilled sol 3056 - focus based on preceding autofocus sub-frame - standoff near 10 cm
mNI00779	SAM inlet 1 ~20 cm standoff	3068MH000779001101169C00	1169	SAM inlet 1 cover open after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter - manual focus assuming 231 mm working distance
		3068MH000779001101170C00	1170	autofocus sub-frame for SAM inlet 1 cover open after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter - standoff near 20 cm
		3068MH000779001101171C00	1171	SAM inlet 1 cover open after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter - standoff near 20 cm
mNI00122	Nontron sample discard pile APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3068MH00122001101172C00	1172	autofocus sub-frame for Nontron sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3068MH00122001101173C00	1173	Nontron sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
mNI00122	Nontron sample discard pile APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3068MH00122001101174C00	1174	autofocus sub-frame for Nontron sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3068MH00122001101175C00	1175	Nontron sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm

7 Definitions, conventions, and acronyms

7.1 Definitions and conventions

absolute focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a commanded (manual) focus setting. The starting focus position (a stepper motor count), and the incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack, are specified by instrument commanding.

best focus image product

A *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *best focus image product* is a color JPEG that combines the in-focus (or closest to in-focus) elements of the up to 8 *parent images* into a single image. The onboard focus merge software also creates a *range map product*.

focus merge product

Using the methods described by Edgett *et al.* (2012), *focus merge products* are created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. Two products are created, a *best focus image product* and a *range map product*.

MAHLI toolframe +X distance

Same as *standoff distance*. See *standoff distance*.

parent and child images

Every MAHLI image has a *parent image*, the picture originally commanded to be acquired. Upon command, the parent image can spawn children (each a *child image*) onboard the instrument. Examples of children include *thumbnail images*, focus merge products, and any version of the image that is compressed differently than the parent (Edgett *et al.* 2012). While a parent can be an image that was compressed during image acquisition, our best practice since landing on Mars has been to acquire and store (onboard the instrument) most MAHLI images in uncompressed 8-bit form. An uncompressed 8-bit parent image can be commanded for compression some time after acquisition and storage, whereas a parent that was compressed at the time of acquisition cannot be further compressed onboard the instrument. When a parent is stored onboard in uncompressed form, it can be used to create multiple versions of the image, each time with a different compression scheme, for downlink to Earth. Thus, if the image received is over-compressed, we have the option to retrieve it again (as many times as necessary) in a less compressed form. Indeed, the majority of MAHLI images received from Mars have been losslessly compressed children of an uncompressed, 8-bit parent.

range

Used here in the context of describing a focus merge range map product, this term refers to the distance between the front lens element and in-focus elements of the imaged subject in a given MAHLI focus merge product. As each MAHLI focus stack is acquired at a fixed *working distance*, the range denotes the distance between the camera and the relief elements of the target (*i.e.*, subject), as indicated by grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) values in the range map product.

range map product

A grayscale JPEG image *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *range map product* accompanies a *best focus image product*. The grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) can be correlated with knowledge of instrument focus, *working distance*, *range*, and pixel scale.

RATIONALE_DESC

The term, RATIONALE_DESC, comes from the NASA PDS archivists. The RATIONALE_DESC for a given MAHLI image is a text description of the rationale or purpose behind the acquisition of a given MAHLI parent image or onboard focus merge product. Each parent image RATIONALE_DESC provides information that the MAHLI team desired to communicate to data users, such as the intended image target, intended working or standoff distance, intended purpose of the image (e.g., stereo, mosaic, autofocus sub-frame, range-finding), image position in a focus stack, as well as information regarding how the image supports observations made by other MSL science instruments, especially APXS and ChemCam. The RATIONALE_DESC for a focus merge product tells the user which images were merged (on what sol they were acquired and images of which CDPIDs were merged), as well as the focus merge product type (best focus or range map product).

relative focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a starting focus position determined by a preceding instrument command. Usually, this is a focus setting based upon a focus position determined by a preceding autofocus command. The incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack is specified by instrument commanding.

RP distance

RP refers to Rover Planners, the personnel who drive the Curiosity rover and operate its robotic arm. RP distance is equivalent to *standoff distance*. See definition of *standoff distance*.

sol

A Martian day; duration of ~1.027 Earth days.

Sol

A specific Martian sol during the MSL Curiosity mission. Because it landed during local afternoon, the sol that Curiosity arrived on Mars was designated Sol 0 and the first full sol after landing was Sol 1.

standoff distance

Also known as the MAHLI *toolframe distance* and *RP distance*, this is range between the subject photographed and the Y, Z plane defined by the two MAHLI contact sensor probe tips when they are not in contact with a surface. In the MAHLI toolframe, the X axis is equivalent to the instrument's optic (z) axis; the distance between the Y, Z plane and the subject is +X; the -X-axis goes from the Y, Z plane into the camera. *Standoff distance* and *RP distance* are equivalent to the +X MAHLI toolframe distance. MAHLI *standoff distance* is 1.9 cm less than *working distance*.

thumbnail images

Reduced-size versions of MAHLI *parent images* and *focus merge products*, approximately 1/8th size in terms of pixel dimensions. Under most circumstances, a *thumbnail image* is returned to Earth for every *parent image* acquired or *focus merge product* created, whether a full-size version of the *parent image* (or a *child image*) or *focus merge product* is returned or not.

working distance

A photography term that refers to the range between the front lens element of a camera and the subject imaged. MAHLI working distance is 1.9 cm greater than the toolframe (also known as standoff or RP) distance.

7.2 Acronyms

APXS

Alpha Particle X-ray Spectrometer (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CDPID or MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID

Each MAHLI parent image acquired or onboard focus merge product created and stored in the instrument's DEA flash memory is assigned a Camera Data Product ID (CDPID). This identifier, plus the time at which (or sol on which) the data were acquired, uniquely identify each image. The CDPID and sol are incorporated into the image ID. Data acquired by the camera but not stored in the DEA have less unique CDPIDs; these acquisitions have generally been rare and easy for the operations team to track (*i.e.*, 12 such images were obtained during Interplanetary Cruise, only one such image was obtained during the first 1000 sols of operations on Mars).

ChemCam

Chemistry Camera; Laser Induced Breakdown Spectrometer (LIBS) and Remote Microscopic Imager (RMI) (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CheMin

Chemistry and Mineralogy x-ray diffraction (XRD) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF) sample analysis investigation (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CHIMRA

Collection and Handling for Interior Martian Rock Analysis (sample handling and processing subsystem on Curiosity's robotic arm)

DEA

Digital Electronics Assembly, the MAHLI electronics housed inside Curiosity's rover body.

DN

data number (image pixel value)

DOF

image depth of field

DRT

Dust Removal Tool (wire brush tool on Curiosity's robotic arm)

EDR

Experiment Data Record

Hazcam(s)

Hazard cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

ID or image ID

Image identifier (NASA PDS image identifier for MAHLI images and focus merge products).

JPL-Caltech

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California, USA

MAHLI

Mars Hand Lens Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MARDI

Mars Descent Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-34 (also M-34 and M34)

34 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-100 (also M-100 and M100)

100 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MSL

Mars Science Laboratory

MSSS

Malin Space Science Systems, San Diego, California, USA

NASA

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (USA space agency)

Navcam(s)

Navigation cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

PDS

Planetary Data System (NASA planetary science data archives)

QMS

Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

RDR

Reduced Data Record

REMS

Rover Environment and Monitoring Station (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

SAM

Sample Analysis at Mars (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

TLS

Tunable Laser Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

USA

United States of America

UTC

Coordinated Universal Time

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